

Conference Proceeding of International Conference on The Role of AI and Multidisciplinary Research in Shaping a Sustainable Future

Jan 11-13, 2024

Organized by
Kaaf University College, Ghana (West Africa)

In Collaboration with
International Institute for Special Education (IISE), Lucknow
(Affiliated to AKTU and Approved by AICTE)

&

Science Tech Institute, Lucknow, UP

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Edited by

Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh

Prof. Pradeep Sharma

Dr. Seema Tripathi

Dr. D.K. Yadav

**Conference Proceeding of International Conference on The Role of AI and
Multidisciplinary Research in Shaping a Sustainable Future**

Editors

Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh
General Secretary
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Lucknow, UP, India

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Assistant Professor,
Department of Statistics & Demography,
NIHFW, New Delhi

KAAF University College, Ghana(West Africa)

KAAF University College was incorporated in 2006 under the Companies Code Act 179 of 1963. However, admissions started during the 2008/2009 Academic Year with a handful of pioneering students. The school started with the establishment of the Faculty of Engineering and later a Department of Business. Within 4 years, the number had risen to nearly 1000, with the Engineering Faculty having the larger number of students. The school currently has a student population of around 1200 and offers courses in engineering, business, law, nursing and computer science. KNUST serve as our mentor institution and for Engineering and Business, GIMPA for our Law Programme and UDS for Computer Science and Nursing. Presently the college has 158 Teaching Staff and 2594 Students.

International Institute for Special Education (IISE) , Lucknow, UP, India

The class and culture of International Institute for Special Education (IISE), Lucknow is as rich as the city in which it is located. IISE is not merely a Management, IT school and Mass Comm. College, but an Institution that acts as a conversion center where budding professional are transformed into potential managers; equipped with all necessary skills and ethics required to succeed in the corporate world.

IISE is committed towards offering quality education and ensuring placements for students for a affordable fee. Its sprawling lush green campus means the students can look beyond the usual concrete jungles and study in the lap of nature. IISE focuses on holistic development of the students by providing them exposure based management, IT and Mass Communication education. With consistent efforts, we convert the students into human capital and this metamorphosis ultimately leads the students to success. IISE's concern for the welfare of its students lies in its inherent philosophy—'Of the students, by the students, for the students'

Science Tech Institute, Lucknow, UP, India

The Science-Tech is one of the premier Institutes of Lucknow dedicated to organize various academic activities like Conferences, FDP, seminars, workshops and Training programme and Certificates Course in collaboration with many National & International organizations and Institute have own Publications House and Journals to be publish various fields of books, Research papers and Magazine. The Institute is run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow. The Society is working for the development of deprived socio-economic students by providing them quality education.

International Conference on The Role of AI and Multidisciplinary Research in Shaping a Sustainable Future

The International Conference on "The Role of AI and Multidisciplinary Research in Shaping a Sustainable Future" is a pioneering gathering of scholars, researchers, and practitioners across the globe. This event serves as a pivotal platform for exchanging insights and innovations in the domains of Artificial Intelligence and Multidisciplinary Research. With a focus on sustainability, it seeks to explore how AI, coupled with a multidisciplinary approach, can address the pressing challenges of our time, from environmental conservation to social equity. The conference provides an opportunity to bridge the gap between academia and industry, fostering collaborations that pave the way for a more sustainable and technologically advanced world . Conference Theme: The conference's central theme, "The Role of AI and Multidisciplinary Research in Shaping a Sustainable Future," embodies a profound vision. It underscores the pivotal role that Artificial Intelligence plays in revolutionizing various fields, including ecology, healthcare, finance, and education. Moreover, the theme emphasizes the critical need for a multidisciplinary approach, acknowledging that sustainability challenges require diverse perspectives and expertise. Attendees will delve into discussions on how AI can drive sustainable practices, enabling us to tackle complex global issues such as climate change, resource depletion, and societal inequalities. This theme encourages attendees to think innovatively and collaboratively, setting the stage for transformative solutions and a more promising future.

International & National Advisory Board

Prof. D.K Sharma, University of Maryland, USA
Prof. O. P.Yadav, North Dakota State University, USA
Prof. Alok Kumar Chakarwar Vice-Chancellor, GGU C.G India
Prof. Anil Shukla,Vice-Chancellor, MDSU Rajasthan, India
Prof. S.P.Tripathi, Vice-Chancellor, IGNTU, MP, Amarkantak, India
Prof. M. Mirja Ex-VC , KCMLU Lucknow, UP, India
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Mr. Ousman Kennedy, Lecturer, Blantyre International University, Malawi
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Prof. (Dr.) Kaman Singh, BBAU Lucknow. UP
Prof. D.K. Awasthi, Jai Naryan PG College, Lucknow, UP
Prof.(Dr.) Om Prakash Singh, Principal, Digvijay Nath P.G College Gorakhpur, UP
Prof. S. Shabihe Raza Baqri Principal, Shia PG.College, Lucknow, UP, India
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Prof. Parikshit Singh, Digvijay Nath P.G College Gorakhpur, UP
Dr. Mahendra Agnihotri, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, UP, India
Dr. Atul Srivastava, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, UP, India
Dr. K.K Yadav, Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia Institute of Medical Sciences, Lucknow
Dr. Sushila, K.M Govt. Girls P.G. College, Noida, U.P
Dr. Zeenat Kashmeeri Dada Ramchand Bakhru Sindhu Mahavidyalaya, Nagpur
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Dr. Shailendra Kumar, Bundelkhand University Jhansi
Dr. Jahan Ara, Karamat Hushain Degree College Lucknow
Dr Mohd Naseem Siddiqui, Mumtaz P.G.College, Lucknow
Dr. K.C. Dubey, Shia PG College, Lucknow, UP, India
Dr. Pushpendra Singh, DSMNRU, Lucknow, UP, India
Mr. Tarun Bose, IISE, Lucknow, UP, India
Mr. Saurabh Srivastava, IISE, Lucknow, UP, India

❖ Awards

1.Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society Award for Best Research Presentation “Theme based” (1500/- Cash Prize).

KAAF UNIVERSITY COLLEGE

DEPARTMENT OF LAW & POLITICAL SCIENCE

Nana Charles Osei-Bonsu
Dean, Faculty of Law
KAAF University College
Gomoa Fetteh , Kakraba-Kasoa,
Ghana
P.O.Box WU 177

MESSAGE

I am extremely excited to welcome you all to this important webinar on “ The role of AI and multidisciplinary research in shaping a sustainable future “(11th-13th Jan- 2024)

As you are undoubtedly aware, AI has become increasingly important in our educational field and it has great impact on our lecturers and students. AI has the potential to revolutionize the way we teach, research and learn and we must be prepared to face new opportunities and challenges. At the end of the workshop, we shall acknowledge the importance of the potential of AI in enhancing the research and learning experience of academics like us.

I respectfully urge you to devote all your time and attention so as gain maximum benefit from this seminar.

Thank you very much

FACULTY OF LAW
OFFICE OF THE DEAN
KAAF UNIVERSITY COLLEGE
GPS - 470 - 09 - 24

Best Regards

Mrs. Shweta Singh
Chairman,
MKSES Educational Society
Lucknow, UP, India

Message

It gives me immense pleasure to share that **KAAF University College, Ghana (West Africa) & International Institute for Special Education (IISE) , Lucknow, UP, India Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize “ **International Conference on The Role of AI and Multidisciplinary Research in Shaping a Sustainable Future Jan 11- 13, 2024**”.

The theme of the conference is “**International Conference on The Role of AI and Multidisciplinary Research in Shaping a Sustainable Future Jan 11- 13, 2024**”.

The conference will offer a great opportunity to discuss important issues, researches and topics from varied fields and will allow exchange of knowledge, ideas.

This conference is also an opportunity to meet virtually many eminent faculty, scholars and health specialists of national and international repute on a common platform.

I & my team ensure that the audience will experience the exchange of scientific knowledge and return with a satisfactory take home message.

[Shweta Singh]

IISE · GROUP OF INSTITUTIONS

Campus: Kanchana Bihari Marg (Off Ring Road Via Kalyanpur) Lucknow-226022(U.P.) India.

E-mail: iise@iiseindia.com, Info@iiseindia.com | **Website:** www.iiseindia.com

Phone: +91-7236002222 | 9453350199

Firdous Siddiqui
CMD
IISE Group of Institutions,
Lucknow, U.P. India

Message

Dear Participants, Speakers and Organizers

I am delighted to announce the successful completion of the **Online International Conference on "The Role of AI and Multidisciplinary Research in Shaping a Sustainable Future."** (Jan 11–13, 2024). It is with great pleasure and gratitude that I extend my heartfelt thanks to each one of you for contributing to the success of this groundbreaking event.

Throughout the conference, I witnessed thought-provoking discussions, insightful presentations, and the exchange of innovative ideas that underscored the pivotal role of AI and multidisciplinary research in shaping a sustainable future for our global community.

I extend my deepest appreciation to our distinguished speakers for sharing their expertise and vision. Special thanks are also due to the organizing committee, sponsors, and everyone who worked tirelessly behind the scenes to make this event a resounding success.

As we reflect on the achievements of this conference, I look forward to the continued impact of the knowledge shared and collaborations formed. Let us carry forward the spirit of innovation and cooperation as we collectively strive towards a future that harnesses the power of AI and multidisciplinary research for the betterment of our world.

Thank you for being a part of this remarkable journey. We anticipate even greater strides in the pursuit of a sustainable and technologically advanced future.

Dated : 15.01.2024

Firdous Siddiqui
CMD

Our Institutes

***International Institute for Special Education, Lucknow**

***Internet Institute for Special Education, Lucknow**

***Film Institute of eMITS, Lucknow**

KAAF UNIVERSITY COLLEGE

DEPARTMENT OF LAW & POLITICAL SCIENCE

Prof. Pradeep Sharma
Department of Law
KAAF University College
Gomoa Fetteh, Kakraba-Kasoa,
Ghana
P.O. Box WU 177,

MESSAGE

Dear Sir,

It is a matter of great honor and privilege to be the part of this International Conference. The topic, "The Role of AI and Multidisciplinary Research in Shaping a Sustainable Future", (11th-13th Jan- 2024) is a burning and widely discussed issue in the present scenario. You can find the role of Artificial Intelligence at every corner of the word in various fields of human development. Academic research is also one of the progressive area in this regard. Hopefully his Conference will provide a platform to the researchers and academicians to enrich their methodological and analytical skills.

On behalf of my institution, I whole heartily thank the Director, Chairman, Learned Colleagues, Presiding Officer, Presenters and above all the Organizing Committee of this Conference. May you excel in your future endeavours. May your spirit of excellence achieve zenith..... Thank you

Prof. (Dr.) Pradeep Sharma
Department of Law
KAAF University College

Best Regards

Dr. Arun Kumar Shukla
Director
International Institute for Special Education,
Lucknow, U.P. India

Message

I am highly pleased to extend my warmest congratulations to each and every one of you on the successful completion of our recent **Online International Conference on “The Role of AI and Multidisciplinary Research in Shaping a Sustainable Future” (Jan 11–13, 2024) Organized by Kaaf University College, Ghana (West Africa) In Collaboration with International Institute for Special Education (IISE), Lucknow & Science-Tech Institute, Lucknow, UP.** Your dedication, hard work, and collaborative spirit have truly made this event a resounding success.

Throughout the conference, we witnessed the exchange of cutting-edge ideas, valuable insights, and innovative research, creating a dynamic and enriching environment for all participants. The high level of engagement and active participation showcased the commitment of our diverse community to advancing knowledge and fostering meaningful connections.

The success of this conference is a testament to the collective efforts of everyone involved, from the organizing committee and speakers to the sponsors and attendees. Your passion for pushing the boundaries of knowledge and promoting collaboration across borders has undoubtedly contributed to the overall success of this event.

As we reflect on the accomplishments of the conference, let us also recognize the potential impact of the ideas and collaborations that have emerged. It is through events like these that we pave the way for progress, create lasting networks, and inspire future breakthroughs.

Once again, congratulations to each one of you. Your commitment to excellence has not only elevated the reputation of our institution but has also advanced our shared goals in research, innovation, and international cooperation.

Thank you for making this conference a memorable and impactful experience. I look forward to the continued success of our collaborative endeavors.

Dated : 14.01.2024

Dr. Arun Kumar Shukla

Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh
General Secretary,
MKSES Educational Society
Lucknow, UP, India

Message

On behalf of the whole organizing team, it gives me immense pleasure to share that **KAAF University College, Ghana (West Africa) & International Institute for Special Education (IISE), Lucknow, UP, India Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize “**International Conference on The Role of AI and Multidisciplinary Research in Shaping a Sustainable Future Jan 11- 13, 2024**”.

I am sure that this online gathering will provide a common platform for academicians of different branches (Medical sciences, Humanities etc.), public health experts & researchers to put forth their research studies and works.

I take this opportunity to acknowledge all the concerned authorities or persons for their permission, continuous support and guidance in arranging this conference. I am sure that this conference will succeed in the walk on Commerce this path for improving the various soft skills of faculties and students in varied fields.

[Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh]

International Conference on The Role of AI and Multidisciplinary Research in Shaping a Sustainable Future

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Science Tech Institute, Lucknow, UP

Details of Programe Schedule

DAY-1 (11th Jan, 2024)

For Technical Support Contact

Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh (8299547952)

Dr. Dharmendra Kumar Yadav (8840112492)

WhatsApp group Chat link: <https://chat.whatsapp.com/Go32gEaU6JnKJgBQxg0sBv>

Inaugural Session Hosted by: Dr. Dharmendra Yadav,	
Zoom link: https://us02web.zoom.us/j/85989611969?pwd=cGFUcFQvN3hDOTVQOGRFTnJzOFFRQT09	
Meeting id- 859 8961 1969 Password- 135206	
11:00 AM-12PM	INAUGURATION AND WELCOME ADDRESS BY Conference Chair/Conveners/ Organizing Secretaries
11:45-12:15 PM Key Note Speaker	Prof. N.B. Singh (Emeritus professor at Chemistry Deptt., SBSR & Research and Technology Development Centre, Sharda University)
IT01 12:15-12.45 PM	Dr. Harsha Bhargvi , Assistant Director, NGMA, Ministry of Culture, Govt of India
12:45-1.15 PM IT02	Dr. Neha Singh :- “Fetomaternal outcomes in Pregnant Women Infected with COVID-19 during 3rd Trimester”
1:15-1:40 PM IT03	Dr. S.K Yadav :- “Prediction of monkeypox cases through Statistical and Machine learning methods”
1.40-2:05 PM IT04	Mrs. Usha Malik :-“ Artificial Intelligence in Nursing”
2.05 PM-2:30PM IT05	Dr. Vineet Kumar :- “AI Based Tools for Literature Search”

2.30 to 3.30 PM Day 1 (11th Jan,2024) **Session Chair: Dr.Susheel Kumar Singh**
Oral Presentation **Mobile No.- 8299547952**
Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/85989611969?pwd=cGFUcFQvN3hDOTVQOGRFTnJzOFFRQT09>
Meeting id- 859 8961 1969 Password- 135206
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A1	Dr.ANJANA VERMA	Thin layer chromatography: A Tool for assessment of phytochemicals from Medicinal plants
A2	Dr.Suneeta Pandey	Harnessing the artificial intelligence in sustainable crop improvement
A3	Dr.Arпита kackar	Unveiling Cognitive Biases in AI- driven Decision Making for Sustainability
A4&A39	Dr.Shailesh Jain	How "Secure is Patient Data"? Assessing measures taken by healthcare institutions and professionals in promoting cybersecurity
A5	Dr.BADHUSHA M H N	Influencer Marketing and AI Home Appliances: Assessing the Impact of Social Media Endorsements on Consumer Choices
A6	Mr.VISHNU PRASAD YADAV	Research on the physical and chemical compatibility of herbal pharmaceutical excipients with synthetic drugs

2.30 to 3.30 PM Day -1 (11th Jan,2024) Parallel Session **Session Chair: Prof. Manoj Kumar Sharma**
Email: susheelsingh489@gmail.com **Mobile No.- 8299547952**
Oral Presentation
Zoom link: <https://us04web.zoom.us/j/72692568783?pwd=tQSdw8P5mzaaSjA1kRhKvCabWV185X.1>
Meeting id- 726 9256 8783 Password: 05L2M6
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

A7	Mr.TUSHAR SRIVASTAVA	THE NEED OF LAWS RELATING TO AI WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DEVELOPING ECONOMIES
A8	Dr.Priyanka Singh	Application of AI in diagnosis of Oral lesions
A9	Prof.Asmat Parveen	Evaluation of Public Health-Care Services of District Hospital Budgam Kashmir Valley India.
A10	Dr.Vanga.Rajani	Studies on Phytoplankton Diversity of Perennial Lake at Karimnagar District, Telangana State, India
A11	Dr. Nagapati. Prabhakar. Bhat	EVALUATION OF ANXIOLYTIC PROPERTIES OF HYDRO-ALCOHOLIC EXTRACT OF AEGLE MARMELOS FRUIT (BAEL FRUIT) IN SWISS ALBINO MICE
A12	Mrs.SOMA RANI KARAN	AI in Agriculture

3.30 to 4.30 PM Day-1 (11th Jan,2024)			Session Chair: Dr. Dharmendra Kumar Yadav		
Oral Presentation					
Zoom link: https://us02web.zoom.us/j/85989611969?pwd=cGFUcFQvN3hDOTVQOGRFTnJzOFFRQT09					
Meeting id- 859 8961 1969 Password- 35206					
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation					
ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC			
A13	Dr.Sanjaykumar Ramchandra Torane	Temporal and structural changes in cost of groundnut cultivation in India			
A14	Dr.TORANE SNEHA SANJAY	Temporal and structural changes in cost of finger millet cultivation in India.			
A15	Mrs.P.JABEENA BEGUM	A STUDY ON PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF STEM EXTRACT OF HIBISCUS SABDARIFFA, LINN.			
A16	Dr.ASHWINI KUMAR	Intermittent behaviour of charged particle spectra in relativistic nuclear collisions			
A17	Prof.dhiraj kumar Srivastava	Prevalence of Diabetes Peripheral Neuropathy among Type 2 Diabetic Mellitus in Urban Etawah.			
A18	Prof. Deepti Shukla	Sports as a career			
3.30 to 4.30 PM Day1 (11th Jan,2024)			Parallel Session Session Chair : Dr. Abhishek Tripathi		
Email: susheelsingh487@gmail.com			Oral Presentation		
Zoom link:					
https://us04web.zoom.us/j/75402240432?pwd=VXySi26sAf0chaADU47DkuKI4qXrJO.1					
Meeting id- 754 0224 0432 Password- 2Typ6g					
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation					
A19	Dr.Rashmi Bala	CHALLENGES AND ISSUES IN NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020			
A20	Dr.Sheo Prakash Dwivedi	INTEGRATED TEACHER EDUCATION PROGRAMME(ITEP) OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES			
A21	Mr.K. Jegadeesan	Vibration Energy Harvester Design and Analysis Using Laminated Composite Material			
A22	Mr.Ashok Singh	Synthesis and characterization and molecular docking of Ni(II) complex with schiff base derived from o- vanillin and 4-nitro- o -phenylene diamine			
A23	Prof.Mamta Patel	An Analytical Study on Dark Figures of Crimes against Scheduled Tribes			
A24	Mrs.Swathi K	REPURPOSING OF THE PLANT COMPOUNDS Molecular Docking of Taxus wallichiana™ compounds as a New Potential Inhibitor for Breast Cancer			
4.30- 6.00 PM Day-1 (11th Jan,2024)			Session Chair Dr. Praveen Kumar Misra		
Oral Presentation			Dr. Nirmal Srivastava		
Zoom link: https://us02web.zoom.us/j/85989611969?pwd=cGFUcFQvN3hDOTVQOGRFTnJzOFFRQT09					
Meeting id- 859 8961 1969 Password- 135206					
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation					
ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC			
A25	Dr.Simmi	BER Analysis of Proposed Scheme coded DWT-OFDM in comparison to DWT-OFDM under different simulation conditions			
A26	Miss.Harpreet Kaur	Allelopathy: A Natural Way Towards Weed Management			

A27	Dr.Namrata Roy	The role of Artificial Intelligence in advancing medical education and research.
A28	Dr.Dr. Poonam Choudhary	Incorporation of Artificial Intelligence in Garbhasanskar to enhance Cosmic impact of senses (panchhindriya) on fetus
A29	Dr.Vedapathak Macchindra Damaji	Export Competitiveness of Dairy Farming in India
A30, A31&A182	Dr.Dhyanadipta Panda	ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND ITS INTEMPERANCE IN THE HR DOMAIN
A30, A31&A182	Mrs.Chandrlekha Rath	ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND ITS INTEMPERANCE IN THE HR DOMAIN
A32	Prof.Mamta Patel	Incarcerated Drug Traffickers: Reformation Programs for Offenders in Prison
A33	Prof.Jagmohan Singh Negi	Synthesis and Fungicidal Activity of novel 3-Chloro-4 (3-iodo-4- hydroxy -5-methoxy)â€”2-azetidinone and their Derivatives
A34	Prof.MANE KAVITA BABAN	Statistical Analysis and prediction of eligible candidates for promotion

6.30 to 10.30 PM Day-1 (11th Jan,2024)

Session-Chair: Dr. Abhi Sarika Bharti

Dr. Simpal Kumari

Mobile No. -9452697013, 9415891108

Oral Presentation

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/85989611969?pwd=cGFUcFQvN3hDOTVQOGRFTnJzOFFRQT09>

Meeting id- 859 8961 1969 Password- 135206

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral

Presentation

A35	Dr Prachi bisht	Psychological wellbeing of the spouses of deployed and non-deployed commissioned officers of Indian Armed Forces: A comparative Study
A36	Dr.DIGAMBAR KASHINATH PATIL	Preparation and Spectral Characterization of Cerium metal complexes.
A37	Dr.M. Usha Rani	Impact of self directed learning among phase 1 MBBS students in physiology
A38	Mrs.Nisha Kumari	Female Education and Employment
A4&A39	Dr.Sahil Thakar	How "Secure is Patient Data"? Assessing measures taken by healthcare institutions and professionals in promoting cybersecurity
A40	Dr.Gajraj Singh	Basic Principles and Applications of Applied Statistics in Real World
A41	Dr.Kuldip singh sandhu	NA
A42	Dr.Sunita Singh	NA
A43	Prof.Dr.(Prof.)Anil K. Sahni	AI' & Its Role In Health Care, Medical Education & Research
A44	Dr.Ritu Mahajan	Effect of growth regulators on callus mediated shoot organogenesis in <i>Gloriosa superba</i> L.
A45	Dr.Gajarmal Amit Ashok	â€”Ayurveda Remedies Used In the Mastitis Of Dairy Animals - A Reviewâ€”
A46	Dr.Dr Rasmirekha Behera	Budesonide Combination A Better Clinical Approach in Comparison to Cyclosporine in Treatment of Autoimmune Hepatitis
A47	Dr.Aparnaa Arun Kulkarni	Thyroid Disease prediction by using Statistical Techniques
A48&A153	Dr.Suparna Naresh	Gen AI in Corporate Communication: A Stakeholder Theory Perspective
A49	Dr.MALARKODI. V	ANALYSIS OF LIPID PROFILE IN PLHA

A50	Dr.Suparna Naresh	Role of Influencer Marketing and its Impact on Brand and Brand Loyalty : A Case Study on Skincare Brand.
A51&A114	Dr.Rajni Pandey	Indian Laws for Women - From Tradition to Transformation
A52	Dr.Sunila Sangappa	Oral Health Practices Amongst Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients- Cross Sectional Survey
A53	Dr.Vikramaditya Upmanyu	-
A54	Dr.Hariom Dwivedi	Role of astrophysics in controlling motion of electron
A55	Mrs.Tushara Modugu	Utilizing Artificial Intelligence in the Field of Plant Breeding
A56	Dr.Sampurna Guha	Understanding the Role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Promoting and Fostering Psychological Immunity (PI) Among Adolescents
A57	Dr.Nisha Kapoor	Analysis of root extract of glycyrrhiza glabra L. for its phytochemical potential
A58	Prof.Shaikh Marziya	Personal Key Indicators of Heart Disease
A59	Dr.Suparna Naresh	Examining Consumer Behavior and Brand Perception in Quick-Commerce Applications
A60	Dr.Suparna Naresh	Studying the Unconventional Marketing Strategies of Fintech Giant (CRED)
A61	Dr.AJAY KUMAR	NA
A62	Dr.Suparna Naresh	Trends In The Viewer Perception Of Remake Content In Bollywood Movies
A63 & A177	Dr.Siddegowda Shantharaju	Representation of Therapy and Therapists in Indian Movies and TV Series: An Examination of Accuracy, Influence, and Perception
A64	Dr.Suparna Naresh	Indian Cinema and Political Propaganda: The interplay of Ideologies, Politics, and People's Perception.
A65	Dr.Suparna Naresh	Role of Public Relations Strategies in the success of Tamil Movies
A66	Dr.Punjab Agricultural University	A New dimension in Artificial Intelligence: Its challenges and opportunities
A67	Dr. Lizby Anu Mathews	Qualitative Examination of Successive Extracts of Sphaeranthus indicus

DAY-2(12th Jan 2024)

6.00 AM to 9.00AM Day 2 (12th Jan,2024)		Session Chair: Dr.Yashaswi Singh Dr.Shipra Tripathi Mobile No. -8299547952
Oral/Poster Presentation		Zoom link: https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83279099405?pwd=R0piZ3lCZlZyVU1BK2IUS1pKQmZSsz09
Meeting id- 832 7909 9405 Password- 724195		Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation
ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A68	Mrs.V B MALLESWARI	INTERSECTION OF COPYRIGHT AND RIGHT TO PRIVACY IN THE DIGITAL ERA
A69	Miss.BHANU CHADHA	Treatment of Divorce and Custody in Manju Kapur's Custody
A70	Mr.Dhanaji Pandurang Bhanvase	A Study of Different Data Mining Techniques used for Rainfall Prediction
A71	Miss.Afifa Aftab	Frailty and Pre frailty among Adults of 45+ Age group
A72	Mr.Chandra Prakash Yadav	Evaporative cooling of solar panel
A73	Mr.Dhanaji Pandurang Bhanvase	A Study of Different Data Mining Techniques used for Rainfall Prediction
A74	Miss.Sanjoli Kedia	Essential Employable Skills for Management Graduates:A corporate Perspective
A75	Mr.Tarun Bose	Digital Transformation and Adoption of Retail Internet Banking: A Study of Demographic Factors
A76	Miss.Arunya KG	Weather Prediction Applications: Empowering farmers with the real-time data
A77	Miss.Nelofar Bashir	Breast cancer diagnosis using models based on convolutional neural networks
A78	Miss. Nikhat Perveen	Moral Policing and Gender-Based Violence
A79	Miss.Reetika Bagauli	Oxygen bleaching of Anthocephalus indicus kraft pulps and bleaching effluents characterization
A80	Mr.Prabal Pratap Singh	आर्टिफिशियल इंटेलिजेंस- दुष्प्रचार का खतरनाक हथियार बनती डीपफेक तकनीक
A81	Mr.Lokesh Chauhan	A Biased Perception of Domestic Violence Against Men
A82	Dr.Yogesh Chandra	Government Health Expenditure as a Percentage of GDP and its Impact on Sustainable Development in Healthcare in India
A83	Miss.Sadhna Yadav	Evaluating Transformations: The Impact of Village Health Sanitation and Nutrition Day Program in India
A84	Mr.Hormot Rynniaw Pyngrope	EFFECT OF JOINT TRACTION ON OSTEOARTHRITIS OF KNEE- A REVIEW OF LITERATURE
A85	Mrs.SWATI SATISH MANE	Black Tea Consumption and Cancer Prevention: Current Evidence and Future Directions

9.00 AM to 12.00PM Day 2 (12th Jan, 2024)

Session Chair: Dr. Seema Tripathi

Oral /Poster Presentation

Mobile No. -8299547952

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83279099405?pwd=R0piZ3lCZlZyVU1BK2lUS1pKQmZSsz09>

Meeting id- 832 7909 9405 Password- 724195

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A86	Miss.Uddagiri Yojitha	Synergizing Theory and Insight: An Integrated Theoretical Framework with HR Analytics for Understanding Employee Attrition Dynamics
A87	Miss.Lisha	Exploring Range of mee for Probing Neutrino Hierarchies of Majorana Neutrino Mass Matrix
A88	Mr.Vikas Kumar Sharma	An Analytical Study on Dark Figures of Crime against Scheduled Tribes
A89	Miss.Kritika Tiwari	SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: FROM TRADITIONAL METHODS TO ONLINE ADVANCEMENT
A90	Miss.Trishna Saikia Baruah	EFFECT OF TELEREHABILITATION IN STROKE PATIENTS WITH BALANCE IMPAIRMENT- A LITERATURE REVIEW
A91	Miss.MUSKAN VERMA	Novel delivery of essential oil
A92	Miss.Pooja Swami	Customer-Centric Marketing: How AI is Shaping Customer Experiences in Modern Marketing
A93	Miss.Zoya Amreen	UNLOCKING n nature's SECRET:HOW IS AI REVOLUTIONISING NATURAL PRODUCT DISCOVERY IN MEDICINAL PLANT (DATURA STRAMONIUM)
A94	Mr.RAHUL KUMAR	Linking Autonomic Nervous system to the Progression of Atherosclerosis: A mini-review
A95	Miss.Shriyansha	The insight of artificial intelligence (AI) in drug discovery and development
A96	Miss.Shruti Bhonsle	Artificial Intelligence and Organ Donation: Future Potential
A97	Miss.Jallu Pranaya	Molecular and physiological approaches for improvement of stay green trait in agricultural crops and their utility
A98	Miss.Rakhi R. Maurya	"Mapping and assessing the extent of heavy metal-contaminated soils in different regions of Rajasthanâ€.
A99	Miss.Anuradha Paul	THE ROLE OF TELEVISION IN THE DISSEMINATION OF AGRICULTURE INFORMATION AMONG FARMER
A100	Miss.Kavitha. R	IN SILICO IDENTIFICATIIdssON OF POTENTIAL INHIBITORS OF COVID-19 PROTEASE FROM ABRUS PRECATORIUS
A101	Miss.Vineeta	Human Nature and Genetic Enhancement Technology: A Philosophical Analysis
A102	Miss.PUJARI Ashwini Krushnat	Study of Feminism in Indian Context
A103	Mr.Rupesh Kumar Upadhyay	Incarcerated Drug Traffickers: Reformation Programs for Offenders in Prison
A104	Miss.Sadhana Rai	Phytochemical analysis of methanolic crude extract of fungal endophytes obtained from psoralea corylifolia Linn.

INVITED TALKS- DAY-2(12th Jan 2024)
(IT08-IT10)

Session chair: Dr. Roop Kumar
Dr. Seeta Ram Pal
Mobile No. -8299547952

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83279099405?pwd=R0piZ3lCZlZyVU1BK2lUS1pKQmZSZz09>
Meeting id- 832 7909 9405 Password- 724195

12:00-12.20 PM
IT06
Dr.Omkar Kanneboyena :- “Role of Non Timber Forest Products for tribal women livelihood :a case study in Adilabad district of Telangana, India”

12-20- 12:40 PM
IT07
Dr. Priyanka Singh:-“ Use of Artificial intelligence in the diagnosis of Oral Cancer”

12.40-1:00 PM
IT08
Dr. Nishant Kumar:-“ Systematic Study of Mg Doped ZnO Thick Films”

1.00 to 5.00PM Day 2 (12th Jan,2024)
Oral Presentation

Session Chair: Dr. Dilshad Ahmad Anshari
Mobile No. -9450210623

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83279099405?pwd=R0piZ3lCZlZyVU1BK2lUS1pKQmZSZz09>
Meeting id- 832 7909 9405 Password- 724195
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A105	Mr.Pankaj Bisht	Assessing CPEC and its Security Implications for India
A106	Mr.Kumara Nanda	CPEC and the Rise of Violence in Balochistan
A107	Dr.HIRA KANT SINGH	A/F
A108	Dr.ANITHA	-
A109	Mr.Presenjit	Development of novel analogues of Ampyrone-Schiff Bases for the identification of potential inhibitors targeting the main protease of SARS-CoV-2 through interaction-based computational studies
A110	Mr.Swapnil Ravindra Mouje	Preparation and Characterization of Biopolymer anchored Schiff Base Metal Complexes
A111	Mr.Suresh Mansukhe	Green HRM practices in Indian Railways
A112	Mr.SHUBHAM PUSHKAR	Participation
A113	Mrs.SHRUTI MISHRA	Synthesis and Spectral characterization of thiosemicarbazone ligands
A51&A114	Mrs.Kritika	Indian laws for women -From Tradition to Transformation
A115	Mr.Sugata Datta	Assessing Risks in Food Delivery Packaging in India: BPA and Phthalates Migration
A116	Mr.Ashish Yadav	NA

A117	Dr.VIKRANT KHARE	Enhancing Crop Resilience and Yield through Advanced Genome Editing Techniques
A118	Mrs.Ashly Elizabeth Koshy	On estimation of multicomponent Stress-Strength Reliability for Exponentiated Gumbel Distribution when all the Parameters are Different
A119	Mr.Sudarshan Varma	Role of Artificial Intelligence on Sustainable Agriculture and Environment Conservation
A120	Mr.RAVICHANDRA	The pivotal role of 'R' software in the detection of spore discharge and dispersal of <i>Alternaria porri</i> incitant of purple blotch of onion, in hotspot regions of southern Karnataka
A121	Shiji T M and Kannan vadakkadathmeethal	A PRELIMINARY INVESTIGATION OF THE SYNERGISTIC EFFECT OF METHOTREXATE AND GLUCOSAMINE ON HUMAN COLON ADENOCARCINOMA CELL LINE, HT29.
A122	Miss.Surabhi Shakya	Microbiome - its importance and functions in skin diseases
A123	Dr.Sudhamani Kalluru	Artificial Intelligence in Crop Improvement
A124	Mr.Manthesha H D	Artificial intelligence; A new tool for plant disease diagnosis and detection
A125	Dr.Aqsa Mujaddadi	Effect of 12 weeks high intensity interval training on heart rate variability in patients with obesity-related hypertension: A Randomized control Trial
A126	Miss.JYOTI	A New dimension in Artificial Intelligence:Its challenges and opportunities
A127	Mr.Vikas Upadhyay	Effect of 20-min yoga module on mental health outcomes of healthcare workers: a pilot randomized controlled trial
A128	Dr.NEERJA	The Application of Artificial Intelligence:An analytical study
A129	Miss.Anita Verma	Immediate effect of yoga module on state anxiety and selective attention among healthcare workers in a tertiary care hospital of Uttarakhand
A130	Mrs.Siya Bhatia	Publicly Financed Health Insurance Policies and Sustainable Development: An Integrated Analysis of India's Path towards Universal Health Coverage
A131	Miss.Umme Sulaim	Only participation

6.00 PM to 10.00 PM Day2 (12th Jan,2024)

Session Chair: Dr. Sangeeta Yadav

Oral & Poster Presentation

Dr. Gunjan Singh

Mobile. No.8299547952

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83279099405?pwd=R0piZ3lCZlZyVU1BK2lUS1pKQmZSdz09>

Meeting id- 832 7909 9405 Password- 724195

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A132	Dr.Abhay chavda	Comparison of the effect of two different buffer systems used for the estimation of serum Alkaline Phosphatase on interpretation of the test results.
A133	Miss.Shweta Tyagi	Public Perceptions and Political Perspectives on Social Security Reform
A134	Mr.Chekuri Sri Sumanth	Intelligent Traffic System - Review
A135	Mr.Aman Kanda	Impact of chronic constipation on aerobic endurance in young adults
A136	Dr.G sree krishna	NIL
A137	Dr.ANNIE SANDHU	NA
A138	Miss.Ankita Kumari	Role of serology in covid diagnosis
A139	Miss.Tarannum	study of jaundice
A140	Miss.Neha	Effect of anemia On movement During gascescinal period.
A141	Mr.NIPENDER SINGH PAL	Alterations of Red cell indices during iron deficiency anemia
A142	Miss.Ishika Yogesh Nahar	Role of Influencer Marketing and its Impact on Brand and Brand Loyalty : A Case Study on Skincare Brand.
A143	Miss.Shivangi Kashaudhan	Linking local producers to a global customer base leading to rural success in cyber market
A144	Mr.Pratosh kumar	Cellular metabolism impacts disease
A145	Miss.Megha agarwal	A study on sentiment analysis in teaching learning scenario
A146	Miss.Khushi Singh Parmar	Decoding the Roots of Agony: Exploring the Depths of Cancer-Related Neuropathic Pain
A147	Miss.Shree Kavya D K	A study on sexual harassment for women at workplace and preventing measures
A148	Dr.Zoya Khan	Case Report : Capecitabine causing hand & foot Syndrome
A149	Dr.Sundhareshwaran C	"Behind the Degrees: Decoding Imposter Syndrome Among Medical Students from Eastern India"

A150	Dr.Madhur Shroff	EVALUATION OF GLASGOW (IMRIE) SCORE, CRP AND BALTHAZAR SCORE IN PREDICTING SEVERITY OF ACUTE PANCREATITIS
A151	Dr.Priya Ranjita Patnaik	EFFECT OF IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA ON HbA1C(GLYCOSYLATED HEMOGLOBIN) IN FEMALES WITH CONTROLLED DIABETES MELLITUS
A152	Miss.Ridhima Chopra	Social Television and the Dynamics of Gender Representation through it: A case study on the Netflix Original Series, YOU
A48 & A153	Miss.Rashmi Chacko	Gen AI in Corporate Communication: A Stakeholder Theory Perspective
A154	Miss.Mehak	Effect of Physiotherapy Intervention of Pain and Quality of Life in Cervical Radiculopathy
A155	Dr.Neehal Lingam	A STUDY TO FIND THE USAGE OF SALIVARY CREATININE AS AN ALTERNATIVE TO SERUM CREATININE IN ESTIMATING RENAL FUNCTION IN HEALTHY INDIVIDUALS
A156	Mr.Josy Sam Cheriyan	THE IMPACT OF NOSTALGIA AND FORESTALGIA MARKETING ON THE YOUNG ADULT CONSUMERS IN INDIA

DAY-3 (13th Jan 2024)

7.00AM - 9:00 PM Day-3 (13th Jan,2024) Session-Chair: Dr. Priyanka Singh
Oral & Poster presentations Mobile No- 8299547952
Zoom link:
<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/82875231102?pwd=ZVZaaVYzb3Q0QjE3Smh2bmJIWE8rZz09>
Meeting id- 828 7523 1102 Password 437865
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation & 05 min for PPriyaoster presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A222	Dr.Jasneet Sudan	Chat GPT for Research Writing
A223	Dr.VISHAL SRIVASTAV	Unleashing the Power of Artificial Intelligence in E-commerce for Enhanced Customer Experiences and Business Optimization
A224	Mr.Sanjeev Tiwari	Design a Conceptual Framework rooted in data science principles for the evaluation of how effectively machine learning solutions perform
A225	Mr.CHANDRA BHUSHAN	The Evolution and Impact of Data Science in the Modern Era
A226	Dr.Chavan M	Effect of Drugs Modulating RAAS on Excitatory and Inhibitory Neurotransmitters of Brain In Chemically Induced Experimental Animal Models of Neurodegeneration: A Preclinical Neuropharmacological Screening Study
A227	Dr.Madhav RC	Drugs Blocking Rennin Angiotensin Aldosterone System Had Favorable Significant Outcome on Exploratory Behavioural Endpoints In Experimentally Induced Models of Neurodegenerative Disorders
A228	Dr.Bai MK	Drugs Interfering RAAS and Their Effect On Induced Anxiety In Laboratory Animals: An In Vivo Randomized Experimental Study
A229	Dr.KM Bai	Drugs Targeting Rennin Angiotensin Aldosterone System Had Favorable Outcome on Behavioural Parameters in Chemically Induced Experimental Models of Parkinson's Disease
A230	Dr.Prakash KG	Drugs Modulating RAAS Had Significant Amelioration of Inflammatory Enzymes In MPTP Induced Experimental Animal Models of Neurodegeneration
A231	Dr.Kuppsad PG	Significant Improvement of Immunohistochemistry Scores with RAAS Inhibitors In Chemically Induced Experimental Laboratory Rodents
A232	Dr.Saniya K	Effect of Calcium Channel Blockers on Immunohistochemistry Scores In Chemically Induced Animal Models of Epilepsy: A Preclinical In Vivo Study
A233	Dr.Udma S	Effect of Calcium Channel Antagonists on Inflammatory Biomarkers In Pilocarpine Induced Experimental Laboratory Models of Epilepsy
A234	Mr.Ajay Kumar Dwivedi	Towards a Carbon Neutral Future:The Role of AI in Decarbonisation Strategies
A235	Mrs.Deepti Gupta	Biometric Facial Recognition System for Enhanced Urban Security.
A236	Mr.Mohd Rashid	Role of MRI Diffusion weighted Imaging in Stroke and Space Occupying Leisions (SOL) of Brain
A237	Dr.Avugaddi Iova saranya	Understanding the relationship between severity of type -II diabetes mellitus and high blood pressure in IPD patients.

A238	Mrs.Sheenam	A Comprehensive Analysis of Image Forgery Detection Using Local Binary Pattern and Convolutional Neural Networks
A239	Dr.HARI MOHAN SAXENA	THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON HUMAN CONNECTIVITY: AN IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS
A239	Mrs.MOHINI GUPTA	THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON HUMAN CONNECTIVITY: AN IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS
A240	Kumar Gaurav Bajpai	A Review on antidiabetic activities of Clerodendrum infortunatum
A241	Dr.Anupama Gangrade	The Role of AI and Education Research in Shaping a Sustainable Future
A242	Mr. Naveen Chandra Upreti	Immersive Learning: Redefining Education through Future Interactions with Virtual Reality Technology

9.00AM - 12:00 PM Day-3 (13th Jan,2024) Session-Chair: Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh

Oral & Poster presentations **Mobile No- 8299547952**

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/82875231102?pwd=ZVZaaVYzb3Q0QjE3Smh2bmJIWE8rZz09>

Meeting id- 828 7523 1102 Password 437865

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation & 05 min for PPriyaoster presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
IT09	Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh	Synthesis of Nanomaterials and their applications
IT10	Dr.Dharmendra Kumar Yadav	Leveraging artificial intelligence to deliver on the promise of digital health
IT11	Dr. MOHD.ARFAT	Role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Medical Radiology & Imaging Technology
A193	Ms.Pratishtha Verma	A Comprehensive Review of Artificial Intelligence Applications in E-commerce.
A194	Mr.Anurag Kumar Verma	An Extensive Analysis of Python's Use in Internet of Things (IoT), Machine Learning, and Data Science
A195	Ms.Subhangi	Biometric Facial Recognition System for Enhanced Urban Security
A196	Mr.Kaushal Shukla	Biometric Facial Recognition System for Enhanced Urban Security
A197	Mr.Saurabh Pandey	Evolution and impact of data science in modern era
A198	Ms.Ruchi Tiwari	Immersive Learning: Redefining Education through Future Interactions with Virtual Reality Technology
A199	Ms.Geetika Negi	Immersive Learning: Redefining Education through Future Interactions with Virtual Reality Technology
A200	Mr.Mohit Mishra	Intelligent Eco-Systems: Harnessing Artificial Intelligence For Lasting Environmental Sustainability
A201	Mr.Pragyan Raj	Intelligent Eco-Systems: Harnessing Artificial Intelligence For Lasting Environmental Sustainability
A202	Mr.Aditya kumar Kushwaha	The Evolution and Impact of Data Science in the Modern Era

A203	Ms.Arfa Rizwan	The Evolution and Impact of Data Science in the Modern Era
A204	Mr.Ankush Kumar Verma	Towards a Carbon-Neutral Future: The Role of AI in Decarbonization Strategies
A205	Mr.Abhishek Maurya	Towards a Carbon-Neutral Future: The Role of AI in Decarbonization Strategies
A206	Mr.Gaurav Tripathi	Unleashing the Power of Artificial Intelligence in E-commerce for Enhanced Customer Experiences and Business Optimization
A207	Mr. Swapnil Gaur	Scope of AI in digital marketing
A208	Mrs.Ravindra Kaur	Participation
A209	Miss.Pooja Chaudhary	Comparative assessment of Lipoarabinomannan antigen and anti-lipoarabinomannan antibody profile for the serological diagnosis of active tuberculosis: Insight into a case-control study
A210	Miss.Neha yadav	RULER DROP REACTION: A STUDY OF REACTION TIME AND ITS RELATIONSHIP TO DISTANCE IN YOUNG ADULTS
A211	Miss.P.VINOTHINI	ATTITUDE:A DETERMINANT OF AGRICULTURAL GRADUATES PARTICIPATION IN VIDEO CONFERENCING TECHNOLOGY
A212	Miss.Prashasti Sinha	Antiviral Drug Discovery: Unique Aspects
A213	Miss.Roshni Kumari	A Recent Advancement on Photocatalytic Behavior of d-block Metal Oxides
A214	Dr.Jasneet Sudan	Chat GPT for Research Writing
A215	Dr.Tarushi Tanwar	Prevalence and Determinants of Excessive Daytime Sleepiness in Sedentary Young Adults: The Role of Sleep Quality, Anxiety, and Depression
A216	Dr.Iram Iram	Prevalence and predictors of gynecological issues in working women: A cross-sectional study
A217	Mr.Md Farhan Alam	Effect of a physical intervention on pronated feet subjects having chronic low back pain: a pilot study
A218	Ms.Anukriti Mishra	A Study on Career Development and Performance Management systems of faculty members in Technical educational institutions in Kanpur.
A219	Dr. Abhi Sarika Bharti	Spectroscopic Study of Interaction of the Chlorophyll and Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles
A220	Dr. Simpall Kumari	Growth and Yield Performance of Pleurotus Mushroom on Different Substrates
A221	Dr. Amit Kumar Verma	Nanoencapsulation of essential oils

12.00 - 5:00 PM Day-3 (13th Jan,2024) Session-Chair: Dr. Seema Tripathi& Ms. Hardeep Kaur

Oral & Poster presentations

Mobile No- 8299547952

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/82875231102?pwd=ZVZaaVYzb3Q0QjE3Smh2bmJlWE8rZz09>

Meeting id- 828 7523 1102 Password 437865

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation & 05 min for Poster presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
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A157	Miss.Banita	A Study Of Instagram Promotions Of The Film 'Gangubai Kathiawadi' And Their Significance In Influencing Audience Perceptions
A158	Dr.D GUNASEELAN	.
A159	Dr.CHAUDHARY KAMALESHKUMAR DHANABHAI	foreign body ingestion in adult
A160	Mr.Anubrat Raina	Extraction and Formulation of Perfumes from Essential Oils
A161	Miss.ANSHU	Antiarthritic activity of herbal plants.
A162	Dr.Shubham Biswas	Phenytoin induced overlap Steven-johnson syndrome/Toxic epidermal necrolysis (A Case report)
A163	Mr.Raj Joshi	Exploring alternative forms of producing and presenting non-fiction content
A164	Mr.Naitik Tulpule	Examining Consumer Behavior and Brand Perception in Quick-Commerce Applications
A165	Mr.ERICK EDWARD MAGANGA	For participation only
A166	Dr.Alina Javed	Dentistry in Metaverse
A167	Mr.Ritik parashari	Essential oils used as probiotics and postbiotics
A168	Dr.Madhur Shroff	Jack Stone Calculi in the Urinary Bladder: A Rare Case Report
A169	Mr.Aviral Singh	Trends In The Viewer Perception Of Remake Content In Bollywood Movies
A170	Miss.Pavitra Mahesh	Exploring Branded Media: Brand Integration and Sponsorship in Indian Broadcast and Digital Media
A171	Dr.AVUGADDI LOVA SARANYA	Prevalence of Pre-hypertension and its relationship with blood group and body mass index
A172	Miss.Shravanthi S	Effects of selected carbonated beverage on cultivated microorganisms from public toilet
A173	Mr.Farhan Akhtar	Exploratory and social inquiry into the phenomenon of beauty pageants in India
A174	Dr.Anurag Sharma	Ethical Challenges of Artificial Intelligence technology in Palliative Care
A175	Miss.Ilakkiya S	Role of Public Relations in the success of Tamil Films
A176	Mr.Ayush Bhattacharya	Studying the Unconventional Marketing Strategies of Fintech Giant (CRED)
A177	Mr.Anoop M Menon	Representation of Therapy and Therapists in Indian Movies and TV Series: An Examination of Accuracy, Influence, and Perception
A178	Miss.Anwasha Pati	Indian Cinema and Political Propaganda: The interplay of Ideologies, Politics, and People's Perception

A179	Mr.Sushil Kumar	Exploring novel therapeutic approaches for knee osteoarthritis:A literature review
A180	Mr.Suraj-Bhan Singh	Ruler drop reaction: A study of reaction time and it's relationship to distance in Young's adults.
A181	Mr.RAMANUJAM	The Application of Artificial Intelligence:An analytical study
A30, A31&A182	Mr.Ayushman Panda	ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND ITS INTEMPERANCE IN THE HR DOMAIN
A183	Mr.Suneel Kumar Umar	Ruler drop reaction: A study of reaction time and it's relationship to distance in Young's adults.
A184	Miss.Akshita Rajput	Creator Economy goes Decentralised: An Examination of the opportunities & challenges of Web 3.0 for Content Producers
A185	Miss.Roman Randhawa	Childhood trauma: a meta-analysis of case studies
A186	Dr.Shabnam	Health and Musculoskeletal Discomfort among Females with Hypothyroidism
A187	Mr.Saurabh Srivastava	Intelligent Eco-Systems: Harnessing Artificial Intelligence For Lasting Environmental Sustainability
A188	Mr.CHANDRA BHUSHAN	Empowering Sustainable Development Harnessing the Potential of Artificial Intelligence
A189	Dr.Jasneet Sudan	Role of Artificial Intelligence in Health Research-A Narrative Review
A190	Dr.Arun Kumar Shukla	Role of Chatbots in Enhancing customer Engagement and providing Real time support in the F& B Industry in India
A191	Mrs.Sandhya Sinha	Essential Employable Skill Sets for Management Graduates:- A corporate Perspective
A192	Mr.BHARATH, M	Swift sight: Pioneering tomato blight diseases detection through tensorflow image classification

Announcement of Winners of Awards & valedictory session, Day-3 at 5:00 PM

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/82875231102?pwd=ZVZaaVYzb3Q0QjE3Smh2bmJIWE8rZz09>

Meeting id- 828 7523 1102 Password 437865

Note: All Participants will Join this session

IT-01

Prof. N.B. Singh
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Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry and
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Research Methodology and its Application of Research

Abstract

Research methodology is the approach in which a researcher solves a problem thoroughly. It is a science of studying how research is conducted systematically. Different steps used in studying a research problem are elaborated. The term Research is related to seek out the information and knowledge on a particular topic or subject. In other words, research is an art of systematic investigation According to Clifford Woody research comprises defining and redefining problems, formulating hypothesis or suggested solutions; collecting, organizing and evaluating data; making deductions and reaching conclusions; and at last, carefully testing the conclusions to determine whether they fit the formulating hypothesis. In the lecture different steps such as review of literature, finding out the research gaps, methodology and interpretation of data will be discussed.

Dr. Neha Singh
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SARS-CoV-2 Infection in Pregnant Mothers during 3rd Trimester

Abstract

SARS-CoV-2 and its adverse effects on pregnant mothers during the third trimester of pregnancy was noticed. However, it's essential to note that research and understanding of the virus continue to evolve. Research studies suggested that pregnant individuals, including those in the third trimester, might be at a slightly higher risk of severe illness from COVID-19 compared to non-pregnant individuals. Common symptoms of COVID-19, such as fever, cough, and shortness of breath, may be more severe in pregnant women. Additionally, there were concerns about potential complications, including preterm birth, PROM, fetal distress, postpartum hemorrhage, low birth weight, histopathological changes but the overall risk appeared to be relatively low. It was recommended that pregnant individuals follow precautions to reduce the risk of exposure to the virus, such as practicing good hand hygiene, wearing masks, and maintaining physical distancing. Medical experts view and supervision is needed during COVID-19 during pregnancy, taking into account individual health conditions and circumstances. According to research common long-term symptoms of COVID-19 included fatigue, difficulty concentrating (brain fog), shortness of breath, and persistent loss of taste or smell. However, the extent to which pregnant individuals and their babies might be affected by long-term symptoms including neurological development, and whether there could be specific implications for maternal or fetal health, were areas that required further investigation and further research.

Key Words: Pregnant Mothers, 3rd Trimester, COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2 Infection, RT-PCR, Pandemic

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Prediction of monkeypox cases through Statistical and Machine learning methods

Abstract

The consequences of Covid-19 on the global economy and healthcare have raised concerns about newly emerging viral infections. Monkeypox (MPX) has become one of these, posing a major threat to public health. In this study, we use three statistical techniques to analyze the infectious monkeypox disease and anticipate its future spread among the top ten nations with high infection rates: "distribution fitting," "ARIMA modeling," and "Random Forest" machine learning modeling. We attempted to precisely analyze and estimate the disease's spread by modeling theoretical distributions with data from multiple countries. We fit data from the nations under consideration into ARIMA models to find the most accurate time series regression model. We also employ the Random Forest machine learning technique to forecast future illness behavior. By comparing the Root Mean Square Errors (RMSE) of both models for each country, we discovered that the Random Forest model outperformed the ARIMA model in six of the ten countries, while the ARIMA model fared better in the other four. The best-fitting model is recommended for sound policy decision-making.

Keywords: Monkeypox virus, Disease modeling, Random Forest, ARIMA, Distribution Fitting, RMSE.

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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN NURSING

Abstract

Artificial intelligence is the intelligence of machines or software, as opposed to the intelligence of humans or other animals. It is a field of study in computer science that develops and studies intelligent machines. Such machines may be called AIs. Nursing encompasses autonomous and collaborative care of individuals of all ages, families, groups and communities, sick or well and in all settings. It includes the promotion of health, the prevention of illness, and the care of ill, disabled and dying people. Artificial intelligence is being utilized to provide diagnostics assistance and decision support for nurses. AI systems can analyse a patient's symptoms, vitals, lab results, and medical history to generate possible diagnoses and their likelihoods. Deep learning AI can be used to help detect diseases faster, provide personalized treatment plans, and even automate certain processes, such as drug discovery or diagnostics. It also promises to improve patient outcomes, increase safety, and reduce costs associated with the delivery of healthcare.

Robotics in nursing is an interdisciplinary discipline that studies methodologies, technologies, and ethics for developing robots that support and collaborate with physicians, nurses, and other healthcare workers in practice. Nursing AI tools include clinical decision support, mobile health and sensor-based technologies, and voice assistants and robotics.

Robot nurses are machines programmed to execute specific tasks related to care delivery and a facility's functionality. Their presence can aid nursing professionals with certain duties, and can also contribute to patient engagement. It has to be pointed out that, although at the moment robots are supposed to administer any medical treatment to a patient, they could be programmed to do so. When compared to humans, robot nurses are quicker to train, cheaper to maintain, easier to refuel and repair, and able to do very odd and repetitive tasks.

Diligent Robotics develops "robots to support and empower patient care teams," according to the company web site opens in a new tab or window, but "AI is not going to replace nurses," Springan emphasized. "There is nothing that can replace the human touch.

Key words- Artificial Intelligence, Robotic Nurse, Nursing

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AI Based Tools for Literature Search

Abstract

We are currently residing in a technological world that is undergoing rapid transformation, with new Artificial Intelligence tools being introduced on a daily basis. The availability of AI-based applications that assist researchers in conducting research, writing research reports, selecting journals, and disseminating the research has also caused a paradigm shift in the research workflow. These applications help researchers in all of these areas. This presentation will discuss the capabilities of some recently developed AI-based tools that are tailored to the steps of literature search and review involved in research. These tools have the potential to reduce the amount of time and effort expended by researchers. In addition to that, the talk highlights the challenges and concerns that come along with using such systems.

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Role of Non-Timber Forest Products for tribal livelihood: a case study in Adilabad district of Telangana, India.

Abstract:

Forests and its products play vital role for the livelihood, sustenance and income generation to forest inhabitants and tribal people. Tribals are local aboriginal people living in and around or near the forest since ancient times. In course of time, they are living in isolation from the main stream life, had a symbiotic relationship with the forest and rely on forest products. Non-timber forest products (NTFPs) are goods of biological origin other than wood, derived from forest, other woody lands and trees outside forest. Collection and sell of different Non timber forest products for commercial purposes are considered as crucial means of their livelihood. The tribal people seasonally collect various NTFPs to satisfy the needs for their food, fodder and medicine., such as medicinal, leaves, flowers (corolla), fruits, seeds, bamboos, gums, resins. The dominant tribes involved in using these forest product in the erstwhile Adilabad district of Telangana State. In the present study tried to explore the role of NTFPs in tribal livelihood of Adilabad district (erstwhile) area through a random sample of 120 respondents selected from five villages. The qualitative and quantitative data were analyzed. About 40 to 56 percentages of tribal people depend on forest for their livelihood and the seasonal collection of NTFPs provide substantial income and provide employment during off seasonal employment and livelihood to local tribal people. Due to lack of knowledge and skill in collection, processing and value addition hamper their economic subsistence. The sustainable harvesting and conservation of natural resource management yield the livelihood to the tribal people.

Key words: Non-Timber Forest Products(NTFPs), sustainable management, Tribal people, Livelihood, Telangana, India.

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Use of Artificial intelligence in the diagnosis of Oral Cancer

Abstract

Although more recent medical advancements and a significant amount of information on various oral diseases, it is impossible to accurately diagnose the disease and assess the progress. The advent of artificial intelligence (AI) has revealed many new possibilities for healthcare improvement and has opened up a new era of increased exactitude in pathology. Artificial intelligence (AI) can be helpful in the diagnosis of diseases, in making prognosis, or in creating patient-specific treatment plans. AI can help the clinicians and pathologists especially when they need to make important judgements quickly. It can eliminate human mistake from the judgement process, resulting in improved and standardised health care. Pathologists can use AI to find specific imaging indicators connected to disease processes in order to improve early diagnosis, assuming prognosis, and select the treatments that are most likely to be successful. AI and pathologists working together can produce outcomes that are superior to what humans are capable of in terms of accuracy, consistency, timeliness, and utility. The future of precision oncology will benefit from this combination, which has the potential to produce personalized care plans.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Pathology, Healthcare

IT-8

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Systematic Study of Mg Doped ZnO Thick Films

Abstract

Currently there is a huge interest in the luminescence properties of zinc oxide owing to its potential for developing photonic devices in the UV and visible spectral region. ZnO, the direct wide band gap of 3.37 eV, semiconductor is being actively studied as it has a spectrum of applications. All the undoped and 5, 10 and 15at.% doped films are polycrystalline with hexagonal wurtzite structure and crystallite size between 60 and 146 nm. The lattice constant as well as anion-cation bond length remains unaltered except for 10 at.% doping and films are predominantly oriented along (101) plane. Surface structure consists of microclusters of dodecahedron-type and nearly spherical grains reducing in size with doping. Monotonous blue shift in absorption peak from 379 to 371 nm with successive increase in doping indicates increment in band gap of the material. Dominant green photoluminescence is obtained from screen printed ZnO films which gets doubled for 15 at% Mg doping and is ~5.4 times stronger than the accompanying UV emission. This is particularly important as no green emission was present in the starting oxide powders. The photosensitivity gets enhanced by nearly three times and becomes 71.68. In view of these properties such films can be a pathway for optical sources, sensors or photoconductors and solar cells.

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Synthesis of Nanomaterials and their applications

Abstract: Nanomaterials, defined as materials with at least one dimension in the nanometer range, have garnered considerable attention due to their unique properties and versatile applications. This talk includes various methods of synthesis of nanomaterials, their characterization, and applications. The synthesis of nanomaterials encompasses a multitude of techniques, including top-down and bottom-up approaches. Top-down methods involve the reduction of bulk materials into nanoparticles through processes like milling, lithography, and etching. In contrast, bottom-up methods focus on the assembly of atoms, molecules, or clusters to build nanomaterials, utilizing techniques such as chemical vapor deposition, sol-gel processes, and hydrothermal synthesis. The choice of synthesis method depends on the desired properties and applications of the nanomaterial. Nanomaterials find applications in fields such as electronics, medicine, energy, and environmental science. In electronics, nanomaterials like graphene and carbon nanotubes have revolutionized the development of high-performance transistors and flexible displays. In medicine, drug delivery systems, imaging agents, and biosensors benefit from the unique properties of nanoparticles to improve diagnosis and treatment. In the energy sector, nanomaterials enhance the efficiency of solar cells, catalytic processes, and energy storage devices, contributing to sustainable energy solutions. Additionally, in environmental science, nanomaterials are utilized for water purification, pollution remediation, and sensors for environmental monitoring.

The significance of nanomaterials in advancing technology and solving complex challenges across multiple domains. As research in nanomaterial synthesis and applications continues to evolve, the potential for groundbreaking discoveries and innovative solutions remains promising.

IT-10

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Leveraging artificial intelligence to deliver on the promise of digital health

Abstract

Rising rates of NCDs threaten fragile healthcare systems in low- and middle-income countries. Fortunately, new digital technology provides tools to more effectively address the growing dual burden of disease. Properly leveraged, we can employ digital solutions and applications to transform health systems from reactive to proactive and even preventive, helping people stay healthy. With artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning, health systems can be made more predictive by detecting risk factors and helping health professionals respond faster to prevent disease. Yet this rapid pace of growth has also complicated the digital health landscape. Myriad digital health apps compete and overlap in the public and private sectors, and significant gaps in the collection and analysis of digital data threaten to leave some behind. Established in 2010, the Broadband Commission for Sustainable Development is led by ITU and UNESCO and advocates for the transformational impact of broadband technologies for development. Its working group on digital and AI in health, co-chaired by the Novartis Foundation and at different times Nokia, Intel and Microsoft, identifies best practices for countries to realize the potential of digital technology in health and care. Interviewing more than 100 key stakeholders and reviewing over 200 documents, the Working Group set out to identify common challenges that countries face in implementing digital health solutions, and to develop a framework that countries can use to build systems for supporting digital health solutions. Common challenges include a lack of coordination leading to fragmented digital health solutions; lack of systems and workforce capacity to manage data and digital technology, and inadequate financing to support digital health. The working group proposes six building blocks for digital health systems: formulate and execute a national digital health strategy; create policy and regulatory frameworks that support innovation while protecting security and privacy; ensure access to digital infrastructure; ensure interoperability of digital health system components; establish effective partnerships; and sustain adequate financing.

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Keywords: Digital technology, intersectoral collaboration, health systems non communicable diseases, sustainable development goals

OP-1

Thin Layer Chromatography: A Tool for Assessment of Phytochemicals from Medicinal Plants

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Abstract: Present study was made to review the basic principles and the importance of Thin Layer Chromatography in research as a tool for assessment of phytochemicals from Medicinal plants. TLC is a simple, cost-effective and easy-to-operate planar chromatographic technique. It has a wide application in identifying impurities in a compound. TLC is applicable for quantitative and qualitative estimation of bio-active compounds present in Medicinal plants. It is also used for comparative assessment of phytochemicals present in Medicinal plants grown under different geographical and climatic conditions. It may also analyse the presence of any heavy metal/toxic elements with beneficial phytochemicals. As medicinal plants/herbs are being used extensively without knowing about list of beneficial and harmful ingredients present with useful phytochemicals.

Keywords: TLC, Phytochemicals, Chromatography, Quantitative, Qualitative

OP-2

Revolutionizing Agriculture with Artificial Intelligence (AI): A Comprehensive Review

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Abstract: The use of artificial intelligence (AI) in agriculture is a rapidly growing field with the potential to revolutionize crop production, improve monitoring, and automate tasks such as irrigation and spraying. As the world population is expected to reach 10 billion by 2050, the demand for agricultural products is set to increase by 50% compared to 2013. AI-based equipment and machines, including agricultural robots and drones, have already made a significant contribution to the agro-based sector, and the use of AI and machine learning in plant pathology has resulted in advanced diagnostic tools for identifying plant diseases in real-time. AI-based systems can also assist in soil analysis by processing data from soil sensors, weather stations, and satellite images. Machine learning algorithms analyse the data to identify patterns and correlations, providing insights into soil health, nutrient content, and water availability. This information helps farmers make informed decisions about crop management practices. In livestock management, AI and the Internet of Things (IoT) are integrated to enable precision livestock farming. Sensor devices, communication technologies, and data management techniques monitor livestock, predict phenotypic traits, and facilitate real-time identification. AI also assists in predicting pig growth, early prediction of parturition in dairy cows using behavioural data and optimizing livestock farming practices. Overall, the use of AI in agriculture has the potential to enhance efficiency, productivity, and contribute to sustainable development and food security.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligent, Machine learning, Drones, Crop management, Disease management, Expert System, Intelligent Diagnosis Tools.

OP-3

Unveiling Cognitive Biases in AI-Driven Decision-Making for Sustainability

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Abstract: As the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) becomes increasingly prevalent in shaping sustainable practices, understanding the cognitive biases embedded within AI-driven decision-making processes is imperative for fostering effective and equitable environmental solutions. This research delves into the intricate interplay between cognitive biases and AI algorithms designed to address sustainability challenges. The study draws on insights from psychology to unveil the subtle yet influential biases that may inadvertently shape AI decisions, impacting the trajectory of sustainable initiatives. Two key areas are explored in this research. First, the investigation identifies prevalent cognitive biases within AI algorithms, examining how biases such as confirmation bias, anchoring, and availability heuristic may distort the accuracy and impartiality of sustainability-related predictions and recommendations. Second, the research explores the psychological mechanisms underlying the adoption and acceptance of AI-driven sustainability solutions, considering factors like trust, perceived transparency, and user satisfaction. This research contributes to the ongoing discourse on the intersection of psychology, AI, and sustainability, offering a nuanced understanding of the cognitive biases that shape AI-driven decision-making processes and providing actionable insights for creating more robust and unbiased AI solutions in the pursuit of a sustainable future.

Keywords: Cognitive Biases, AI-decision making, Sustainability.

OP-4

How "Secure is Patient Data"? Assessing measures taken by healthcare institutions and professionals in promoting cybersecurity

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Abstract

Introduction: The healthcare industry lags in securing vital data as compared to other industries and hence, becomes a prime target for medical information theft. AIM: To assess measures taken by healthcare institutions and professionals in promoting cybersecurity.

Materials and Method: Data was distributed to two groups separately, the first being various healthcare institutions [Hospitals and Teaching colleges (Medical, Dental and Nursing)] as well as individual Medical and Dental Practitioners in Northern India using online forms. Both questionnaires consisted of sixteen questions each and were divided into two sections. Data was analysed using SPSS version 24.0 and the student's independent sample's t-test and multivariate logistic regression was applied keeping a p value of ≤ 0.5 as significant.

Results: While most hospitals (88%) have started storing data online, teaching institutions lag behind (30%). Most practitioner also preferred storing their patient data physically (68.8%). Few hospitals reported having a dedicated IT team (23%), while only 12% of institutions did so. Although most participants reported having an anti-virus installed in their system (98.2%), they were unaware of its type (78.4%), licence validity (81.6%) and how frequently it updated itself (75.1%). Differences between hospitals and teaching institutions was found to be significant with respect to data breach policies $p=(0.02)$, and password security ($p=0.04$).

Conclusion: The vulnerability of the healthcare industry to modern threats needs to be addressed seriously and necessary policies need to be implemented in case such a breach is noticed by skilled experts.

OP-5

Use of Artificial intelligence in the diagnosis of Oral Cancer

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Abstract: Although more recent medical advancements and a significant amount of information on various oral diseases, it is impossible to accurately diagnose the disease and assess the progress. The advent of artificial intelligence (AI) has revealed many new possibilities for healthcare improvement and has opened up a new era of increased exactitude in pathology. Artificial intelligence (AI) can be helpful in the diagnosis of diseases, in making prognosis, or in creating patient-specific treatment plans. AI can help the clinicians and pathologists especially when they need to make important judgements quickly. It can eliminate human mistake from the judgement process, resulting in improved and standardised health care. Pathologists can use AI to find specific imaging indicators connected to disease processes in order to improve early diagnosis, assuming prognosis, and select the treatments that are most likely to be successful. AI and pathologists working together can produce outcomes that are superior to what humans are capable of in terms of accuracy, consistency, timeliness, and utility. The future of precision oncology will benefit from this combination, which has the potential to produce personalized care plans.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Pathology, Healthcare.

OP-6

**Evaluation of Public Health-Care Services of District Hospital Budgam Kashmir Valley
India**

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Abstract

Introduction: One of the most important public health concerns for the foreseeable future according to the WHO is disparities in access to healthcare. Therefore, it is important to design the healthcare delivery system such that it can meet the demands of the entire community. We used primary and secondary data like availability, accessibility of the selected public healthcare facility, utilization of public healthcare institution, satisfaction among in- and out-patients, satisfaction among medical professionals, nursing, and other health care professionals' and observed nursing performance score. The present study examines how frequently people in the Kashmir division use healthcare services and how satisfied they are with it because most of the prior research has only used secondary sources.

Methods: This study is a cross-sectional study conducted in District Budgam of Kashmir region in northern India, the observational availability tool of district hospital was developed to assess the available public health services with confirmation to IPHS norms 2012 , selected utilization of public health care services (performance indicators) tool was framed to assess the utilization of public health services, the structured questionnaire cum interview schedule, was developed and used for data collection in particular healthcare facilities. Based on the accessibility and use of the public health services offered at the chosen hospital, the satisfaction of in-patients and out-patients was evaluated. Finally, the level of satisfaction among different healthcare experts was assessed in terms of professional growth, equipment, emergency supplies, residential facilities, staff requirements, interpersonal relationship with healthcare workers and patients, working conditions, recognition and growth.

Results: The study revealed a 25%, 33% and 20% shortage of medical and surgical specialists and nursing staff respectively, whereas paramedical staff strength was roughly in line with Indian Public Health Standards (IPHS 2012). The overall mean patient satisfaction was 67.2%

indicating a high degree of contentment among patients who used this health care facility's services.

Conclusion: The findings of this study underscore critical challenges within the healthcare system, particularly in the shortage of medical, surgical specialists and nursing staff by 25%, 33% and 20% respectively, while paramedical staff levels align with the Indian Public Health Standards (IPHS 2012). Despite these workforce imbalances, the study reveals a noteworthy aspect of neutral to agree, with both medical and paramedical staff expressing levels of satisfaction. The overall mean employee satisfaction stands at 55.5%, and patient satisfaction at 67.2%. These results highlight the complex dynamics within the healthcare workforce, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to address specialist and nursing shortages. Additionally, recognizing the satisfactory levels of employee and patient satisfaction suggests a potential avenue for building on existing strengths to enhance overall healthcare delivery and provider morale. Future efforts should focus on strategic recruitment and retention strategies for medical, surgical, specialists and nursing staff while sustaining the positive aspects of employee and patient satisfaction observed in this study.

Keywords: *Public Health, Health-Care Services, utilization of public healthcare, Performance indicators, Availability.*

OP-7

**Studies on Phytoplankton Diversity of Perennial Lake at Karimnagar District,
Telangana State, India**

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Abstract: Phytoplanktons are often considered powerful biological indicators of fresh water ecosystems. Biological indicators act as important measures of the state of an Ecosystem more so when combined with chemical data. Phytoplankton being very small in size, they are microscopic plants, they respond quickly to the environmental changes. Changes in the chemistry of water will alter the change in abundance, growth and composition of species. Phytoplankton is a fundamental component of many of these aquatic ecosystems, not only in terms of biological diversity but also because it contributes to primary productivity that helps to maintain fisheries and other important lake ecosystem attributes. Diversity of phytoplankton helps to enhance the productivity and strongly depicts the water quality. The present study was undertaken to study the diversity of phytoplankton population of fresh water lake in Karimnagar district, Telangana state, India and after survey of Mulukanoor fresh water lake was selected. The main aim of the present study was to explore the phytoplankton from Mulukanoor Freshwater Lake, study the diversity pattern and assess quality of the lake. In the present study was carried out of one year from June 2015 to May 2016. A total number of 25 species were recorded. The phytoplankton diversity study provided several new data with many of the phytoplankton taxa being recorded for the first time in study site, such as 10 species among the Chlorophyceae, 6 species of the Cyanophyceae, 4 species of the Euglenophyceae and 5 species of the Bacillariophyceae. The present observations revealed that Chlorophyceae species were dominant followed by Cyanophyceae, followed by Euglenophyceae and Bacillariophyceae were observed during the study period. There were percentage of Chlorophyceae (37%), Cyanophyceae(24%), Euglenophyceae(21%) and Bacillariophyceae(18%).

Keywords: Mulukanoor Freshwater Lake, Phytoplankton Diversity, Seasonal Variation.

OP-8

Evaluation of Anxiolytic Properties of Hydro-Alcoholic Extract of Aegle Marmelos Fruit (Bael Fruit) in Swiss Albino MICE

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Abstract

Background: Many anciently used medicinal plants with natural neuroprotective and antioxidant properties have shown to be beneficial in a variety of behavioral disorders such as anxiety disorders

Objectives: To Screen the hydro-alcoholic extract of *Aegle marmelos* (HAAM) fruit for its anti-anxiety activity in Swiss albino mice

Methods: 100 mg/kg and 200mg/kg extracts of *Aegle marmelos* fruit and a combination of 200 mg/kg extract plus standard diazepam were compared with the standard (Diazepam 1mg/kg) and control (distilled water). Six Swiss albino mice weighing 25-30 mg were used for each group. Level of anxiety was studied using the behavioral models Elevated plus maze and Light and dark arena. Observations on time spent in open and closed arm in EPM model and time spents in bright and dark areas in LDA were calculated.

Data was analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Turkey Kramer's test.

Results: Among the test group, highest value was for HAAM 200 mg/kg plus diazepam group when compared with the control, standard, HAAM 100 mg and HAAM 200 mg.

HAAM 200 has equivalent anxiolytic effect when compared to the standard diazepam. When HAAM 200 mg + diazepam was given, the mean time spent in the light box and open arm was more and this was also found to be statistically significant when compared to control group and standard

Conclusion: The two doses 100 mg and 200 mg has anxiolytic properties when compared to the control and standard. The combination of hydroalcoholic extract of *Aegle marmelos* (HAAM) 200mg with the standard Diazepam has also showed a significant anxiolytic effect when compared to the standard and control group. Hence *Aegle marmelos* may be used as a potential resource for the treatment of anxiety.

Keywords: *Aegle Marmelos*, Anti-anxiety, Elevated plus maze, Light Dark Arena, Swiss albino mice

OP-9

AI in Agriculture

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Abstract: Agriculture plays a crucial role in the economic sector for each country. As the global population continues to grow, the demand for food rises accordingly. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is leading to a revolution in agricultural practices. This revolution has safe guarded the crops from being affected by distinct factors like climate changes, the porosity of soil, etc. AI finds many applications in the agricultural sector, including crop monitoring, soil management, pest detection and a lot more. The primary idea of using Artificial Intelligence in agriculture is due its adaptability, superiority and cost-viability. The customary techniques that were utilized by the farmers were not adequate enough to satisfy their necessities. In this way, new computerized strategies were presented. These techniques fulfilled the food prerequisites. The primary focus of this chapter is to review the applications of AI in farming.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, monitoring, soil management, pest detection, etc.

OP-10
Sports as a Career
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Sport is an exciting and healthy pastime game to many, but if the sport is really one's passion it can be a very rewarding and satisfying career too. It was traditionally considered as a hobby especially in India but now it is taken as a serious career option.

The success of sports people in a recent international sporting event has brought the focus to sports careers. Sports help you to make your body physically fit and keep your mind good. If you choose sports as a career, it also gives lots of fame and money.

You can make a career in any sports field depending on what sports you take up as your expertise. Various sports fields are *Cricket, Badminton, Volleyball, Football, Basketball, Boxing, Gymnastics, Hockey, Table Tennis, Wrestling, Cycling, etc.* 1982 was a watershed year for the growth and development of sports in India. First time, the Asian Games were hosted at Delhi in India.

Successful sport persons of India are: ***Sachin Tendulkar, MS Dhoni, Sania Mirza, Abhinav Bindra, RVS Rathore, Sushil Kumar, Viswanathan Anand, Mary Kom*** and many others.

COURSES & DURATION

As a sports person, you can get training from various institutions of Sports Authority of India. In India, there are various institutes and academies under the Sports Authority of India (SAI) that impart training to young talents to transform them into talented sports persons. Other than SAI, there are many state levels and private organizations that support sports enthusiasts.

Sports opened up many career opportunities for young talents in India. To become a sports person, having a talent in the chosen sport is very important. Along with talent, Strong determination and perseverance is needed.

For every sports person, it is a dream to represent their nation at the international level. You can start your career in school and college level and start play at the State level, Regional level and then explores opportunities at national and international levels.

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Other than actually being an active sportsman, then other career opportunity are: sport marketing, coaching, athletic administration, sports medicine, sport promotion, sport psychology and so on.

Sports person can be employed in private and public sector. The Indian Government and Armed forces also have special recruitment drives for exceptional sporting talent. You can also set up your own business in manufacturing of sports equipment after gaining experience in this field.

OP-11

Vibration Energy Harvester Design and Analysis Using Laminated Composite Material

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Abstract

The significant benefits of the piezoelectric vibration energy harvesters for many engineering field applications emerge from their mechanical and electrical energy conversion mechanisms. Over the past several years, energy harvesting from ambient vibration has emerged as an area of active research because it can be utilized in a variety of applications. In this paper, we used the laminated composite material for the vibration energy harvester beam. The modelling and analysis are performed using finite element analysis and the results are compared with the analytical calculations. Further, the enhancement of the harvester performance is also carried out using optimization. The composite laminate properties are used as the variables and the output voltage is considered as the objective for the optimization. The obtained optimal results are validated using finite element analysis and analytical calculations.

Keywords: Vibration energy harvester; Composite Laminates; Piezoelectric; Finite Element analysis; Optimization.

OP-12

Synthesis, characterization and molecular docking of Ni (II) complex with Schiff base derived from o-vanillin and 4-nitro-o-phenylenediamine

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Abstract: Schiff bases are good chelating agents and form a variety of stable chelates with transition metals in various oxidation states. These chelates show various biological activities. Here we introduce 3-methoxy-salophen ligated Ni(II) complex, in which the unique O,N chelation mode of 3-methoxy-salophen ligand (bis[2-methoxysalicylidine]-4-nitro-1,2-iminophenylenediamine) was used to form Ni (II) complex. Schiff base H₂L is prepared from o-vanillin by condensing it with 4-nitro-o-phenylenediamine. Further it was complexed with Ni(II) by mixing ethanolic solutions of it and NiCl₂.6H₂O in 1:1 molar ratio, followed by addition of few drops of triethylamine and refluxed for 6-7 hrs. Ligand and complex both are physically and chemically analyzed by elemental analysis and are characterized by different spectroscopic techniques like UV, FT-IR and NMR. Ligand and complex both are screened against fungi by molecular docking.

Keywords: Chelates, Schiff base, transition metal complex, biological activity, molecular docking.

OP-13

Repurposing of the Plant Compounds Molecular Docking of '*Taxus wallichiana*' compounds as a New Potential Inhibitor for Breast Cancer

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Abstract: Breast cancer remains a global health challenge, necessitating the search for innovative therapeutic solutions. Our study focused on molecular docking analysis of bioactive compounds from '*Taxus wallichiana*' to identify potential breast cancer inhibitors. '*Taxus wallichiana*' is renowned for its rich source of bioactive molecules, particularly taxanes, known for their anti-cancer properties. Employing computational techniques, we predicted the binding affinity of '*Taxus wallichiana*' compounds with key targets in breast cancer progression. Molecular docking simulations, utilizing advanced software and considering three-dimensional structures, targeted proteins associated with cell proliferation, apoptosis, and angiogenesis. Results showcased promising interactions between specific '*Taxus wallichiana*' compounds and active sites in breast cancer-associated proteins. Analyzing binding affinities and interaction modes provided insights into potential anti-cancer mechanisms, with an exploration of contributing structural features. This study significantly contributes to breast cancer drug discovery, providing a foundation for future experimental validations and preclinical studies. Identifying '*Taxus wallichiana*' compounds as potential breast cancer inhibitors lays the groundwork for exploring natural products as therapeutic agents. This opens avenues for developing targeted and effective treatments for this prevalent and challenging disease, offering hope in the ongoing fight against breast cancer.

Keywords: *Taxus wallichiana*, Taxanes, Cell Proliferation, Angiogenesis, Apoptosis

OP-14

BER Analysis of Proposed Scheme coded DWT-OFDM in comparison to DWT-OFDM under different simulation conditions

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Abstract: Modern wireless communication systems demand for high bit rate transmission techniques. Channel coding has been emerged as a scheme to improve the reliability of communication system. Most commonly used Error Correction and detection scheme is Convolution codes. Researchers are continuously working to develop new schemes for improving the performance of the system. In this paper, we investigated the performance of proposed scheme coded Discrete Wavelet Transform based Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (DWT-OFDM) over Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) channel in comparison to DWT-OFDM System. The simulation has been done using MATLAB software. The Bit Error Rate (BER) performance of the proposed system has been studied in terms of signal to noise ratio (E_b/N_0). It is found by MATLAB simulations that the performance of proposed scheme coded DWT-OFDM outperforms the DWT-OFDM with both 16 and 32 QAM modulation. Further, simulations are performed for 16 and 32 PSK modulation. Again, proposed scheme based DWT-OFDM leads to less BER in comparison to conventional DWT-OFDM.

Keywords: OFDM, DWT, QAM, PSK.

OP-15

Allelopathy: A Natural Way towards Weed Management

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Abstract: Allelopathy refers to beneficial or harmful effect of one plant on other plant by release of certain biochemicals. These biochemicals are known as Allelochemicals. They are very effective in weed killing and they are also known as natural weed killers. Allelochemicals are sub set of secondary metabolites (such as alkaloids, phenolics, flavonoids, terpenoids and glucosinolates. They are present in almost all the parts of plant tissues for eg .leaves, flowers, stem, roots, and rhizomes etc. They get released from plant tissues in surrounding environment by volatilisation, leaching, root exudation. These biochemicals may inhibit the growth of neighboring plant by inhibiting nutrient uptake, inhibit shoot/root growth, or they may attack a natural occurring symbiotic relationship thereby destroying the plant's natural source of nutrients. Allelochemicals can be used as growth regulators and natural herbicides, to promote sustainable agriculture and to reduce the usage of synthetic fertilizers. Allelopathic effects depend on the joint action of allelochemicals, so increase in the study of these interactions might lead to advances in the understanding of their action on target organisms. Allelopathy requires further research for widespread application in crop production worldwide. Improve crop management by using Allelopathic properties of some plants will increase crop production efficiency ,that would definitely boost food, fiber and bioenergy production and help to address the world's food demand.

Keywords: Allelochemicals, Secondary Metabolites Bioenergy, Volatilisation

OP-16

The Role of Artificial Intelligence in advancing medical education and research

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Abstract: Artificial intelligence (AI) plays a crucial role in medical education and research by boosting efficiency, accuracy, and innovation. In medical education, AI-fueled tools enable personalized learning experiences. Virtual tutors and simulators use AI algorithms to adapt to individual student needs, providing real-time feedback and tailoring educational content. This customized approach helps medical students learn skills and knowledge more effectively. In research, AI speeds up the analysis of extensive datasets, making it easier to identify patterns and insights. Machine learning algorithms can detect potential drug candidates, predict disease outcomes, and analyze complex genetic interactions. AI also assists in image analysis by interpreting medical imaging such as X-rays, MRIs, and CT scans with high precision, aiding clinicians in making diagnoses. Additionally, AI supports continuous medical education through platforms that deliver updated information, ensuring healthcare professionals stay up-to-date with the latest research and practices. Virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) applications, powered by AI, enhance surgical training, allowing practitioners to simulate procedures in a risk-free environment. By automating routine tasks, AI frees up time for healthcare professionals to concentrate on more complex aspects of patient care and research. Collaborative platforms employ AI to connect researchers worldwide, promoting a faster exchange of ideas and findings. Integrating AI into medical education and research not only enhances educational outcomes, but also accelerates breakthroughs in diagnostics, treatment, and overall healthcare delivery, ultimately contributing to advances in medical science and patient care.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, medical education, medical research, advancement, sustainability.

OP-17

Export Competitiveness of Dairy Farming in India

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Abstract: India has emerged the World's biggest in milk producer. Total milk production in India was 230.58 million tonnes with first rank in world during 2022-23. Compound annual growth was 5.5 percent during the 1950 to 2022. Per capita availability of milk production increases 130 gram per day to 459 per gram per day during 1950 to 2022. But during this period, India's dairy industry has lack of market access in world wide. This paper explains the India's export competitiveness of dairy farming in in international market by using the Revealed Comparative Advantages (RCA) Index during 2003 to 2022. The result is indicated that all dairy products are less competitiveness in global market. In recent year India's dairy products share in world export is continuously declined. However, India can increase the export of dairy products. It is necessary to implement the ongoing 'Make in India' initiative in dairy farming. By setting up high-take dairy processing industry in rural area, processed dairy products export can increase by giving the brand of 'Made in India.'

Keywords: India, Dairy Farming, Export Competitiveness.

OP-18

Artificial Intelligence and its Intemperance in the HR Domain

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Abstract: Human Resources have long been a fundamental sector within industries, evolving alongside the rapid development spurred by the industrial revolution. Initially reliant on manual labor, industries were hazardous due to chaotic working conditions. The advent of Human Resource management aimed to organize and regulate this workforce, transforming it into a valuable asset.

With the onset of digitalization, traditional notions of labor shifted, making way for advanced technological support that not only saved time and resources but also delivered quicker outcomes. As digitalization surged forward, Artificial Intelligence emerged, marking an unparalleled revolution. Mundane and repetitive tasks were replaced by intelligent, supported work methods, significantly enhancing industry flexibility and advancement.

This discussion paper delves into the profound impact of Artificial Intelligence on industry, exploring its influence on workplace satisfaction, the equilibrium of work-life dynamics, and its potential to further revolutionize the world in the years to come.

Keywords: Human Resource Management, Artificial Intelligence, digitalization, industry, development

OP-19

Incarcerated Drug Traffickers: Reformation Programs for Offenders in Prison

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Abstract: Drug trafficking incidents are increasing alarmingly every year in India. Illegal trafficking as well as consumption for personal use also are on high. In 2022, Kerala topped in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances (NDPS) crimes; the second was Maharashtra, and both were high for personal use or consumption of drugs. Punjab has been third for registering NDPS crime but has been first for drug trafficking in India. A total of 4811 NDPS cases were registered in Madhya Pradesh in the year 2022. In the correctional services, the rehabilitation approach plays an important role by transforming the prisoners into better than they entered in prison. The objective of this study was to know about reformation programs in prison for incarcerated convicted drug traffickers. The study was conducted on 166 drug traffickers across nine prisons in Madhya Pradesh, India. The purposive sampling method was adopted for this study. The structured interview schedule was used for the collection of primary data. The result shows that most of the convicted drug traffickers (68.1%) have learned something in the prison as vocational training under the correctional programs for the prisoners. The offenders have different types of work assigned to them in the prison as guard duty, cleaning work, cooking, tailoring, agriculture work, carpentry, etc. A total of 88.6 percent of offenders have decided to do something better for their livelihood after release from prison. More than half of the offenders felt guilty and remorse for their deeds as it is against the norms of society. The study suggests that better rehabilitation training and positive thinking may be betterment towards the reformation of offenders and rehabilitation in society.

Keywords: Drug traffickers, Offenders, Prison, Correctional programs.

OP-20

Statistical Analysis and Prediction of Eligible Candidates for Promotion

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Abstract: Developments in Human Resources Management (HRM) are fast being integrated with corresponding changes in data and information processing, which are restructuring our environments. The domain of human resource analytics, which can be understood as a data and analytical thinking-centred approach to Human Resources Management, is fast becoming an indispensable part of organisational setups. With the emergence of HR Analytics in organizations; gathering, interpreting, and measuring of HR data has become easy. HR Analytics act as a tool which is a combination of statistical techniques that enable collection, interpretation, measurement, and forecasting of data. HR analytics enlightens solution to the organizational problems and make accurate decisions. HR analytics hence aligns HR strategy with overall business strategy to obtain a competitive advantage. HR analytics has passed through phases of measuring the Sub HR functions. HR Analytics provides various opportunities to business as it forecasts workforce requirements, enables HR to achieve corporate goals, and improve organizational performance which helps businesses in finding success. Despite the success, the business faces some big challenges like data governance, skill gap among employees, top management support, and many other such challenges in implementing and using the HR Analytics tool in business. So many papers have come focusing on the conceptual part of HR analytics, past , present and future scenario of HR analytics, acceptance of HR analytics in organizations, the extent of its utility, rise of HR analytics, and various other related studies. This study aims to identify the right candidate for promotion (only for manager position and below) and prepare them in time. The study will provide the pros and cons of implementing and using HR analytics.

Keywords: Data, Correlation, Regression, Target variable, Prediction

OP-21

Health and Musculoskeletal Discomfort among Females with Hypothyroidism

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Abstract: Hypothyroidism is one of the most common forms of thyroid dysfunction. Generalized musculoskeletal aches and pains are common in hypothyroidism and continue in some patients despite pharmacological restoration of thyroid function. This cross-sectional study investigated the prevalence of musculoskeletal discomfort & their impact and association on health related quality of life among female subjects with hypothyroidism. The total number of subjects was 100 females. They were selected on the basis of inclusion and exclusion criteria, were recruited from HAHC hospital, Jamia Hamdard in New Delhi. We measured Musculoskeletal Discomfort by means of Musculoskeletal disorder questionnaire by The National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) and Health Related Quality of Life by means of HRQL Questionnaire-RAND version of Short form-36 (RAND SF-36) in 100 hypothyroidism subjects. The subjects reported pain & discomforts reported highest in low back pain (26%) followed by knee pain (14%), neck pain(13%), hand/finger pain (11%), ankle/foot pain(12%), hip pain(7%), elbow pain(6%), upper back pain(5%), shoulder pain(4%), thigh pain(1%) and calf pain(1%). The musculoskeletal discomfort mainly includes knee, ankle /foot, hip, thigh & calf involving the lower limb & in upper limb mainly includes elbow, hand/finger, shoulder, upper back, and lower back. The study concluded that there is prevalence of MSDs in different regions hypothyroid females but no significant association was found with the Quality of life. The prevalence of musculoskeletal discomforts was highest in lower back (26%) among the females with hypothyroidism in the selected sample.

Keywords: Hypothyroidism, musculoskeletal discomfort, musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs), Health related Quality of life (HRQOL)

OP-22

Chat GPT for Research Writing

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Abstract: ChatGPT (Chat Generative Pre-Trained Transformer) is a chatbot developed by OpenAI and launched on November 30, 2022. It enables users to refine and steer a conversation towards a desired length, format, style, level of detail, and language. Successive prompts and replies, known as prompt engineering, are considered at each conversation stage as a context. AI tools like ChatGPT help to improve the quality of scientific writing by identifying potential errors, inconsistencies, or gaps in the argument. This helps human authors to refine their writing and ensure that their manuscript is accurate, well-structured, and well-supported by all available evidence as much as possible. It not only saves time but also help us manage large amounts of data and can prove to be helpful to non-English speaker researchers.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, manuscript, scientific writing, Chat GPT

OP-23

Intelligent Eco-Systems: Harnessing Artificial Intelligence for Lasting Environmental Sustainability

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Abstract: This research explores the intersection of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and environmental sustainability, investigating their potential to revolutionize traditional approaches. Focusing on resource optimization, the paper delves into AI's role in enhancing energy efficiency, waste reduction, and water conservation. Through literature review and case studies, the study reveals how AI-driven predictive modeling and machine learning contribute to adaptive and resilient environmental systems. The research extends to AI's application in monitoring and mitigating environmental pollution, emphasizing real-time air quality assessments and pollution source identification through satellite imagery analysis. AI facilitates early detection, intervention, and contributes to enhancing overall ecosystem quality and safeguarding public health.

In summary, this research offers a comprehensive exploration of the synergy between AI and environmental sustainability. Providing insights for policymakers, researchers, and practitioners, it underscores AI's potential as a catalyst for innovation. By addressing urgent environmental issues, AI fosters a harmonious coexistence between technology and nature, offering transformative solutions for a sustainable future.

Keywords: Sustainable Environment, Sustainable Future, Artificial Intelligence, Environmental sustainability with AI, Public Health, Energy Efficiency.

OP-24

The Impact of Social Media on Human Connectivity: An In-Depth Analysis

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Abstract: In the digital age, social media has emerged as a transformative force in reshaping the dynamics of human connectivity. This paper delves into the complex relationship between social media platforms and the intricacies of human interaction. With the proliferation of platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and Snapchat, individuals have found new ways to connect, share, and communicate with others globally. However, this phenomenon has raised significant questions about whether social media has enhanced or eroded human connectivity.

This in-depth analysis encompasses a multidimensional exploration of the subject, encapsulating both positive and negative facets of social media's impact. On the positive side, social media has redefined the concept of distance, allowing individuals to effortlessly bridge geographical gaps and maintain connections with friends, family, and acquaintances across the world. It has also facilitated the formation of online communities, offering solace and support to those grappling with shared challenges or interests.

Yet, the transformative power of social media is not devoid of its pitfalls. Concerns have been raised about its potential to engender social isolation by replacing meaningful face-to-face interactions with virtual exchanges. The prevalence of cyberbullying, misinformation, and the adverse effects of excessive screen time has sparked debates about the harmful consequences of uncontrolled social media use.

This analysis draws from an extensive array of sources, including scholarly research, surveys, and case studies, to provide an understanding of the impact of social media on human connectivity. It synthesizes empirical evidence, throwing light on the complex interplay between social media usage patterns, individual perceptions and its influence on the quality and quantity of social relationships.

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Ultimately, this paper reveals that the impact of social media on human connectivity is a complicated phenomenon, shaped by innumerable factors, including individual preferences, intentions and societal context. As we navigate this digital landscape, it becomes clear that striking a balance between harnessing the benefits of social media for connectivity while mitigating its potential drawbacks is essential for fostering healthy and meaningful human connections in the modern era.

Keywords: Social media, human connectivity, technological shift, mental health, interpersonal relationships.

OP-25

**Synthesis and Fungicidal Activity of novel 3-Chloro-4 (3-iodo-4- hydroxy -5-methoxy)-
2'-azetidinone and their Derivatives**

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Abstract: The present study was conducted to evaluate the antimicrobial activity, many phenols and compounds with phenolic groups have antifungal potency. A large number of fungicides are formulated as wettable powders; this is the form most commonly used for spray mixes. Modern wettable powders are easily wetted and disperse well in water. The structures of all the newly synthesized compounds were confirmed by spectroscopic data ¹H NMR, MS and elemental analysis. Some other chemicals, like certain phenanthrene derivatives and Bordeaux mixture, may inhibit spore production without affecting the growth of vegetative fungal hyphae. These are called "antisporeulants". 2-amino 4-Phenyl Thiazole condensed with appropriate ethanol and piperidine aromatic was refluxed on water bath for 1 hr. Various obtaining gave benzylidines and thiazolidones respectively and synthesized compounds showed moderate to good antifungal activity with respect to standard drugs.

Keywords: 2-amino 4-Phenyl Thiazole, EtOH, structure-activity relationship; synthesis, Fungicidal Activity

OP-26

“Prevalence of Diabetic Peripheral Neuropathy among Type 2 Diabetic patient in Urban Etawah”

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Abstract

Background: Diabetic peripheral neuropathy (DPN) is a common and one of the severe complications of diabetes mellitus. It affects almost half the diabetic population and worsens quality of life of the patient. The present study was aimed to determine the prevalence of peripheral neuropathy and associated risk factors.

Aims and Objectives: To assess the Prevalence of Diabetic Peripheral Neuropathy (DPN) among Type 2 DM patients and its associated risk factors.

Material and Methods: The present was a community based survey conducted over a period of one and a half year. Cluster sampling technique was used to collect the study sample in urban Etawah. Study participants aged ≥ 30 years residing in urban Etawah with known history of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus of ≥ 5 years were included in the study. Participants who were severely ill and mentally challenged were excluded from the study. Diabetic Peripheral Neuropathy (DPN) was diagnosed using 10 g monofilament test. Association was calculated using chi-square test. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All the statistical analysis was performed using SPSS v25.

Results: A total of 400 DM patients were enrolled in the study. Out of which 28% (n = 112) patients were diagnosed with DPN using Semmes-Weinstein (SW) 10-g monofilament test. Statistically significant association was also noted with Family history of DM, BMI, Systolic and Diastolic blood pressure, Family history of HTN and History of Smoking

Conclusion: The current study found a high prevalence of DPN and it was found to be significantly associated with advancing age, duration of diabetes and history of smoking.

Keywords: Diabetic Peripheral Neuropathy, Prevalence, Risk factors, Type 2 DM

OP-27

An Analytical Study on Dark Figures of Crime against Scheduled Tribes

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Abstract: According to the Indian Constitution, a tribe is a group of distinct people, who are mostly dependent on their land & forest for their livelihood and they are largely self-sufficient. They are called Scheduled because they are included in one of the Scheduled parts of the Constitution of India. However, Section 2 (wa) of the Criminal Procedure Code, 1973 defines the term victim means any person who has suffered any loss or injury caused because of the act or omission for which the accused person has been charged. The main aim of the study is to know about the nature of crime and the pattern of victimization against Scheduled Tribes under dark figure (non-registered) cases. A total 376 number of cases were registered during the year 2020-2022 in Sagar district in Madhya Pradesh. The total registered (261) and non-registered (45) cases were taken through the primary data collection method. Only non-registered cases were used in this study. The census method was adopted for this study to cover the whole data for the depth study. The result shows that 27 percent of victims have not reported crime because of family influence, 20 percent of victims settled the cases by themselves, while 11 percent of victims have not reported cases because of misbehaving in the police station, and the same 11 percent due to fear of the accused. However, lowest number of cases, 7 percent of victims they have mistrust in the criminal justice system. The study suggested that there is an urgent need for the government to develop positive police public relations, a smooth policing and criminal justice system, and swift crime prevention strategies for controlling and reducing crime.

Keywords: Scheduled Tribes, Victimization, Crime, Dark Figures etc.

OP-28

Incorporation of Artificial Intelligence in Garbhasanskar to enhance cosmic impact of senses (*panchhindriya*) on fetus

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Abstract: The concept of Garbhsanskar in ayurveda defines as *Shreyasipraja* emphasizes the holistic development of the unborn child, including physical, mental, and spiritual aspects. While traditional practices focus on the mother's overall well-being, incorporating AI to enhance sensory experiences during pregnancy could potentially contribute to a more enriched environment for both the mother and the developing fetus. Here are some ways in which AI could impact the cosmic aspect of senses improvement in the context of Garbhsanskar. AI can create enhanced Audio Experiences (*Sabda therapy*) which can be personalized for the pregnant individual for Chanting of *mantras*, *meditation*, *garbhsamvada* (talking to baby in womb), Music therapy, Reading of good books. Sensory Feedback Devices (*Sparsh therapy*) AI can be integrated into wearable devices that provide sensory feedback, such as haptic vibrations or gentle movements, enhancing the tactile experience for the pregnant individual. AI-driven Visual Stimulation can be personalized to provide visually appealing and calming stimuli. Virtual Reality (VR) Experiences (*rupa therapy*) can create immersive environments for the pregnant person, allowing them to virtually explore serene landscapes, engage in mindfulness activities, or participate in calming scenarios. AI algorithms can analyze preferences and sensitivities to curate personalized aromatherapy experiences (*gandha therapy*). Scent diffusers or devices can release specific fragrances known for their calming or uplifting properties, positively impacting the olfactory senses. Biofeedback and Mindfulness Training incorporate with AI results in monitoring of physiological signals and providing real-time feedback to guide practices such as deep breathing and meditation. Biometric Monitoring for Stress Reduction can be analyze by AI for heart rate variability and cortisol levels, to identify stress patterns. Personalized recommendations can then be generated regarding diet according to *prakriti (rasa therapy)* to help manage stress and maintain a positive cosmic impact on the overall well-being of the mother and child. It's important to approach the integration of AI in Garbhsanskar with cultural sensitivity, recognizing that the cosmic aspect involves a connection between the individual and the universe.

Keywords: *Garbhsanskar, Shreyasipraja, Panchhindriya, Artificial Intelligence, Ayurveda*

OP-29

Psychological Well-Being of the Spouses of Deployed and Non-Deployed Commissioned Officers of Indian Armed Forces: A Comparative Study

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Abstract: Spouse of armed force personnel face anxiety and stress during the periods of deployment of their husbands to high altitude and other field areas and stress due to the danger of their husband's life as well as managing every task single handedly. Work pressure and separation from the family together makes the condition worse for the soldier thus, cases of anxiety and even suicides among soldiers are also increasing day by day which is also a contributing factor to disturb psychological well being of those spouses whose husbands are deployed away from home. Considering the gravity of the matter present study establishes the differences of various dimensions of psychological well being and overall psychological well being between spouses of deployed and non-deployed commissioned officers of armed forces. 100 officers' spouses among which 50 were those who belong to deployed category and 50 belonged to non-deployed category were selected as respondents. Statistical differences were found using students' T test. The results of the analysis show significant differences in total psychological well-being, life satisfaction and mental health between deployed and non-deployed officers' spouses.

Key words: Deployed, non-deployed, psychological-wellbeing, stress, mental health

OP-30

Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes of cerium (III) metal from ligands containing N & O donor atoms and study of their physicochemical, spectral, thermal, and antibacterial properties.

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Abstract: The research study includes the formation and characterization of Cerium (III) Mixed-ligand complexes using 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde oxime (BO) as the primary ligand and organic compounds 2-amino-3-(1H-indol-3-yl)propanoic acid (L₁), 2-amino-4-(methylthio)butanoic acid (L₂), 2-amino-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)propanoic acid (L₃), 2-Amino-3-sulfhydrylpropanoic acid (L₄) as secondary ligands. All complexes are brown color and shows stability, as evidenced by conductometric measurements indicating non-electrolyte behavior. FTIR analysis reveals coordination through O and N donor atoms, while thermogravimetric studies highlight stability with coordinated water molecules, supported by high decomposition temperatures. UV studies demonstrate intra-ligand and ligand-to-metal charge transfer transitions. Elemental analysis confirms a 1:2:1 ratio for the complexes. Antibacterial assays using agar cup and tube dilution methods affirm the complexes' antibacterial activity against specific bacterial strains.

Keywords: mixed, complexes, metal, antibacterial.

OP-31

Female Education and Development

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Abstract: Education has become a powerful tool to raise the level of all human beings especially of females; as they have remained deprived and untouched in the way of all kinds of development. Education empowers the women to take part in decision making process and leads the society at higher level. Furthermore, education helps in self-realization of powers and changes the attitude of society towards females. Previously, they were limited to household works and agricultural activities. Moreover, they were not credited for these services. But now-a-days, education has changed the scenario. They are getting educated. They are becoming the part of economic work force of a nation. They are getting reward in the form of salary and raising their standards. But it has been observed in many of the studies that their services are more limited to the traditional work. Further, when it comes to the education of females among SCs, they are most neglected section of the society. In this regard, an attempt has been made through this study to analyse education and participation in non-agricultural activities among schedule caste females of Himachal Pradesh. To achieve this objective, graphical presentation of data has been done with the help of digital mapping. Simple percentage technique has been used to make absolute values in relative sense. It was found in this study that increased level of literacy has shifted SC females into non-agricultural activities. However, the rate of increase in literacy and participation in non-agricultural activities is not same. But there is positive relationship between literacy and non-agricultural activities.

Keywords: Education, Non-agricultural activities, Scheduled caste females, women standard digital mapping.

OP-32

How "Secure is Patient Data"? Assessing measures taken by healthcare institutions and professionals in promoting cybersecurity

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Abstract:

Introduction: The healthcare industry lags in securing vital data as compared to other industries and hence, becomes a prime target for medical information theft. AIM: To assess measures taken by healthcare institutions and professionals in promoting cybersecurity.

Materials and Method: Data was distributed to two groups separately, the first being various healthcare institutions [Hospitals and Teaching colleges (Medical, Dental and Nursing)] as well as individual Medical and Dental Practitioners in Northern India using online forms. Both questionnaires consisted of sixteen questions each and were divided into two sections. Data was analysed using SPSS version 24.0 and the student's independent sample's t-test and multivariate logistic regression was applied keeping a p value of ≤ 0.5 as significant.

Results: While most hospitals (88%) have started storing data online, teaching institutions lag behind (30%). Most practitioner also preferred storing their patient data physically (68.8%). Few hospitals reported having a dedicated IT team (23%), while only 12% of institutions did so. Although most participants reported having an anti-virus installed in their system (98.2%), they were unaware of its type (78.4%), licence validity (81.6%) and how frequently it updated itself (75.1%). Differences between hospitals and teaching institutions was found to be significant with respect to data breach policies $p=(0.02)$, and password security ($p = 0.04$).

Conclusion: The vulnerability of the healthcare industry to modern threats needs to be addressed seriously and necessary policies need to be implemented in case such a breach is noticed by skilled experts.

OP-33

Basic Principles and Applications of Applied Statistics in Real World

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Abstract: Although statistics is an ancient scientific field, its relevance has never been greater. The study of data collection, analysis, interpretation, and presentation is the focus of the mathematical field of statistics. The practice of statistical science has become more and more popular as a result of increased computational capacity. We begin to gather data from a variety of sources, including web server logs, online transaction records, twitter streams, social media, and data from various sensors, thanks to emerging technologies like the internet of things. As big data becomes more widely available, there is a growing demand for experts in applied statistics who can interpret, display, and analyze data in order to address challenging real-world issues. The foundation of data analysis is applied statistics, which is the study and application of data analysis for the purpose of identifying and defining organizational needs. Applied statistics are now found in many different sectors, including business, marketing, accounting, engineering, information technology, and medical. This work aims to elucidate applied statistics, its underlying concepts, and demonstrate its utilization across diverse domains.

Keywords: Applied Statistics, Statistical tools, Big Data.

OP-34

Effect of growth regulators on callus mediated shoot organogenesis in *Gloriosa superba* L.

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Abstract: *Gloriosa superba* L. (family: Colchicaceae) is an important medicinal plant that grows at high altitudes. The plant has been affirmed as endangered plant due to its over exploitation by herbal industries as the tubers are rich source of an alkaloid, colchicine. Also, tuber dormancy and poor seed germination restricts its multiplication and thus the available germplasm is very less. So, there is urgent need to develop an efficient and reproducible protocol for its *in vitro* conservation and commercial propagation. Seeds treated at 4°C for 24 hrs resulted in poor seed germination with only 10-15% seeds showing germination after three weeks. MS supplemented with 2.0 mg/l BAP, 0.5mg/l Kn and 1.0 mg/l GA3 resulted in 88.67% shoot multiplication and 8.7±0.18 average number of shoots per explant while MS containing 2.0 mg/l IBA resulted in 84.50% of long and healthy roots with an average of 7.47±0.29 roots per explant. Embryogenic callus resulted in multiple *in vitro* shoot and root formation on MS medium supplemented with BAP, Kn and IBA. Subculturing of embryogenic callus on MS medium containing 2,4-D, BAP and Kn resulted in somatic embryos with globular structures while MS medium supplemented with BAP only, resulted in heart shaped somatic embryos on the callus. The efficient shoot regeneration and somatic embryogenesis can be further used as target tissues for genetic transformation studies in *Gloriosa*.

OP-35

‘Ayurveda Remedies Used In the Mastitis of Dairy Animals - A Review’

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Abstract: In the 21st century, Dairy farming is India's largest self-sustaining industry and the largest rural employment sector providing a third of all rural income. Under the white revolution in India, on average 1.41 million Kg of milk has been processed each day which is expected to give around Rs.2,458.7 billion in revenue in the upcoming years. As technology grows, due to modernization, nowadays dairy animals have been facing health issues very badly. Mastitis/*Stana Shotha*/*Stana Vidradhi* i.e. inflammation of the mammary gland is one of the most costly diseases of dairy animals resulting in the reduction of milk yield by up to 70%. A prevalence rate found for clinical mastitis is 11% & that for the sub-clinical mastitis is 77%. For treatment of Mastitis, to counteract antibiotic resistance, now it is high time to explore the options of alternative therapies for the treatment of mastitis such as *Ayurveda* herbs, which we have reviewed in this article.

Keywords: *Ayurveda*, Veterinary, Mastitis, Dairy, Herbs

OP-36

Thyroid Disease Prediction by using Statistical Techniques

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Abstract: Thyroid is one of the most popular disease across the world. Various studies indicated 42 million people in India undergoes through thyroid disease. It is one of the most common diseases found in human being which cause many other side effects. There are two types thyroid disease: Hyperthyroid and Hypothyroid. Thyroid disorders occur due to dysfunction of the thyroid gland or pituitary gland, iodine deficiency, cancer in some parts of the body, or due to side-effects from other medications. Hyperthyroidism, Hypothyroidism, goiter, and thyroid cancer are some of the elements that result due to thyroid disorders. Some other reasons like pregnancy, or medications for other illnesses may also show abnormal levels of thyroid hormones.

Prior diagnosis of thyroid is very important and beneficial for the betterment of human life, an early diagnosis and detection of this disease can help human being to fight against this disease. In medical science traditional techniques are being used to diagnose various types of disease. Statistical techniques are used to analyse the frequency of occurrence of various factors towards each type of the disease and test for significance of factors is also done. The results are used to build a data model that helps to predict the occurrence of specific type of thyroid disorder in a patient based on significant symptoms. The results emphasize that age, sex, values of hormones like TSH, T3, T4, TT4 and FTI of a patient play a predominant role in classifying and determining the type of thyroid disorder in the person. We also classify the given dataset using various decision tree techniques in different ways and compare the results. We study various attributes commonly found in patients with thyroid disorders to identify those attributes that may specifically describe the type of thyroid disorder in a person.

Keywords: Hypothyroidism, TSH, T3, TT4, T4U, FTI.

OP-37

Gen AI in Corporate Communication: A Stakeholder Theory Perspective

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Abstract: The study delves into the ever-changing landscape of corporate communication in the Generative Artificial Intelligence (Gen AI) era and how it impacts organisational relationships. Using the stakeholder theory as a foundational framework, the research investigates how corporate communication professionals use Gen AI to enhance organisational communication practices. Semi-structured expert interviews are used for this study, with purposive sampling ensuring the inclusion of individuals with significant expertise in both corporate communication and Gen AI integration. Through a comprehensive exploration of communication professionals' perspectives, experiences, and strategic decision-making processes, this research aims to uncover the intricate dynamics in integrating Gen AI. The focus is on understanding how professionals navigate the evolving landscape of technological advancements to meet stakeholders' diverse needs and expectations. The study uses Stakeholder Theory as a lens to analyse and interpret the implications of Gen AI on stakeholder relationships. By delving into the strategic choices made by communication practitioners, the research aims to contribute a nuanced understanding of the evolving role of Gen AI in shaping corporate communication strategies. This research, situated at the intersection of technology and organisational communication, aims to provide valuable insights for academics and practitioners. By elucidating the practical applications of Gen AI within Stakeholder Theory, the findings are expected to inform current discourse and guide future developments in corporate communication practices amidst the ongoing digital transformation.

Keywords: Corporate Communication, Generative Artificial Intelligence (Gen AI), Stakeholder theory, Stakeholder engagement, Organisational relationships.

OP-38

Role of Influencer Marketing and its Impact on Brand and Brand Loyalty: A Case Study of Skincare Brand

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Abstract: In the digital era, the dynamics of marketing and consumer behavior have undergone a paradigm shift. One development in this realm is the emergence of influencer marketing, which has transformed the landscape of brand-consumer relationships. This research investigates the connection between influencer marketing and brand loyalty, employing qualitative methodology of case study. The study seeks to contribute to the existing body of knowledge by shedding light on influencer marketing influences and sustains brand loyalty. The qualitative component of this research engages in a systematic case study analysis of Plum Goodness that has effectively harnessed influencer marketing as a core component of their marketing strategy. The case study provides a deep and nuanced understanding of how influencer marketing campaigns are designed and executed. They also explore the various tactics, strategies, and communication methods used by brands to foster brand loyalty through influencers. The qualitative analysis allows for a rich exploration of the qualitative dimensions of influencer marketing in building brand loyalty. The findings of this dissertation reveal that influencer marketing plays a pivotal role in building and sustaining brand image. The qualitative analysis demonstrates that brands employ influencers as a bridge to connect with their target audience, enabling them to convey authenticity, trustworthiness, and relatability. This research underscores the indispensable role of influencer marketing in shaping brand loyalty. The results demonstrate that influencer marketing is an effective strategy for brands seeking to enhance brand image, but brand loyalty to achieve through influencer marketing is something the brands should not be aiming at. The brand can focus on connecting with their target audience on a personal and emotional level. By integrating influencers strategically into their marketing initiatives, brands can harness their authenticity, credibility, and relatability, ultimately driving customer loyalty and long-term brand success.

Keywords: Influencer Marketing, Brand Loyalty, Qualitative Method, Qualitative Analysis, Case Studies, Consumer Behavior, Digital Marketing.

OP-39

Indian Laws for Women - From Tradition to Transformation

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Abstract: India's history is marked by periods of social and political change, and these shifts have had significant implications for women's roles and rights. For centuries, women in India were subject to traditional practices and societal norms that often restricted their autonomy and limited their participation in various aspects of public life. However, in the post-independence era, India embarked on a journey of modernization and development, accompanied by legal reforms aimed at improving the status and protection of women. Factors such as education level, socioeconomic status, and geographic location significantly affect legal awareness. Therefore, tailored educational and awareness campaigns are essential to ensure equitable access to legal knowledge among women. This study contributes to addressing the identified literature gap, offering a nuanced understanding of Indian women's identity protection in the context of legal reforms. The findings underscore the need for ongoing efforts to enhance legal awareness, culturally sensitive interventions, and reforms that address the evolving needs of modern Indian women.

Keywords: Legal reforms, Women's empowerment, Indian laws, Legal awareness, Gender equality.

OP-40

Role of Attophysics in Controlling Motion of Electron

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Abstract: Scientists all over the world are working to discover the mysterious things and searching and planning the use of mysterious things for betterment of humanity. In this direction, precision measurement is playing key role in all sciences dealing with in quantitative research. It becomes very important in the study of dynamics in physics. Measurement becomes very difficult at the atomic scales which requires sophisticated instruments and well planned experimental setup. Electron motion is considered very fast hence it is very difficult to localise the moving electron in atoms and molecules. It is well known fact that electron completes one revolution around the proton (or Hydrogen atom) in around 150 attosecond. Study of electron dynamics needs sophisticated experimental setup giving measurement at such small time scale.

In 2023, Noble prize in Physics was awarded to three scientists for devoting whole life in the discovery of measurement of pulse generated for attosecond (10^{-18} second) time limit. They used experimental setup to recreate attosecond light pulse by shining laser light through the gas. At present, shortest pulse of light generated within a time of 43 attoseconds is recorded. The efforts are going on to study light pulse of less than 43 attosecond. This discovery will be used in the study of electron dynamics giving information about position of electron in electronic orbits in the atoms and molecules. If instant actual position of electron during motion is known, then motion of electron can be controlled and finally their motion can be manipulated through the external devices according to our needs.

As we know that electronics, on which whole information technology is based, is dependent on the motion of electron and their behavior. At present, it is based on development works in the field of attosecond physics used in the study of electron dynamics will be reviewed and discussed in detail.

Keywords: Electron dynamics, attosecond, applications.

OP-41

Utilizing Artificial Intelligence in the Field of Plant Breeding

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Abstract: Various high-throughput omics technologies have emerged in plant breeding, aiming to expedite crop enhancement and cultivate new varieties resilient to climate variations, pests, and diseases while boosting yield performance. These cutting-edge technologies have generated extensive data on plant genetic structures, offering insights into pivotal traits crucial for crop betterment. Consequently, plant breeders have turned to high-performance computing, bioinformatics tools, and artificial intelligence, particularly machine-learning techniques, to skillfully navigate and analyze this intricate and voluminous data landscape. Artificial intelligence (AI) harnesses computational techniques to imitate human cognitive functions such as problem-solving and decision-making. In the contemporary digital landscape, AI stands out as a swiftly advancing domain within computer science, birthing computers with cognitive capabilities akin to human intelligence. One prominent application of AI lies in expediting plant breeding processes. Through methods like high-throughput genomics and phenomics, AI aids in the creation of new plant varieties. Machine learning (ML) techniques play pivotal roles in tasks like genomic prediction, selection, and marker-assisted breeding. Plant breeders utilize AI-driven systems to gain deeper insights into plant responses under diverse climatic conditions. AI's role in phenomic data management encompasses three crucial facets: crafting algorithms to transform sensory data into actionable phenotypic insights, formulating models that elucidate genotype-phenotype dynamics in varying environments, and overseeing database systems for streamlined information sharing. Recent research emphasize AI's efficacy in enhancing crop phenotyping accuracy and predictive capabilities. As AI continues to permeate plant genomics, its potential for comprehensive genome exploration becomes increasingly apparent. Bioinformatics powered by AI facilitates the concurrent assessment of countless gene expressions across the genome under diverse scenarios. These AI-driven methodologies pave the way for holistic crop phenotype predictions and novel breeding tactics anchored in computational modeling and training. Looking ahead, AI is ready to generate extensive genotypic and phenotypic data sets necessitating model-based envirotyping for identifying

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adaptive genetic traits. To expedite breeding cycles and amplify genetic gains, rapid breeding strategies and advanced material segregation AI will be essential.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Plant Breeding, Machine Learning

OP-42

Understanding the Role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Promoting and Fostering Psychological Immunity (PI) Among Adolescents

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&

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Abstract: Psychological Immunity denotes the capacity to effectively cope with and navigate the daily stressors inherent in individuals' lives through a systematic integration of positive cognitive processes, impulse modulation, self-regulation, and goal-directed behaviour. The PIS is analogous to our immune system safeguarding the body against pathogens, viruses, and diseases, the Psychological Immune System (PIS) shields the mind by deploying psychological antibodies. The breakdown of the PIS exposes adolescents to suicidal tendencies, and under extreme circumstances, the inability to regulate emotions propels them toward risk-taking behaviours, culminating in suicidal acts. The escalating incidence of suicides among the 15-19 age group, as documented by the National Crime Record Bureau (NCRB), underscores the critical importance of understanding and fortifying psychological immunity in youth. Contemporary adolescents grapple with multifaceted changes that surpass their adaptive capacities. Their struggle to align their actions with perceived social norms which contributes to social and emotional distress. Research underscores the efficacy of school-based interventions, incorporating well-defined curricula and innovative practices such as mindfulness, meditation, and life skills training. Another pivotal avenue for exploration and examination involves meaningful engagement strategies tailored to this age group. This paper endeavours to shed light on the considerable potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in fostering positive behavioural transformations among adolescents. Given the inclination of this demographic towards technology and digital devices, the paper posits that leveraging AI can be instrumental. The paper highlights the risk of digital addiction resulting from the misuse of technological power. In the realm of digital interventions, an unexplored reservoir lies in harnessing the rich potential of AI in promoting positive and meaningful engagement of adolescents. This study makes an attempt to highlight the ways and manner in which we can augment their engagement using AI. Ultimately, this approach aims to advance the development of Psychological Immunity.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Digital addiction, Psychological Immunity, Psychological Immune System

OP-43

Analysis of root extracts of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L. for its phytochemical potential

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Abstract: *Glycyrrhiza glabra* has been known for its medicinal potential for centuries. It is locally known as mulethi and is an important medicinal herb. Extracts prepared from roots of *Glycyrrhiza* were screened for phytochemicals. Methanol and n-Hexane extracts were checked for antioxidant activity by DPPH radical and Ferric ion reducing power assay. Presence of phenolics, tannins, saponins, steroids, terpenoids and flavonoids were found to be present in n-Hexane and methanol extracts, while anthocyanins were absent in both the extracts. Flavonoid content was found to be highest (178 ± 0.023 mgQE/g extract) in the n-Hexane extract. Phenolic content (29 ± 0.014 GAE/g extract) was observed to be highest in methanol extract. DPPH assay of methanol root extracts revealed the best antioxidant properties with IC_{50} values of 7.90 ± 0.15 μ g/ml than n-Hexane extracts (9.62 ± 0.02 μ g/ml). Ferric ion reducing antioxidant power was observed to be lower for the methanol extract (5.81 ± 0.006 μ mol/g dry wt $\pm$ SD Fe^{2+} reduced) as compared to the n-Hexane root extract (6.11 ± 0.0005 μ mol/g dry wt $\pm$ SD Fe^{2+} reduced). The antioxidant activity of the extracts is attributed to the presence of the identified phytochemicals.

Keywords: *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, antioxidants, phytochemicals, flavonoids, phenolics, free radicals

OP-44

Personal Key Indicators of Heart Disease

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Abstract: According to the CDC (centers for disease control and prevention), heart disease is one of the leading causes of death for people of most races in the US (African Americans, American Indians, Alaska Natives, and white people). Almost half of all Americans (47%) have at least 1 of 3 key risk factors for heart disease viz high blood pressure, high cholesterol, and smoking. Other key indicator includes diabetic status, obesity (high BMI), not getting enough physical activity or drinking too much alcohol. Detecting and preventing the factors that have the greatest impact on heart disease is very important in healthcare. In order to study key risk factor for the heart disease among US peoples, data available on Kaggle is studied. To study presence of heart disease among US peoples, fit the logistic regression model. Apply Chi-Square test of independence of risk factors on incidence of heart disease. Risk ratio is calculated to study which group is exposed to the heart disease. Different machine learning algorithm is being developed such as logistic regression, decision tree, KNN, random forest, etc. To make the classes balance, apply oversampling and undersampling tools.

Keywords: Chi-Square test of independence, risk ratio, logistic regression, KNN, decision tree, random forest.

OP-45

The Application of Artificial Intelligence: An analytical study

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Abstract: The artificial intelligence is a technology which is now coming in fashion. It is making our life easy and full of comfort. There are so many applications of this technology in our day to day life like Alexa, Google Assistant etc. This paper will cover application part of artificial intelligence technology and its practical role etc.

Keywords: technology, artificial intelligence, comfort etc.

OP-46

Qualitative Examination of Successive Extracts of *Sphaeranthus indicus*

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Abstract: The medicinal value of plants depends on the phytochemical compounds that can impact definite physiological processes in the animal body. Compounds like alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins and phenolic compounds are the major bioactive compounds that can bring about therapeutic effects. It is highly relevant to subject plant materials under study to undergo standardization process which involves stepwise pharmacognostic methods. This is an effective approach that can ensure discovery of new antioxidants and anti-infective agents present in plants (Duraipandiyani et al., 2006). The preliminary phytochemical tests are useful in locating chemical constituents in the plant material that may lead to their quantitative estimation and also in locating the source of pharmacologically active compounds (Bhandary et al., 2012). In this study, dry powder of the stems and leaves of *Sphaeranthus indicus* were subjected to successive solvent extraction using Soxhlet extractor. Six different solvents viz. petroleum ether, benzene, chloroform, acetone, ethanol (95%) and water were selected for successive extraction. Weight of the extract with each solvent with respect to the air-dried weight of the plant material was compared to calculate the yield. Consistency and colour of the extract were also noted after extraction with each solvent. Maximum yield of 40.5 % was obtained for aqueous extract which was sticky and dark brown in colour. However, the lowest yield was reported in chloroform extract. The extracts obtained as above were then subjected to qualitative tests for the identification of various plant constituents like alkaloids, carbohydrate, phytosterols, phenol, saponin and volatile oil. Aqueous extract indicated the presence of carbohydrate, phenols, volatile oils and saponins. Hence, we can conclude that the aqueous extract is more potent as the active principles in the plant dissolved more readily in and were better extracted by a more polar solvent (water). This is in line with the studies conducted on the aqueous garlic extract (Rasul et al., 2012).

Keywords: *Sphaeranthus indicus*, solvent, phyto compounds

OP-47

Preliminary qualitative chemical evaluation and antioxidant activity of *Trichosanthes cucumerina*

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Abstract: Finding natural and potent antioxidants to prevent pathological issues brought on by free radicals is now a rising area of research. This involves screening and measuring antioxidants from biological samples. The present study was to investigate phytochemical & antioxidant activity of ethanolic whole plant extract of Snakegourd (*Trichosanthes cucumerina*) plant belongs to cucurbitaceae family. Extraction was done by soxhlet method using ethanol as solvent. The phytochemical screening showed the presence of Phenols, Steroids, Alkaloids. The 1-1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging method was used to measure the antioxidant activity using ascorbic acid as standard. The results of this study indicated that the *Trichosanthes cucumerina* whole plant is a good source of functional ingredients, exert significant antioxidant activity on comparing with standard ascorbic acid. However, further research is required to isolate the natural compounds with fascinating biological and pharmacological effects.

Keywords- Traditional Plants, Soxhlet method, *Trichosanthes cucumerina*, Phytochemical Screening, Antioxidants, DPPH assay.

OP-48

Temporal and Structural Changes in Cost and Returns in Groundnut Cultivation in India

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Abstract: The research investigates the growth patterns in Cost A1, C2, C3, gross returns, and yield, analyzing the per cent change in various cost components across different states of India over an eighteen-year period (2004-05 to 2021-22). Notably, the upward trajectory in Cost A1 for groundnut cultivation surpassed Cost C3, indicating a more rapid increase in input and paid-out costs compared to indirect expenses such as land rent and fixed capital interest across all Indian states. Maharashtra stood out with the highest growth in Cost C (20.64%), contrasting with a lower rate observed in Orissa (9.27%). Negative yield changes were identified in Odisha, whereas Gujarat and Karnataka demonstrated improved performance. Interestingly, Gujarat, Maharashtra, and Tamil Nadu exhibited a less pronounced trend in manure expenditure, unlike the rest of India, where a substantial increase was noted. Despite escalating costs in both manures and chemical fertilizers, the study underscores the importance of strategic planning to mitigate input cost escalation, especially in light of the relatively lower growth in yield.

Keywords: Cost, Groundnut, Temporal and Structural Changes

OP-49

Temporal and Structural Changes in Cost and Returns in Finger Millet (*Eleusine coracana*) Cultivation in India

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Abstract: This study assesses the growth trends in Cost A1, C2, C3, gross returns, and yield in the context of Finger millet (*Ragi*) cultivation across various states in India. Over an eighteen-year period (2004-05 to 2021-22), an analysis was conducted to examine the percentage change in Cost A1, C2, C3, as well as expenditures on seed, fertilizer, manures, human labor, and animal labor. The findings revealed an upward trajectory in Cost A1 for Finger millet (*Ragi*) cultivation across all Indian states, surpassing Cost C3. This suggests a swifter increase in input and paid-out costs in comparison to indirect expenses like land rent and fixed capital interest. Notably, Tamil Nadu exhibited the highest growth in Cost C at 46.02%. Negative yield changes were observed in Tamil Nadu and Maharashtra, whereas Karnataka demonstrated improved performance. In terms of expenditure, the percentage increase in spending on chemical fertilizer was lower compared to manures, despite both inputs experiencing a substantial overall increase. This analysis sheds light on the intricate dynamics of cost components and agricultural performance in Finger millet (*Ragi*) cultivation across diverse states in India.

Keywords: Cost, Finger millet (*Ragi*), Temporal and Structural Changes

OP-50

**Integrated Teacher Education Programme (ITEP) Opportunities and Challenges
Different programme of teacher education its merits & short comings**

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Abstract: Teacher Education is truly vital in creating the team of quality Teachers in India. So MHRD introducing Integrated Teacher Education program all over the India from 2020. Four year Integrated Education programme is integrated the liberal science and Liberal Arts with B.Ed pedagogy. This professional Training programme is qualitative and well designed, but it is facing some challenges also. The Researcher conducted a survey on “Integrated Teacher Education program” on 56 students of Basundhara Teachers' Training College Muzaffarpur Bihar. For this purpose a questionnaire was given to students and 81% of students had shown positive attitude towards ITEP. This Programme saves Teacher trainees' 1 year valuable time and money and students will get admission to Programme through 'National level common entrance test'. ITEP provides dual- liberal bachelors degree to students in Education and specialised subjects and it provides good infrastructure facilities like library and laboratories to learners .ITEP is encouraging faculty to conduct research activities. But Science stream students are not showing much interest towards teaching profession, so ITEP should design skill-based curriculum to attract them and to create professional Teachers.

Keywords: “ITEP (Integrated Teacher Education Programme)”, “Multidisciplinary”, “Teacher Education”, “Dual- liberal degree”, “Research Activities”.

OP-51

CHALLENGES AND ISSUES IN NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020

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Abstract: Education is the foundation stone of the nation as it plays a powerful role in the growth and development of the country and its citizens. One cannot deny the fact that education is a powerful tool and based on the recommendations by a panel headed by Dr Kasturirangan former chairman of Indian space research former Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO), the New Education Policy has been drafted that focuses on equity, quality, affordability, and accountability of education in our country. In this paper, the author is going to explore about issues and the challenges in the implementation of various policies mentioned in national education policy 2020, the key areas that remain missing, and the complexities involved. Last but not the least, the paper also discusses the divide between the policy and practices together with the recent data statistics. All the details related to the possible challenges due to the changes in the new education policy have been analyzed in the forthcoming sections of this paper.

Keywords: National Education Policy, Higher Education, Challenges

OP-52

COPYRIGHT OF AI-GENERATED WORKS IN INDIA: FOSTERING A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE WITH INSIGHTS FROM THE RAGHAV APP

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Abstract: Copyright grants creators the right to control and financially benefit from their intellectual works, such as literary, music, dramatic, artistic works, cinematographic films, and sound recordings. These rights are exclusive but have a limited duration, after which the work becomes accessible to the public. Copyrights in India are regulated by the Copyright Act of 1957, with the Copyright Office responsible for registrations. Notably, in the fiscal year 2021-22, a total of 20,673 copyright certificates were issued marking a significant 26.5% increase in applications compared to the previous year.

The rapid progress of Artificial intelligence (AI) and its transformative ability to autonomously create a wide array of creative content, from music to literature and more, has given rise to a complex interplay between technology and traditional copyright laws in India. As AI generated works become more prevalent, it is imperative to address copyright issues while fostering a sustainable future for both creators and AI technology. This paper investigates the evolving area of copyright for AI-generated works in India, using the 'Raghav' app as a case study. It explores the current copyright framework, its challenges, legal implications and offers recommendations that include legal and ethical guidelines, collaboration and international cooperation. These recommendations aim to strike a balance between AI-generated works and creator's rights while nurturing a sustainable creative ecosystem. The objective is to support India's leadership in the intersection of copyright and AI while safeguarding the interests of society.

Keywords: Copyright, Intellectual Property Rights, Artificial Intelligence, Artistic works

OP-53

Treatment of Divorce and Custody in Manju Kapur's *Custody*

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Abstract: The concept of divorce and custody has always been a debatable issue in society. However, the legal system has a variety of rules and regulations for handling divorce and custody cases. In literature, these variously observed issues have been registered and reflected for a long time. One such work is Manju Kapur's *Custody* which portrays the story of divorces and custody clash matter-of-factly. This research paper aims at to analyze the depiction of divorce and custody in Manju Kapur's *Custody* and its significance to the contemporary legal framework portrayed in literature by using a qualitative approach to analyze this novel. The research will also carry out a comprehensive scrutiny of the text to identify the themes and motifs relevant to divorce and custody.

Key Words: Marriage, Complexities, Divorce, broken houses, custody, suffering children,

OP-54

A Study of Different Data Mining Techniques used for Rainfall Prediction

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Abstract: Agriculture is the backbone of Indian economy, in India irrigation facility is still not so good and most of agriculture sector depends upon the rain. So the Indian economy depends upon the agriculture Sector. Early prediction of rainfall is necessary for the better economic growth of our country so rainfall plays an important role in agriculture sector. Also the early prediction of rainfall is necessary for the different areas as like ongoing project, Transportation, developing the different infrastructure in our country, scientific research etc. Rainfall prediction become one of the most scientifically and technologically challenging task in the world. Unlike the use of different traditional methods, the modern Weather forecasting consisting of the combination of knowledge of trends and patterns with different weather forecasting models. There are different rainfall forecast methods are available such as the Empirical method and dynamic method. The rainfall analysis based on historical data by using empirical methods and its relationship is different for atmospheric and oceanic variables. The most of empirical approaches used for climate prediction are regression, artificial neural network, and Sensor-Based, Numerical weather prediction model.

Keyword: Data Mining, Rainfall predication, Regression. WEKA Tools.

OP-55

Evaporative cooling of solar panel

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Abstract: Evaporative cooling of solar panel is the cooling process of solar panel, by which the solar cell temperature will be reduced. In the present work a wetted cotton clothes is used for evaporative cooling process. By using evaporative cooling method, it is able to reduce the solar panel temperature up to 10°C lesser than without cooling. By which efficiency of solar panel is increased.

Introduction

Today, the application of renewable energy is broadly encouraged. Photovoltaic (PV) modules are one of the most effective, sustainable, and eco-friendly systems. Only a small portion of solar irradiation incident to these modules is converted into electricity. Only visible range of irradiation are useful in photovoltaic phenomenon. The rest of the irradiation is converted into heat, which overheats the PV module and reduces its performance. Various operating parameters such as irradiation intensity, cooling fluid mass flow rate, humidity, and dust effects the PV module performance by affecting cell temperature. At 1000 W/m² irradiation level without cooling, cell temperature increased to 56 °C; the output power decreased to 20.47 W; and the electrical efficiency decreased to 3.13%. Cooling of photovoltaic (PV) solar panels is an important requirement to keep their efficiencies at a competitive level with other conventional and nonconventional electricity generation methods. A wet clothe will be used on the back surface of PV module to cool cell temperature by evaporative technique or method. Evaporation is a type of vaporization that occurs on the surface of a liquid as it changes into the gas phase. The surrounding gas must not be saturated with the evaporating substance. When the molecules of the liquid collide, they transfer energy to each other based on how they collide with each other. When a molecule near the surface absorbs enough energy to overcome the vapor pressure, it will escape and enter the surrounding air as a gas. When evaporation occurs, the energy removed from the vaporized liquid will reduce the temperature of the liquid, resulting in evaporative cooling.

OP-56

Role of Chabot's in Enhancing Customer Engagement and Providing Real-Time Support in the F&B Industry in India

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Abstract: The Food and Beverages (F&B) industry is passing through a phase of culinary tradition and technological innovations, adapting to shifting consumer behaviours. In response to the evolving landscape, the sector has embraced technological solutions, with chatbots emerging as a pivotal tool for enhancing customer engagement and real-time support. This research explores the multifaceted role of chatbots in the Indian F&B sector, investigating their impact on customer engagement and support processes.

The study employs a mixed-methods research approach, combining quantitative surveys, qualitative interviews, and case studies. By analyzing literature, case studies, and insights from industry professionals, the paper aims to provide a nuanced understanding of how chatbots contribute to the F&B ecosystem. The research addresses the evolution of chatbots, their role in customer engagement, real-time support, and implications for the future of the industry.

Examining successful chatbot implementations through case studies, the paper highlights their positive impact on personalized experiences, streamlined ordering processes, and efficient support. However, challenges such as privacy concerns, technical limitations, and the need for continuous updates underscore the importance of a strategic approach to implementation.

Looking forward, the paper discusses future implications in F&B Industry anticipating advancements in Natural Language Processing, integration with emerging technologies, predictive analytics, voice-activated interfaces, and enhanced backend system integration.

Keyword- Chatbots, Customer Engagement, Real-Time Support, F&B Industry, India, Technology, Artificial Intelligence, Personalization.

OP-57

Digital Transformation and Adoption of Retail Internet Banking: A Study of Demographic Factors

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Abstract: This research paper investigates the transformation and adoption of retail internet banking and its relationship with demographic factors. The study aims to explore how age, gender, education, occupation, and income influence individuals' decisions to adopt online banking services. A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews. The sample consisted of individuals from various age groups, genders, educational backgrounds, occupations, and income levels.

The findings revealed that demographic factors play a significant role in the adoption of retail internet banking. Younger individuals showed a higher inclination towards adoption, while higher income and education levels were positively associated with adoption. Occupation also emerged as a significant factor, with individuals in tech-savvy or professional occupations being more likely to adopt online banking services. However, the influence of gender on adoption rates was inconclusive, with mixed findings from previous research.

The study provides valuable insights into the interplay between demographic factors and the adoption of retail internet banking. It highlights the need for personalized approaches to cater to the diverse needs and preferences of different demographic segments. The research findings have theoretical implications, contributing to the existing body of knowledge on technology adoption and demographic factors.

Practically, the study offers important implications for banks and policymakers. The findings can guide the design of targeted strategies to promote adoption, enhance user experiences, and address specific barriers faced by different demographic groups. Furthermore, understanding the role of demographic factors can aid in fostering financial inclusion and capitalizing on the potential of digital banking services.

Keyword: Internet banking adoption, Demographic factors, Technology acceptance. Retail banking, Digital banking.

OP-58

Weather Prediction Applications: Empowering farmers with the real-time data

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Abstract: This study discusses the use of real-time data in weather prediction applications to empower farmers. The Indian Metrological Department developed Meghdoot, an application that provides the public with weather prediction and warnings for rainfall. This application uses the device's location once it is installed in any device. Even though this application was launched in 2019, but many farmers are unaware. The farmers in the study region were impacted by climate change. This causes abiotic stress to be created in both irrigated and rainfed agriculture, which lowers crop production. The main occupation in the Paravanar river basin of South India, where the study is concentrated, is growing food crops. An analysis of the trend in coriander cultivation shows that it has declined significantly over the past ten years. A seasonal crop that is grown twice a year is coriander. The first time was from June to September, and the second time was from September to December. The monsoon in this area falls in October, November, and December, which destroys second-time farming. Farmers, agriculturalists, and the leaders of the region's villages have all been included in the participatory method and modelling of the risk assessment to revive farming. The rise in the frequency and severity of heavy rains has been identified as the cause of the decline in coriander cultivation. About 150 people have been involved in this strategy. Through the setting up awareness meetings and ongoing phone conversations, the chosen group of people has been advised to follow Meghdoot's instructions from September to November 2022. 33 farmers have thus been successful in reviving the September–October harvest.

Breast cancer diagnosis using models based on convolutional neural networks

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Abstract

Breast cancer is the most prevalent cancer in the world, impacting millions of women each year. Traditional computer-aided methods for diagnosing illnesses and patient monitoring have been significantly outperformed by machine-learning techniques in various healthcare applications. In recent years, researchers have proposed many deep-learning models to aid in the diagnosis of breast cancer. Based on published research, convolutional neural networks have demonstrated promising results for both feature extraction with contextual data and tumor classification using image datasets. The lack of availability of datasets for deep learning model training is the main obstacle to breast cancer detection. with this motivation, this work used transfer learning to observe the classification performance of breast cancer from ultrasound pictures using four pre-trained CNN models with precise adjustment. Two distinct datasets are used to create the images. We used the Adam, SGDM optimizers to evaluate the refined pre-trained models. The ResNet50 with Adam optimizer reaches an overall accuracy of 92.4%. Further, we suggest a short customized convolutional neural network that performs better on several performance metrics than the pre-trained models.

Keywords: Deep Learning ,CNN,Adam optimizer.

OP-60

Online Moral Policing and Gender-Based Violence in India

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Abstract: This paper explores the distressing incidents of moral policing in the digital sphere and its insightful bang on gender dynamics. Scientific developments have made social media a part of our daily lives. The capability of social media to cross physical boundaries causes a change, especially in cultural assimilation. Misogyny is not considered a hate crime in India. Various articles in the Indian constitution provide equal rights and status to women in every sphere. Using a theoretical framework grounded in feminist perspectives and digital sociology, the article aims to shed light on the secret yet invasive nature of online moral policing, dividing its appearance as a form of gender-based violence. In general terms, the article looks into how individuals, particularly women, and a few examples of celebrities experience an understated yet powerful form of control and verdict online.

It draws on feminist theories to analyze how online spaces can become grounds where traditional norms and expectations are enforced, enabling detrimental gender stereotypes.

Through real-life examples of a few celebrities, the article not only reveals the unseen agenda of online moral policing but also calls for a collective consciousness and review of online behavior. By combining personal narratives with theoretical insights, it seeks to empower both genders to recognize and confront these dynamics, nurturing an online environment that prioritizes respect, inclusivity, and the deconstructing of detrimental gender-based stereotypes.

Keywords: Gender Based Violence, Digital Sphere, Misogyny, Hate Crime, Personal Narrative, Gender Stereotype.

OP-61

Oxygen bleaching of *Anthocephalus indicus* kraft pulps and bleaching effluents characterization

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Abstract

Kraft pulps of *Anthocephalus indicus* of kappa number 39.49 and 24.76 were bleached adopting O/C/E/H/H, O/C/E/H/P and conventional C/E/H/H bleaching sequences. It was observed that bleached pulps possessed comparable strength properties; burst index, 5.33 + 0.27; tensile index, 87.30 + 1.55; tear index, 4.95 + 0.21 however, bleached pulp yield was about 7-8 % higher for kappa number 24.76. Intrinsic viscosity/degree of polymerization of pulps also holds the same trend. COD, BOD₅ and AOX values were 104.95, 37.56 and 7.54 kg/tonne of pulp (kg/tp) for O/C/E/H/H and minimum 45.25, 14.79 and 2.56 kg/tp for O/C/E/H/P bleaching effluents of pulp of kappa number 36.49 COD, BOD₅ and AOX values were 74.56, 27.46 and 5.20 kg/tonne for the C/E/H/H bleached pulp; 38.11, 14.36 and 2.80 Kg/tp for the O/C/E/H/H 32.23, 12.57 and 2.40 kg/tp bleaching effluents of pulp of kappa number 24.76. Thus, COD, BOD and AOX values were highest for C/E/H/H followed by O/C/E/H/H and minimum for O/C/E/H/P and appreciably decreased on oxygen treatment.

Keywords - Kappa number, Lignin, Viscosity, Bleaching, Degree of Polymerization

OP-62

शीर्षक – आर्टिफिशियल इंटेलिजेंस- दुष्प्रचार का खतरनाक हथियार बनती डीपफेक तकनीक

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सारांश: आर्टिफिशियल इंटेलिजेंस के दौर में असली, नकली की पहचान करना मुश्किल हो गया है। इस संदर्भ में प्रधानमंत्री नरेंद्र मोदी की हालिया टिप्पणी काबिलेगौर है। तकनीक के इस विकास के साथ मशीनों ने जहां मनुष्य के दैनिक जीवन के कार्यों को सरल और सुगम बनाया है वहीं, इस तकनीक के दुष्परिणाम भी देखने को मिले हैं। जहां आर्टिफिशियल इंटेलिजेंस में शुमार सिरी, अलेक्सा जैसे रोबोट ने मानवीय गुणों के अनुरूप व्यवहार करने में दक्षता हासिल की वहीं आर्टिफिशियल इंटेलिजेंस की डीपफेक तकनीक ने मानवीय मूल्यों को संकट में डालने का काम किया है। यह तकनीक अब दुष्प्रचार का खतरनाक हथियार बनती जा रही है। इसमें ऐसे एल्गोरिदम का इस्तेमाल किया जाता है जिससे यह पहचानना मुश्किल हो जाता है कि असली कौन है और नकली कौन? इस तकनीक के फायदे चाहे जितने हों लेकिन इसके जरिए प्रसिद्ध लोगों की प्रतिकृति बनाकर उनके खिलाफ दुष्प्रचार करना आसान हो गया है। डीपफेक तकनीक के माध्यम से पिछले दिनों दो भारतीय फिल्म अभिनेत्रियों का चेहरा बदलकर किसी दूसरे के शरीर पर उनका चेहरा लगाकर वीडियो सोशल मीडिया पर वायरल कर दिया गया। जिसे लाखों लोगों ने देखा। इस पर तमाम लोगों ने तरह-तरह की प्रतिक्रियाएं दीं। वहीं कुछ लोगों ने इस वीडियो पर चिंता जाहिर करते हुए इस पर रोक लगाने और इस तकनीक का इस्तेमाल कर दुष्प्रचार करने वाले पर सख्त कार्रवाई की मांग की। भारत सरकार के आईटी मंत्री के हस्तक्षेप पर सोशल मीडिया प्लेटफॉर्म से वीडियो तो हटा लिया गया लेकिन तब तक बहुत देर हो चुकी थी। सवाल उठता है कि डीप फेक तकनीक से जब सेलिब्रिटी के चेहरे के साथ छेड़छाड़ कर कुछ भी किया जा सकता है तो आम आदमी कब तक इस तकनीक के दुष्प्रभाव से बचा रह सकता है? यह तकनीक एक तरफ लोगों के चरित्र को धूमिल करने का काम करती है तो दूसरी तरफ निजता के कानून को सीधे चुनौती देती है। यह तकनीक भविष्य में अत्यधिक खतरनाक साबित हो सकती है।

बीज शब्द (KEY WORD) : आर्टिफिशियल इंटेलिजेंस, डीपफेक, तकनीक, दुष्प्रचार, हथियार।

OP-63

A Biased Perception of Domestic Violence against Men

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Abstract: The issue of domestic abuse is always raised in relation to women. When we hear the word "domestic violence," many examples of it from our everyday lives spring to mind, including verbal and mental abuse as well as physical abuse for dowry. Domestic violence, as defined broadly, is also known as intimate partner violence or domestic abuse. It can also refer to the actions of one partner against another or against their spouse. It can happen in many different kinds of partnerships, such as marriage, cohabitation, or dating. In our Indian society, women are disproportionately affected by these problems since they are viewed as having very little or no significance when it comes to the major decision-making processes. In a patriarchal and male-dominated country such as India, it is difficult to accept that males can also be victims of domestic violence. This stereotype suggests that domestic violence is mostly experienced by women. Every time, a man is assumed to be the culprit. However, with recent socioeconomic advancements changing family arrangements, domestic violence is no longer confined to women and affects both women and men. Men are also subjected to physical, verbal, psychological emotional, and sexual abuse. Male victims do not report these incidents because the laws and policies in our culture are biased and do not give them justice. The purpose of this article is to examine the problem of domestic violence against men. Gender-neutral laws against domestic abuse are in demand. On the other side, since domestic violence is typically linked to women, it is now necessary to alter our perception of it as well.

Keywords: Intimate Partner Violence, Physical Abuse, Psychological Abuse, Sexual Abuse, Gender-Neutral Laws.

OP-64

Government Health Expenditure as a Percentage of GDP and its Impact on Sustainable Development in Healthcare in India

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Abstract: The study "Government Health Expenditure as a Percentage of GDP and its Impact on Sustainable Development in Healthcare in India" looks into how the relationship between government health spending and sustainable development has changed throughout the course of the current Indian decades. This analysis focuses on the proportion of General Government Health Expenditure (GGHE-D) in relation to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as an indicator of public commitment to healthcare. The study investigates the relationship between changes in this expenditure and wider outcomes related to sustainable development by looking at decadal patterns. The initial results portray a complex picture that has fascinating ramifications for public health programs and policy. Key health indicators, such as the maternal mortality rate (MMR), infant mortality rate (IMR), and neonatal mortality rate (NMR), show a significant negative connection with GGHE-D. This suggests that there is a noticeable improvement in mother and child health outcomes as government health spending rises as a proportion of GDP. This study explores into the complexities of this correlation, considering potential contributing factors and contextual nuances. As India strives for sustainable development, understanding the dynamics of government health expenditure becomes important. The findings hold implications for policymakers aiming to allocate resources effectively for improved health outcomes, thereby contributing to the broader agenda of sustainable development in the country. Further research is needed to elucidate causal mechanisms and refine policy recommendations based on these insightful correlations.

OP-65

Evaluating Transformations: The Impact of Village Health Sanitation and Nutrition Day Program in India

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Abstract: Village Health Sanitation and Nutrition Day has been conceptualised as a community-level strategy for convergent actions in health, early childhood development, nutrition, and sanitation. This is a government programme aimed at delivering maternal and child health nutrition services at the village level. The programme involves the participation of various frontline workers and committees, such as the village health, sanitation, and nutrition committee (VHSNC). The VHSND sessions are organised regularly and effectively to bring about behavioural changes in the community and promote health-seeking behaviour. In this study, secondary research data were reviewed from various reports and government official websites. After analysing various official documents and research study data, it can be concluded that the Village Health Sanitation and Nutrition Day (VHSND) in India has had a positive impact on the availability and utilisation of health services in rural areas. Various studies have also shown that VHSNDs have improved the accessibility and quality of health services, leading to increased utilisation of modern care and visits to health facilities. VHSNDs have also been effective in promoting antenatal and postnatal care, as well as in-facility births. Additionally, VHSNDs have been found to have a significant effect on child height, indicating improved early-life health and human capital accumulation. However, there are still gaps in the provision of services at VHSNDs, with some sites lacking essential instruments and equipment. To sustain the impact of VHSNDs, it is important to ensure continuous supervision, equitable participation, align committee rules with existing decentralised government structures, and provide key supports such as engaging NGOs as implementation facilitators and sustained financial support.

Keywords: VHSND, VHSNC, maternal health, health services, postnatal care

OP-66

**EFFECT OF JOINT TRACTION ON OSTEOARTHRITIS OF KNEE- A REVIEW
OF LITERATURE**

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Abstract

Background: Osteoarthritis is a progressive degeneration of the joint cartilage which lead to the destruction of the cartilage and reduce or narrowing of the joint space. This will increase the friction and reduce the shock absorption of the joint and also affect the loading on the joint. About 3.8% of the world population is suffering from symptomatic knee osteoarthritis and the number keep on growing as the age increase. Osteoarthritis can be Primary osteoarthritis where the cause is not known or secondary osteoarthritis where there is a known cause. OA causes pain, joint swelling, stiffness, reduced range of motion, it reduce the strength of muscles, and it can also lead to deformity of the joint. It's also affect the activity of daily living. There are many ways to manage knee osteoarthritis, but in this study the focus is on finding out the effective of tibiofemoral traction for the management of knee osteoarthritis.

Methods: A literature search was conducted from the internet mainly from google scholar, PubMed, Medline by using the keywords knee osteoarthritis, tibiofemoral traction, knee distraction. Several research paper and articles between the year 2007 to 2023 and which are relevant to the topic.

Conclusion: Based on the present review of literature it is demonstrated that there is a beneficial effect of tibiofemoral traction on management osteoarthritis of knee.

Keywords: Knee osteoarthritis, Tibiofemoral traction, Knee joint distraction.

OP-67

Black Tea Consumption and Cancer Prevention: Current Evidence and Future Directions

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Introduction: - Black tea is among the most popularly consumed beverages worldwide, gaining recognition for its potential health advantages, particularly in potential cancer prevention. Extensive research has investigated the link between black tea consumption and cancer risk, yielding contradictory outcomes. Some studies propose that consistent consumption of black tea could lower the risk of specific cancers. However, the precise mechanisms underpinning this connection remain not fully elucidated. Thus, a comprehensive review of existing literature is necessary to evaluate the strength of evidence and identify avenues for further investigation. This paper aims to fulfill that need by critically examining the epidemiological and clinical evidence concerning the potential cancer-preventive effects of black tea consumption. Additionally, it explores the underlying biological mechanisms and potential confounding factors at play. The outcomes of this review hold implications for public health initiatives and strategies aimed at disease prevention.

OP-68

Synergizing Theory and Insight: An Integrated Theoretical Framework with HR Analytics for Understanding Employee Attrition Dynamics

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Abstract: In response to the evolving challenges of employee attrition, this research introduces a groundbreaking approach that unifies theoretical constructs with the transformative capabilities of HR analytics. This integrated theoretical framework not only advances our comprehension of employee turnover dynamics but also strategically leverages data-driven insights for a more proactive and nuanced understanding. The framework commences with a robust emphasis on data-driven foundations, incorporating HR metrics, key performance indicators, and historical turnover data. Employing sophisticated machine learning algorithms, the framework engages in predictive modeling to unearth patterns and variables predictive of attrition risks, enhancing the precision of our understanding. Breaking away from conventional paradigms, HR analytics facilitates the segmentation of the workforce, allowing for interventions tailored to individual needs. This personalized approach, rooted in analytical insights, seeks to optimize employee satisfaction, engagement, and ultimately mitigate attrition risks.

Integral to the framework is the integration of real-time monitoring systems and sentiment analytics tools. These technologies empower organizations to detect early indicators of attrition risks and gauge employee sentiment through feedback analysis, fostering a proactive response to potential challenges. HR analytics enables organizations to conduct thorough cost-benefit analyses of diverse retention strategies. The framework advocates for dynamic adjustments based on ongoing analytics, ensuring continuous optimization of retention efforts in response to the ever-evolving organizational landscape. The framework culminates in a strategic focus on exit interviews analyzed through advanced text mining techniques. Additionally, it emphasizes industry benchmarking and comparative analytics within the HR domain, offering insights into unique organizational factors influencing attrition and enabling organizations to contextualize their strategies within broader industry norms.

This pioneering integration of theoretical constructs with HR analytics not only expands our understanding of employee attrition dynamics but also equips organizations with actionable

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insights derived from the power of analytics. By synergizing theory and insight, this framework empowers organizations to proactively navigate attrition challenges and cultivate a resilient and engaged workforce.

Keywords: employee attrition, turnover, theoretical framework, HR analytics, predictive modeling, personalized employee experience, real-time monitoring, sentiment analytics, retention strategy, exit interviews, comparative analytics.

OP-69

**Exploring Parameterization Impact on Effective Majorana Mass in Inverted Hierarchy:
A Theoretical Analysis**

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Abstract: Neutrinoless double beta decay ($0\nu\beta\beta$), representing the inaugural signal for a lepton number-violating process, holds the potential to unveil concealed neutrino properties. This exceptionally rare, hypothetical second-order decay process, if detected, would conclusively establish the Majorana nature of neutrinos and facilitate precise measurements of their masses. The extraordinary sensitivity of this process is contingent upon the effective Majorana mass (m_{ee}), which, in turn, relies on CP-violating phases. Calculations of the m_{ee} range for diverse parameterizations within the inverted hierarchy of neutrino masses consistently align with the Particle Data Group (PDG) range and closely correspond to experimental data obtained from various experiments.

OP-70

**SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE:
FROM TRADITIONAL METHODS TO ONLINE ADVANCEMENT**

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The Sustainable Development is the most needful action in the world, which should be accelerate in next gear for now unless it will be too late. The advanced era of Artificial Intelligence could help achieve 79% of the Sustainable Development Goals. This research paper presents how AI is helpful for speedup our efforts to achieve these goals. It helps us to shift from traditional methods to the era of advancement. The nonstop working helps in analysing the data in a short span of time which helps in tackle with real time consequences and assist as a tool. For dispersing the awareness about sustainable development the use of online environment in different platforms like Facebook, Twitter and Instagram seems prove to be most useful. The paper also discusses about course of action, how to handle with the issues of AI literacy as well as the fear of humanity downfall. In concluding part, the paper also suggests the way forward for the interdisciplinary inclusion of early steps in social science research as the progressive world can't ignore the impact of artificial intelligence.

In this study, the paper signifies AI as a tool, neither enemy nor saviour. No doubt the social science research is product of humankind logical thinking but in analytical and prediction AI helps a lot than traditional methods.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, sustainable development, SDGs, AI, advanced methods, interdisciplinary research

OP-71

EFFECT OF TELEREHABILITATION IN STROKE PATIENTS WITH BALANCE IMPAIRMENT-A LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract: Telerehabilitation has emerged as a promising avenue for stroke patients with balance impairment. It has shown promising effects in stroke patients with balance impairment. Several studies and clinical trials have explored the impact of telerehabilitation on this specific population. The foremost advantage lies in the ability of telerehabilitation to break down geographical barriers. Patients residing in remote areas or grappling with mobility issues, can access rehabilitation services conveniently from their homes. Overcoming challenges related to transportation, this approach encourages regular participation in rehabilitation programs. Timely and consistent care is a hallmark of telerehabilitation, addressing disparities in healthcare access. The platform's capacity for remote monitoring allows therapists to tailor rehabilitation programs to individual needs. Beyond clinical advantages, implementing telerehabilitation yields cost savings. By reducing travel expenses and eliminating the need for facility usage, it alleviates the economic burden associated with in-person rehabilitation. This cost-effectiveness not only benefits patients but also renders rehabilitation services more sustainable and accessible. Telerehabilitation's interactive features, such as virtual reality or gamification, enhance patient engagement. Moreover, the flexibility in scheduling therapy sessions accommodates diverse patient needs, allowing for seamless integration into busy lifestyles. The COVID-19 pandemic underscored the resilience of telehealth and telerehabilitation in ensuring continuity of care during crises. Telecommunication emerged as adaptable solutions, enabling healthcare services to persist even when in-person visits were restricted. Telerehabilitation plays a crucial role in improving healthcare accessibility, promoting individualized care, enhancing patient engagement, and contributing to the overall efficiency of rehabilitation services.

Keywords: Telerehabilitation, Stroke, Balance.

OP-72

Novel Delivery System of Essential Oil

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Abstract: Essential oils play an important role in the field of the pharmaceutical industry. The novel delivery system can easily convert essential oils into many formulations like microemulsion, nanoemulsion, nanoparticles, nanoemulgel, etc. with the help of the Nobel technique. Essential oil-based formulations like microemulsion and nanoemulsion contain two phases which are mainly oil in water or water in oil. Essential oils come in the form of liquids that's by they are volatile and consist of aromatic odors which are mostly pleasant in smell. Over the previous years, unexpected developments have taken part and completed efficaciously in the progress of novel delivery of essential oil. Many types of essential oils like lavender oil, neem oil, clove, etc are beneficial for the skin and give both therapeutic and cosmeceutical benefits. Essential oils are intricate combinations of volatile oils and have chemical constituents like terpenoids, phenolic scented constituents, or aliphatic constituents and have a strong concentration in the field of cosmeceutical, pharmaceutical, agricultural, sanitary, and food industries. The formulation which is made with essential oils through the Nobel technique is easily used for bactericidal, insecticidal, and fungicidal, and on the other hand, it can also be used for therapeutic purposes like anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and sedative properties. Current advances in microemulsion and nanoemulsion are auspicious tackles to come across various boundaries of essential oil-based manufacturing and increase their activity and safety from external atmospheric conditions. Essential oils give many types of benefits which are beneficial for health and also in the field of cosmeceuticals and in the pharmacy industry.

Keywords: Essential oil, Novel delivery, Microemulsion, Nanoemulsion, Therapeutic property, Formulation.

OP-73

Customer-Centric Marketing: How AI is Shaping Customer Experiences in Modern Marketing

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Abstract: Marketing has been significantly impacted by artificial intelligence (AI), which has begun to change many facets of our personal and professional life. The application of artificial intelligence and Chat-GPT in marketing is revolutionizing how consumers are reached and engaged. AI may assist marketers with performing better across a range of tasks, including data analysis and programmatic advertising. In the past few years, it has become crucial for companies to be cognizant of and acknowledge customers' expectations and needs for both products and services which is the prime agenda of this study is to bring to the light how various AI technologies are changing the landscape of marketing. The data used for this study were gathered from secondary sources, which included a thorough examination of published research papers, official documents, scholarly journals, and trade publications. The study aims to examine the entire idea of applying artificial intelligence to marketing. It goes into detail about the positive aspects of using AI in marketing and how it is changing the industry in terms of new trends like Chat-GPT, voice and visual search, VR and AR, and many more. AI's necessity in marketing is demonstrated using instances from actual companies in the real world. The reader will also gain a thorough understanding of modern Artificial Intelligence marketing techniques as well as a comprehensive understanding of the AIM field.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Sustainability, Emerging trends, Consumer, Marketing

OP-74

Title: Linking Autonomic Nervous system to the Progression of Atherosclerosis: A mini-review

Running Title: Autonomic Nervous system and Atherogenesis

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Abstract: Progressive fat deposition leads to changes in vasodilation properties via dysfunctional endothelial cells in the arterial walls resulting in atherosclerotic plaque. Autonomics nervous system regulates the endothelial dependence vasodilation property. The appearance of nerve fibers outside the arterial wall was having a vital role in the progression of atherosclerosis. This review aims to summarise the role of nerve fibers in the progression of plaque.

Keywords: Atherosclerosis Plaque; Endothelial Cells; Immune Cells; Inflammation; Nerve Fibers.

OP-75

“ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND ORGAN DONATION: FUTURE POTENTIAL”

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Abstract: This paper explores the multifaceted challenges surrounding organ donation through the lenses of medical care professionals and social work perspectives, shedding light on the intricate dynamics that impact the organ donation process using Artificial Intelligence. Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative force across various sectors, and its potential to revolutionize healthcare is particularly promising. This research paper explores the intersection of artificial intelligence and organ donation to shed light on the current state, challenges and future possibilities. The shortage of organ donors is a significant global health challenge, and the use of artificial intelligence technologies can offer innovative solutions to address this critical issue.

The paper begins by providing an overview of the current state of organ donation and transplantation, highlighting the continuing gap between the demand for organs and the limited supply. It then dives into the role of artificial intelligence in healthcare, highlighting its ability to improve data analysis, decision-making and overall efficiency in medical processes.

Integrating artificial intelligence into organ donation processes represents a multifaceted approach, including optimization of organ matching algorithms, predictive analysis of organ availability, and streamlining of administrative tasks. Artificial intelligence has the potential to significantly improve the organ allocation process by considering various factors such as medical compatibility, geographic distribution and urgency.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Organ Donation, Organ Transplantation, Social Work.

OP-76

Molecular and physiological approaches for improvement of stay green trait in agricultural crops and their utility

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Abstract: The "stay green" trait in crop plants, characterized by the delayed senescence of leaves which, plays a pivotal role in enhancing crop productivity and stress resilience. Crops with enhanced stay green traits exhibit prolonged photosynthetic activity, resulting in increased yield potential and improved stress tolerance. This proves invaluable in the face of climate change, where unpredictable environmental conditions pose challenges to conventional crop production. Physiological interventions explore in understanding the intricate mechanisms governing senescence. By elucidating the biochemical pathways and hormonal regulation involved in leaf senescence, researchers can devise strategies to prolong the functional lifespan of plant tissues. This includes optimizing nutrient management, hormonal treatments, and environmental conditions to mitigate premature leaf aging. Concurrently, molecular strategies involve the identification and manipulation of key genes associated with senescence regulation. Advances in genetic engineering enable the overexpression or suppression of specific genes, such as those involved in chlorophyll degradation or nutrient recycling, to modulate the stay green phenotype. Additionally, genomic tools, such as CRISPR/Cas9, facilitate precise gene editing for targeted trait improvement. In conclusion, the integration of molecular and physiological approaches holds promise for tailoring the stay green trait in crop plants, fostering sustainable agriculture by enhancing resilience and productivity. These advancements contribute to the development of resilient crop varieties capable of thriving in dynamic agricultural landscapes.

Keywords: stay green, chlorophyll degradation, CRISPR/Cas9 and gene editing.

OP-77

The Role of Television in the Dissemination of Agriculture Information among Farmer

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Abstract: In today's world, information and communication technology (ICT) is highly significant. The majority of developing countries use various information and communication technologies for development of agriculture. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the type of agricultural information that farmers receive from television and the potential of television for disseminating agricultural information. The present study depends on primary data. The study has conducted in the Madurai East block in the Madurai District of Tamilnadu in India. Simple random sampling techniques were used with a total sample of 130 farmers from the rural areas. The finding of the study revealed that most of respondents are 41-50 age, have education secondary level and have farming experience 10 to 20 years. Most of the farmer have own television at home and prefer to watch television program. Farmer agreed that television as moderately effective in increasing agricultural income. Farmer is obtained through TV agriculture information are weather information, Crop protection, Post harvest techniques and Farm machinery etc. It also reveals that there is relationship between ownership of Television and income level of farmer.

Keywords: Television, Agricultural Information, Farmer, Perception, Viewing pattern.

OP-78

IN SILICO IDENTIFICATION OF POTENTIAL INHIBITORS OF COVID-19
PROTEASE FROM *Abrus Precatorius*

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Abstract: In early December 2019, the Corona virus (SARS-CoV-2) causing COVID-19 disease originated in Wuhan City, China. Then it has been spreading to several other countries, and it has caused a respiratory disease that has led to numerous deaths across the globe. In this study, we have used bioinformatics tools, PyRx and Autodock-Vina, to identify potent inhibitors against the main proteases of COVID-19. This investigation is aimed at determining the inhibition mechanism by bioactive compounds of *Abrus precatorius* seed extract interacting with COVID-19 virus proteases 6LU7, 6M03, 6VXX, 6Y2G, 6W6, and 7BUY. This will analyse the binding interactions of bioactive compounds with the main proteins (6LU7, 6M03, 6VXX, 6Y2G, 6W6, 7BUY) through the molecular docking method. Then, pharmacokinetics results and drug-likeness prediction results of the bioactive compounds of *A. precatorius* were done by Swiss ADME. We have identified some potent inhibitors from the compounds from the *A. precatorius* medicinal plants, such as Anthocyanins, Beta-sitosterol, Choline, Cycloartenol, Hypaphorine, and Pectin, which have proven to show a high-affinity interaction of inhibition towards the COVID-19 protease attributed to virus replication in the human body.

Keywords: COVID-19, bioactive compounds, inhibition mechanism, high-affinity interaction.

OP-79

Study of Feminism in Indian Context

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Abstract: This research paper delves into the multifaceted landscape of feminism on a global scale, examining its historical roots, cultural diversity, and contemporary challenges. Highlighting the waves of feminism, it explores the evolution from suffrage movements to intersectional approaches, recognizing the interconnected nature of gender, race, class, and sexuality. The paper scrutinizes the persistent issues faced by women worldwide, such as gender-based violence, economic disparities, and limited access to education. Emphasizing legal and political dimensions, it investigates the ongoing efforts to secure equal rights and representation, with a focus on diverse and empowering media portrayals. Additionally, the research addresses the economic empowerment of women, confronting wage gaps and workplace discrimination. Despite achievements, the paper acknowledges the global resistance and challenges faced by feminist movements, emphasizing the importance of international solidarity. Through a nuanced examination of the cultural, political, and economic aspects, this research contributes to a comprehensive understanding of the complexities surrounding feminism in the contemporary world. Keywords: feminism, equality, gender, women, race, class etc.

OP-80

Incarcerated Drug Traffickers: Reformation Programs for Offenders in Prison

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Abstract: Drug trafficking incidents are increasing alarmingly every year in India. Illegal trafficking as well as consumption for personal use also are on high. In 2022, Kerala topped in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances (NDPS) crimes; the second was Maharashtra, and both were high for personal use or consumption of drugs. Punjab has been third for registering NDPS crime but has been first for drug trafficking in India. A total of 4811 NDPS cases were registered in Madhya Pradesh in the year 2022. In the correctional services, the rehabilitation approach plays an important role by transforming the prisoners into better than they entered in prison. The objective of this study was to know about reformation programs in prison for incarcerated convicted drug traffickers. The study was conducted on 166 drug traffickers across nine prisons in Madhya Pradesh, India. The purposive sampling method was adopted for this study. The structured interview schedule was used for the collection of primary data. The result shows that most of the convicted drug traffickers (68.1%) have learned something in the prison as vocational training under the correctional programs for the prisoners. The offenders have different types of work assigned to them in the prison as guard duty, cleaning work, cooking, tailoring, agriculture work, carpentry, etc. A total of 88.6 percent of offenders have decided to do something better for their livelihood after release from prison. More than half of the offenders felt guilty and remorse for their deeds as it is against the norms of society. The study suggests that better rehabilitation training and positive thinking may be a betterment towards the reformation of offenders and rehabilitation in society.

Keywords: Drug traffickers, Offenders, Prison, Correctional programs.

OP-81

**Phytochemical analysis of methanolic crude extract of fungal endophytes obtained from
Psoralea corylifolia Linn.**

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Abstract: *Psoralea corylifolia* Linn., also known as “Babchi” is an endangered and medicinal plant which belongs to family leguminosae. It is found in tropical and sub-tropical region of all over the world. The present study was aimed to investigate the phytochemical analysis of methanolic crude extract of fungal endophytes isolated from *Psoralea corylifolia*. Total four endophytic fungi were isolated from methanolic extracts viz *Piriformospora indica*, *Alternaria alternate*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium citrinum*. The crude fungal extracts were assayed for different secondary metabolites as Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Glycoside, Saponins, Carbohydrate, Tannins, Proteins and amino acids. The result showed that the range of phenolic content was found to be 183.00 ± 0.000 mgGAE/g *Aspergillus niger* to 121.00 ± 0.000 mgGAE/g *Alternaria alternate* and the flavonoid content of fungal isolates was 699.00 ± 0.005 mgQE/g *Aspergillus niger* and 130.50 ± 6.111 mgQE/g *Piriformospora indica*. It was observed all phytochemicals are present in methanolic crude extract of fungal endophytes except tannins. Phytochemical examination of the methanolic crude extract of *Psoralea corylifolia* fungal endophytes concludes that these endophytes have the potential to be an important source of bioactive chemicals. To fully utilise these fungal endophytes for medicinal purposes and to convert their bioactive substances into useful applications for human health and sustainable agriculture, more research is necessary.

Keyword: *Psoralea corylifolia*, phytochemical screening, fungal endophytes, phenolic content, flavonoid content.

OP-82

Role of Chabot's in Enhancing Customer Engagement and Providing Real-Time Support in the F&B Industry in India

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Abstract: The Food and Beverages (F&B) industry is passing through a phase of culinary tradition and technological innovations, adapting to shifting consumer behaviours. In response to the evolving landscape, the sector has embraced technological solutions, with chatbots emerging as a pivotal tool for enhancing customer engagement and real-time support. This research explores the multifaceted role of chatbots in the Indian F&B sector, investigating their impact on customer engagement and support processes.

The study employs a mixed-methods research approach, combining quantitative surveys, qualitative interviews, and case studies. By analyzing literature, case studies, and insights from industry professionals, the paper aims to provide a nuanced understanding of how chatbots contribute to the F&B ecosystem. The research addresses the evolution of chatbots, their role in customer engagement, real-time support, and implications for the future of the industry.

Examining successful chatbot implementations through case studies, the paper highlights their positive impact on personalized experiences, streamlined ordering processes, and efficient support. However, challenges such as privacy concerns, technical limitations, and the need for continuous updates underscore the importance of a strategic approach to implementation.

Looking forward, the paper discusses future implications in F&B Industry anticipating advancements in Natural Language Processing, integration with emerging technologies, predictive analytics, voice-activated interfaces, and enhanced backend system integration.

Keyword- Chatbots, Customer Engagement, Real-Time Support, F&B Industry, India, Technology, Artificial Intelligence, Personalization.

Keywords: GGHED-General Government Health Expenditure, IMR-Infant Mortality rate, NMR-Neonatal Mortality rate, MMR-Maternal Mortality rate, SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals), Total Planned Behaviour (TPB)

OP-83

Attitude: A Determinant of Agricultural Graduates participation in Video Conferencing Technology

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Abstract: The study envisaged to evaluate the attitude of agricultural graduates towards Videoconferencing (VC) technology. Study focused at persuasion stage of adoption process of innovations. A Likert-type-scale was developed, which consisted of 23-items. The scale instrument had four sections, viz., training, distance learning, agricultural communication and extension management. Instrument was administered to randomly selected, forty agricultural graduates of Madurai Agricultural University (MAU), Tamil Nadu, India during 2020-21 academic years. Attitude survey proved insightful with agricultural students. They had positive attitude in applied areas of VC technology, viz. training, distance learning, agricultural communication and extension management. Significant difference between users and non-users of VC technology was observed. Users had significant positive attitude towards VC technology. An enhanced understanding of attitudes is imperative before effective intervention strategies to moderate attitudes for enhancing acceptance and implementation of VC technology. Including transfer of agricultural innovations, VC can be encouraged in services like training, distance education, extension management, communication, administration, health, education and knowledge sharing. For these, infrastructure available within National Agricultural Research System (NARS), India can be effectively utilized for learning and technical counseling. This study adds value to the body of knowledge in evaluation and theory building from attitude perspective. As standard methodology is lacking to comprehend mindset of agricultural students, it will serve foundation for other future investigations.

Keywords: Attitude, Agricultural Students, Technology and Video Conferencing.

OP-84

Antiviral Drug Discovery: Unique Aspects

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Abstract: This review explores the distinctive challenges and novel strategies associated with antiviral drug discovery, highlighting the unique aspects that set it apart from other therapeutic areas. Antiviral drugs face the daunting task of addressing the remarkable diversity among viruses, which exhibit a broad range of structures, replication strategies, and genetic compositions. Unlike bacteria, viruses lack independent cellular machinery, making it imperative to design drugs that selectively target viral components without compromising host cell integrity. The constant threat of viral mutation adds complexity to drug development, necessitating continuous surveillance and adaptive approaches to combat emerging drug-resistant strains. A comprehensive understanding of host-pathogen interactions is pivotal for identifying potential drug targets, often involving interference with specific stages of the viral lifecycle. The review emphasizes the importance of computational tools, such as molecular modeling and virtual screening, in unraveling complex viral structures and facilitating the identification of promising drug candidates. Additionally, the review delves into the challenges posed by viruses that establish latent or persistent infections, requiring drug development strategies that address both active replication and dormant phases. Collaborative research efforts and global surveillance emerge as essential components in the battle against emerging viral threats. Despite economic considerations, the urgency of managing viral outbreaks underscores the necessity for innovative approaches, international cooperation, and sustained research endeavors in the field of antiviral drug discovery. This comprehensive examination sheds light on the multifaceted nature of antiviral drug discovery, providing insights into the dynamic and evolving landscape of this critical therapeutic discipline.

Keywords- Antiviral drug discovery, Targeted therapies, Technological advancement,

OP-85

A Recent Advancement on Photocatalytic Behavior of d-block Metal Oxides

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Abstract: A photocatalyst is a substance that facilitates chemical reactions when exposed to light, typically ultraviolet (UV) or visible light. Photocatalysts are essential components in various applications, including environmental remediation, water purification, hydrogen production and solar energy conversion. Metal oxides have proven to be invaluable materials in the realm of economic and environmental applications. Hence, understanding their behavior in photocatalysis is crucial for harnessing their potential in addressing pressing global environmental challenges. This review summarizes the recent advancement on photocatalytic properties of d-block metal oxides focusing on their role in environmental remediation, solar energy conversion, and other emerging technologies.

Keywords: Photocatalysis, d-block elements, Photodegradation, Environmental Remediation

OP-86

Design a Conceptual Framework rooted in data science principles for the evaluation of how effectively machine learning solutions perform

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Abstract: The framework was created by isolating individual components of machine learning system development and analysing them separately. Several classification algorithms were used to apply clustering to datasets that had already been labeled. The datasets have numerical values for eight skills that make up a manager's overall profile. All of these numbers came from a comprehensive 360-degree assessment. After outlining a generic approach, we proposed a set of measures for rating the classifiers' efficiency. Our effort is primarily applicable in the real world, but it also guarantees a theoretical advance in the field. Any problem that could benefit from analysis of data with machine learning techniques could theoretically be solved using the suggested framework.

Keywords: Framework, Machine Learning, Implement, Algorithms, Functional

OP-87

**EFFECT OF DRUGS MODULATING RAAS ON EXCITATORY AND INHIBITORY
NEUROTRANSMITTERS OF BRAIN IN CHEMICALLY INDUCED
EXPERIMENTAL ANIMAL MODELS OF NEURODEGENERATION: A
PRECLINICAL NEUROPHARMACOLOGICAL SCREENING STUDY**

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Abstract: Drugs modulating RAAS in CNS may have important physio-pathological roles. Drugs modulating RAAS were selected to evaluate their effect on excitatory and inhibitory neurotransmitters of brain in standard laboratory animal models. The experimental drugs were searched and selected based on their favorable pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties. The experimental test drugs were prepared and administered as per the approved standard protocol. The various parameters including levels of excitatory and inhibitory neurotransmitters of brain were studied in the experimental laboratory animals. The experimental test drugs were able to exert their significant favorable effects on levels of excitatory and inhibitory neurotransmitters of brain in comparison to the vehicle control group [P<0.05].

Keywords: RAAS, Neurodegeneration, Neurotransmitter, Neuropharmacology.

OP-88

DRUGS BLOCKING RENNIN ANGIOTENSIN ALDOSTERONE SYSTEM HAD FAVORABLE SIGNIFICANT OUTCOME ON EXPLORATORY BEHAVIOURAL ENDPOINTS IN EXPERIMENTALLY INDUCED MODELS OF NEURODEGENERATIVE DISORDERS

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Abstract: It was well established that, motor functions are impaired in the chronic progressive neurodegenerative disorders. It has been well documented that, central RAAS has either direct/indirect link with the etiopathogenesis of chronic progressive neurodegenerative disorders. With this background it was hypothesized that, drugs modulating RAAS will have significant role in improving the motor functions [Exploratory] in neurodegenerative disorders. The drugs modulating the RAAS were selected and their equivalent doses in standard laboratory animals were administered as per the standard approved protocol procedure(s). The CPCSEA guidelines were followed with strict adherence while carrying out experiments on laboratory rodents. The study findings concluded that, drugs modulating RAAS showed statistically significant improvement in the motor functions [Exploratory] in neurodegenerative disorders when compared to the controls.

Keywords: Neurodegeneration, Motor, Exploratory, Preclinical, RAAS

OP-89

**DRUGS INTERFERING RAAS AND THEIR EFFECT ON INDUCED ANXIETY IN
LABORATORY ANIMALS: AN IN VIVO RANDOMIZED EXPERIMENTAL
STUDY**

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Abstract: Anxiety has been shown to be associated with neurodegenerative disorders. The pathophysiological link of anxiety disorder and drugs interfering RAAS is well supported as per the published medical literature. The role of drugs interfering RAAS and their effect on induced anxiety were screened in appropriate rodent experimental laboratory animal models. The anxiety in the experimental laboratory animal models were screened using elevated plus maze apparatus and exploratory hole board tests as per the defined and approved standard protocol procedure(s). The recommended human-animal equivalent doses of drugs interfering RAAS were administered and requisite parameters were recorded and subjected for comparison among the various study groups. The experimental test drugs had significant anti-anxiety properties in animal models.

Keywords: Anxiety, Plus Maze, Laboratory Animals, Preclinical Screening, RAAS.

OP-90

DRUGS TARGETING RENNIN ANGIOTENSIN ALDOSTERONE SYSTEM HAD FAVORABLE OUTCOME ON BEHAVIOURAL PARAMETERS IN CHEMICALLY INDUCED EXPERIMENTAL MODELS OF PARKINSON'S DISEASE

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Abstract: It has been observed that, chronic neurodegeneration is associated with various motor symptoms. It is crucial to explore in depth about pathophysiological connections in chronic neurodegenerative disorders. With understanding of pathophysiological mechanisms underlying chronic neurodegenerative disorders, it is the need of an hour to explore further this arena in more depth for better quality of life in patients suffering from these disorders. Drugs modulating RAAS were selected as experimental test drugs to explore their efficacy in chronic neurodegenerative disorders. With this prior hypothesis, it was decided to screen the efficacy of drugs modulating RAAS against experimentally induced laboratory animal models. The study findings had favorable outcome on behavioral parameters in chemically induced experimental models of Parkinson's disease.

Keywords: Neurodegeneration, PD, Dopamine, Preclinical Research, RAAS, Screening, Animal Models

OP-91

**DRUGS MODULATING RAAS HAD SIGNIFICANT AMELIORATION OF
INFLAMMATORY ENZYMES IN MPTP INDUCED EXPERIMENTAL ANIMAL
MODELS OF NEURODEGENERATION**

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Abstract: The research protocol received an approval from Scientific Advisory Committee [SAC] and Institutional Animal Ethics Committee [IAEC]. Throughout the experimentation, study protocol followed the national guidelines given by the Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals [CPCSEA]. The study had four groups and which were: Group I [Vehicle control], Group II [Negative control], Group III [Positive control] and Group IV [Experimental Test Drug]. The appropriate statistical test procedure(s) were applied to analyze the collected data for significant differences among the study groups(s) at P value of less than 0.05. The results of this research confirmed that, the inflammatory biomarker [Myeloperoxidase (MPO)] was significantly reduced in the experimental test drug [Group IV] when compared to the negative control [Group II] with $P < 0.0001$. It was also seen that, the values of MPO in the experimental test drug group were in comparison to the standard/positive control [Group III] with P value more than 0.05.

Keywords: RAAS, Neurodegeneration, Preclinical Research, Inflammation

OP-92

**SIGNIFICANT IMPROVEMENT OF IMMUNOHISTOCHEMISTRY SCORES
WITH RAAS INHIBITORS IN CHEMICALLY INDUCED EXPERIMENTAL
LABORATORY RODENTS**

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Abstract: Currently used drugs for chronic neurodegenerative disorders have many drawbacks including severe ADRs and hence it is necessary for further exploration in this arena. This research protocol was planned with an objective of evaluation of efficacy of RAAS inhibitors in chemically induced neurodegeneration in experimental laboratory rodent models on the brain Immunohistochemistry [IHC] scores. The experimental laboratory animals were randomized as per the approved standard procedures and the protocol into various groups. The collected data including IHC scores were compared among various study groups with appropriate statistical tests of significance at $P < 0.05$. The findings of the study resulted in improvement of IHC scores in experimental test drugs in comparison with the control group [$P < 0.001$].

Keywords: Neurodegeneration, Preclinical Research, RAAS, Screening, Animal Models, IHC

OP-93

EFFECT OF CALCIUM CHANNEL BLOCKERS ON IMMUNOHISTOCHEMISTRY SCORES IN CHEMICALLY INDUCED ANIMAL MODELS OF EPILEPSY: A PRECLINICAL IN VIVO STUDY

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Abstract: The calcium channels have many pathophysiological and biochemical functions in maintaining the physiological homeostasis in animals and humans. The modulation of these channels may play a vital role and therefore have many therapeutic roles in combating the pathogenesis of medical disorders. The primary objective of this research was to explore and further understand the role of calcium channel blockers in the neurodegenerative disorders. This study proposal was approved by the Institutional Review Board [IRB] with adherence to CPCSEA guidelines. The experimental laboratory animals were procured from the Institutional Central Animal House Facility [IAHF] and were allowed for acclimatization to the experimental laboratory for about 7 days. This research proposal was in adherence to the national and international GLP standards. The appropriate statistical tests were applied to compare the difference among study groups at prior fixed P value of less than 0.05. The results of this preclinical screening confirmed that, experimental test drugs [CCBs] significantly decreased the IHC scores in comparison to the vehicle control group [P<0.001].

Keywords: Neurodegeneration, CCBs, Preclinical Research, Rodents

OP-94

EFFECT OF CALCIUM CHANNEL ANTAGONISTS ON INFLAMMATORY BIOMARKERS IN PILOCARPINE INDUCED EXPERIMENTAL LABORATORY MODELS OF EPILEPSY

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Abstract: The research protocol got approval from the Institutional Research Committee [IRC] and the CPCSEA approved Institutional Animal Ethics Committee [IAEC]. This study protocol adhered all national and international guidelines including the Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals [CPCSEA] under MoEF&CC [GoI]. The study had different groups and were: Group I [Vehicle control], Group II [Negative control], Group III [Positive control] and Group IV [Experimental Test Drug]. The appropriate statistical test procedure(s) including parametric and non-parametric version(s) were applied to compare among different study groups. The P value of <0.05 was considered as statistically significant. The research findings of this protocol confirmed that, inflammatory biomarker [Myeloperoxidase (MPO)] was significantly reduced in the experimental test drug [Group IV] when compared to the negative control [Group II] with $P < 0.05$. It was also revealed and highlighted that, the values of MPO in the experimental test drug group were in comparison to the standard/positive control group(s) [Group III] with P value more than 0.05.

Keywords: Epilepsy, Neurodegeneration, Preclinical Research, CCBs, Screening, Inflammation

OP-95

"Towards a Carbon-Neutral Future: The Role of AI in Decarbonisation Strategies"

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Abstract: The threat posed by climate change necessitates quick action. The revolutionary potential of artificial intelligence (AI) in advancing decarbonization methods across several sectors is examined in this article. We contend that artificial intelligence (AI) can help achieve carbon neutrality by revolutionizing industries, enabling sustainable behaviours, and optimizing energy production and consumption. This paper explores AI's complex role in decarbonization initiatives. We examine its use in fields such as smart grids, green manufacturing processes, energy efficiency optimization, and integration of renewable energy. We look at how AI can improve transportation through intelligent traffic control and electric vehicle charging infrastructure, transform agriculture through precision farming, and aid in carbon capture and storage. The adoption of AI is hampered by issues with data privacy, employment displacement, and equitable access, all of which are acknowledged in the article. We provide methods for the ethical and responsible creation and application of AI-driven decarbonization solutions, with a strong emphasis on community involvement and teamwork. We demonstrate the concrete usefulness of AI in decarbonization initiatives by looking at case studies and real-world situations. We finish by stressing AI's enormous potential to hasten the shift to a future carbon neutral and by urging everyone to commit to using this technology for the good of the Earth and its inhabitants. Artificial intelligence can help with these efforts because it can analyse data, find trends that humans would overlook, and suggest the best course of action. It is another thing entirely to take extreme measures to effect change, particularly in the context of an economy driven by pandemics. Many businesses have been compelled to put off the task due to the difficulty and expense of fully calculating their carbon emissions and subsequently lowering or eliminating them. Artificial intelligence (AI) has the power to alter the rules in this situation.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence(AI), renewable energy, Carbon Emission, Decarbonization, Carbon neutrality.

OP-96

Biometric Facial Recognition System for Enhanced Urban Security

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Abstract: The "Biometric Facial Recognition System for Enhanced Urban Security" is a state-of-the-art security solution designed to bolster safety in smart homes and cities. This system utilizes advanced facial recognition technology as a secure and convenient method for identifying individuals. In smart homes, residents can enjoy a hassle-free and secure living experience as the system replaces traditional keys or passcodes with facial recognition. This not only simplifies access but also enhances overall security. The adaptability of the system extends to smart cities, contributing to the safety of public spaces and critical infrastructure.

The system integrates seamlessly with existing surveillance networks, allowing real-time monitoring and rapid identification of potential security threats. This proactive approach empowers law enforcement, enabling swift responses to incidents and fostering a safer urban environment. To address privacy concerns, the system incorporates robust data protection measures, ensuring that facial recognition data is securely stored and accessed only for authorized purposes. Ethical considerations are paramount, striking a balance between technological innovation and individual privacy rights.

In essence, the "Biometric Facial Recognition System for Enhanced Urban Security" stands as a pivotal solution to evolving security challenges. Its user-friendly approach not only simplifies daily life in smart environments but also sets a new standard for urban security, creating safer and smarter living spaces for residents.

Keyword: Urban Security, Smart Homes, Smart Cities, Facial Recognition Technology, Security Solution

OP-97

A Comprehensive Analysis of Image Forgery Detection Using Local Binary Pattern and Convolutional Neural Networks

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Abstract: The advancement in image processing and computer vision has been remarkable in recent years due to the growing availability of high resolution devices and escalating demand for intelligent visual systems. As digital manipulation tools become increasingly sophisticated, the need for robust and reliable forgery detection techniques emerges as a critical imperative to protect the credibility of visual content in the digital world. Traditional approaches frequently depend on manually crafted features and statistical analyses, which can be limited in capturing subtle tampering patterns and may struggle to adapt to emerging manipulation techniques. The Local Binary Pattern is a powerful texture descriptor that captures the local structure of an image by comparing each pixel with its neighbors. This method provides a robust representation of image textures, making it particularly suitable for detecting regions that have been tampered with. Convolutional Neural Networks, on the other hand, are inspired by the human visual system and excel at learning hierarchical features from images, demonstrating remarkable performance in a variety of computer vision applications. This research highlights the distinct capabilities of LBP and CNN, demonstrating how their collaborative integration enhances the detection accuracy and reduce the computational burden on CNNs across a range of image manipulations. Our analysis shows that incorporating Local Binary Pattern (LBP) into the classification task results in an enhancement compared to relying solely on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). The addition of LBP's texture information augments the CNN's ability to distinguish between different classes of images, leading to improved accuracy and overall performance in the classification task.

Keywords: Deep learning; image forgery detection; convolutional neural networks; local binary patterns; hierarchical features

OP-98

ASSESSING CPEC AND ITS SECURITY IMPLICATIONS FOR INDIA

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Abstract: The Pakistan- China relations have always had India as its central theme; with China trying to balance India in South Asia while Pakistan seeing China as a counter weight to India. CPEC is passing through Gilgit- Baltistan (GB) region which is a disputed area and illegally occupied by the Pakistan. Gilgit- Baltistan connects both Pakistan and China through Karakorum Highway. Pakistan, unlike India, has not produced an accession instrument. Endorsing the CPEC without consulting India will have security implications to India's territorial sovereignty. The corridor will lead to further integration of northern areas into Pakistan and may enable their occupation. Even Chinese presence may become a permanent feature, creating a possibility of future claims by Chinese for the strategically important areas of Gilgit - Baltistan. Since, the Partition of India in 1947 Pakistan's state authorities and local government bodies along with the army has controlled the territory to various extents. The increasing Sino-Pak Defence nexus, nuclear and missile technologies and strategic contacts are a cause of concern for India. The South Asian powerhouse is edged by two of its rivals from the past, both of which it has engaged in conflict with and is therefore in a precarious situation. Issues that encompass India's territorial integrity significantly challenge its strategic and geopolitical interests in the region. India is opposed to the proposal of the CPEC and thus, must work out own stratagem that would assist as a counter-weight in the region. The China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) involves Gilgit-Baltistan and this study will investigate the geo-economics and geo-politics of CPEC and security implications of this corridor for India's national security.

Keyword: CPEC, India, China, Pakistan, Gilgit- Baltistan, Economic, Security

OP-99

Increase in Violence in Balochistan Due to CPEC

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Abstract: In 1876 Balochistan came under the British Rule under a treaty signed between the British and the Kalat State. The 1876 treaty, specifically mentioned that the British government ‘engages to respect the independence of Khelat’ in exchange for the Khan of Kalat agreeing to ‘to oppose to the utmost all the enemies of the British government, in all cases to act in subordinate cooperation with that government, and to enter into no negotiation with other states without its consent...’.

At the time of independence, Kalat continued to maintain that its status was different from the other 565 princely states as its sovereignty was assured. In November 1947, The Pakistan Army was poised to launch an offensive, therefore the decided to accede to Pakistan on 27 March 1948. This was opposed by his brother Prince Abdul Karim and the first rebellion was started. But in the absence of adequate preparation, the prince was forced to surrender.

Similar armed struggles have been fought in the second rebellion in 1958 – 59 against the one-unit plan and the subsequent arrest of the Khan of Kalat, the third rebellion in 1962 – 63 against the Basic Democracy System and setting up of cantonments and the fourth rebellion in 1973-77 against the dismissal of the democratically elected government.

Since 2003, coinciding with increased Chinese involvement in infrastructure projects, the fifth rebellion is going on. Unlike the earlier rebellions this rebellion is being spearheaded by the educated middle class. With changes in the demography likely to be caused by CPEC, the will of the Balochs is likely to be suppressed in the simple majority terms. In 2003, when the Chinese took over the construction of the port and work commenced on the coastal highway to link Gwadar to Karachi, hardly any local labour was hired, not even for low-skilled manual labour, thereby fuelling resentment. With Gwadar being billed as the biggest thing to happen in Pakistan, people from all over the country procured land and most of it was cornered by officials and politicians. According reports, half the land was with the Pakistan Navy and the rest comprised housing and commercial schemes in which the who’s who of Pakistan had invested.

Balochistan has remained underdeveloped despite its natural resources. Due to ethnic tensions, poverty, and illiteracy Balochistan has remained violence prone, with attacks being directed against the security forces and Chinese workers. The reprisal has been severe with a number of cases of forced disappearances being reported.

The government of Balochistan also feels that the province has received less than its deserving share of the whole investment committed under the CPEC. Of the 62 BUSD investment under CPEC, Balochistan is getting only 600 MUSD.

Thus, CPEC has been one of the reasons due to which the ongoing rebellion in Balochistan, has continued for a far longer duration than all the previous rebellions. While statistically year on year casualties may not be alarmingly different, the fact remains that the violence has increased in terms of duration, in terms of geographic expanse and in terms of engulfing a larger cross section of the society.

Keywords: China, Pakistan, CPEC, Balochistan

OP-100
A STUDY ON PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF STEM EXTRACT
OF HIBISCUS SABDARIFFA, LINN.

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Abstract: Medicinal plants have been prescribed and used extensively for thousands of years to treat various disorders and ailments in traditional herbal medicine systems all over the world. The use of plants for healing purposes predates human history and forms the origin of much modern medicine. Clinical, Pharmacological, and chemical studies of these traditional medicines, which were derived predominantly from plants. The traditional medicinal plant *Hibiscus sabdariffa* belonging to the family of Malvaceae is chosen to conduct studies on Anti-oxidant and Phytochemical analysis. *H. sabdariffa L.* is used in many folk medicines. It is an annual or perennial herb or sub-shrub, growing upto 2–2.5 m tall. The leaves are deeply 3-5 palmately lobed and 8–15 cm long, arranged alternately on the smooth, cylindrical red stems. The flowers are auxiliary or terminal and 8–10 cm in diameter, white to pale yellow with a dark red spot at the base of each petal, and have a stout fleshy calyx at the base, 1–2 cm wide, enlarging to 3–3.5 cm, fleshy and bright red as the fruit matures. *H. sabdariffa* can be considered as a potent source of phytomedicine. The Qualitative phytochemical screening of stem extract of *H. sabdariffa* showed the presence of alkaloids, terpenoids, steroids, phenols, flavonoids, tannins, glycosides carbohydrates, saponins, and quinones. The phytochemical constituent exhibits the anti-bacterial, anti-fungal, anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory properties which shows the potent therapeutic activity of the plant. High content of phenolic and flavonoids in medicinal plants have been associated with their antioxidant activities that play a role in the prevention of the development of age-related disease, particularly cause by oxidative stress.

Keywords: *Hibiscus sabdariffa*, Phytochemical analysis, Anti-oxidant and anti-microbial activity, invitro studies.

OP-101

**Preparation and Characterization of Biopolymer anchored Schiff Base
Metal Complexes**

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Abstract: The polymers derived from natural sources are referred as bio-polymers, Starch, cellulose, chitosan and cyclodextrin are some low cost, renewable and biodegradable polymers which have great economic and environmental importance. Bio-polymers binds effectively with fine suspended particles, pollutants, bacteria, heavy metals etc. Thus, the biomaterial supported catalysts have attracted much attention in recent past due to their eco-friendliness, non-toxicity, biodegradable features, and high metal adsorption capacity.

The Schiff base ligands have hard donor-atom frameworks, good stability and can undergo easy modification. Therefore, the Schiff's base metal complexes find widespread application in chemical synthesis.

We have developed a protocol of anchoring the Schiff's base metal complex on to a bio-polymer. The Chitosan is explored as a polymer support to the Schiff's base metal complex. This enhances the activity of the Schiff's base metal complex by making it easily separable metal complex. The series of Chitosan supported Schiff's base metal complex is prepared and characterized.

Keywords: Biopolymer, Chitosan, Biodegradable Polymers, Schiff Base Complexes.

OP-102

Synthesis and Spectral characterization of Thiosemicarbazone ligands

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Abstract: Thiosemicarbazone ligands were synthesized using thiosemicarbazide and substituted thiosemicarbazone with diacetyl- α -monoxime. Structural features were obtained from their elemental analysis and spectral (IR, UV-Vis and ^1H NMR) studies. The ligands are of tridentate nature.

Keywords- Thiosemicarbazone, spectral analysis, biological activity

OP-103

Indian Laws for Women - From Tradition to Transformation

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Abstract: India's history is marked by periods of social and political change, and these shifts have had significant implications for women's roles and rights. For centuries, women in India were subject to traditional practices and societal norms that often restricted their autonomy and limited their participation in various aspects of public life. However, in the post-independence era, India embarked on a journey of modernization and development, accompanied by legal reforms aimed at improving the status and protection of women. Factors such as education level, socioeconomic status, and geographic location significantly affect legal awareness. Therefore, tailored educational and awareness campaigns are essential to ensure equitable access to legal knowledge among women. This study contributes to addressing the identified literature gap, offering a nuanced understanding of Indian women's identity protection in the context of legal reforms. The findings underscore the need for ongoing efforts to enhance legal awareness, culturally sensitive interventions, and reforms that address the evolving needs of modern Indian women.

Keywords: Legal reforms, Women's empowerment, Indian laws, Legal awareness, Gender equality.

OP-104

Assessing Risks in Food Delivery Packaging in India: BPA and Phthalates Migration
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Abstract: The escalation in the consumption of take-out foods has been conspicuous within India in recent times, resulting in the extensive utilization of plastic containers by numerous food delivery services. These containers, amounting to several hundreds of millions annually, pose potential health hazards due to the release of substances like bisphenol A (BPA) and phthalates into the contained food, potentially impacting the populace. To better understand this concern, a nationwide online survey was performed. The survey used questionnaires to explore Indian consumers' dietary preferences, frequency of take-out food consumption, average delivery time, and the types of packaging used. Based on the findings, an analytical approach was devised to identify and evaluate the migration of BPA and Phthalic acid from diverse food-contact materials (FCMs) into food-simulating substances such as water, 3% acetic acid, 10% ethanol, 50% ethanol, and n-heptane utilizing HPLC-UV. This methodology involved subjecting 105 FCMs to a temperature of 70°C for varying exposure durations (15, 30, and 45 minutes). Substantial levels of BPA (47.07 µg/ml) and Phthalic acid (50.75 µg/ml) migration were notably observed in 3% acetic acid following 45 minutes of exposure in polyethylene pouches. Factors contributing to heightened migration encompassed the selection of food-simulating substances, elevated temperatures, and prolonged exposure duration. A microbial bioassay utilizing the *Salmonella typhimurium* Ames bacterial reversion assay was conducted to assess the potential mutagenic effects of the migrated plasticizers. Several stimulating substances from diverse FCMs exhibited significant mutagenic attributes, particularly upon metabolic activation, implying potential genotoxic effects in mammalian systems.

Keywords: Plastic containers, BPA, Phthalates, Food-contact materials (FCMs), Mutagenic effects.

OP-105

**Role of Artificial Intelligence on Sustainable Agriculture and Environment
Conservation**

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Abstract: The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the realm of sustainable agriculture and environmental conservation has emerged as a promising avenue to address pressing challenges in food security, resource optimization, and ecological preservation. This paper explores the multifaceted role of AI applications in revolutionizing agricultural practices while concurrently fostering environmental sustainability. AI-driven technologies, including machine learning algorithms, remote sensing, and robotics, have facilitated data-driven decision-making processes for farmers, enabling precise crop management, predictive analytics for disease detection, and optimized resource allocation. Moreover, AI-powered systems aid in mitigating environmental degradation by optimizing water usage, minimizing pesticide application, and reducing greenhouse gas emissions through precision farming techniques. Additionally, AI plays a pivotal role in monitoring biodiversity, deforestation, and climate patterns, offering insights crucial for devising conservation strategies. While AI presents immense potential, challenges such as data privacy, accessibility, and ethical considerations necessitate comprehensive deliberation. This review underscores the transformative impact of AI in fostering a symbiotic relationship between agriculture and the environment, emphasizing the need for responsible and inclusive adoption to ensure a sustainable future.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Remote sensing, Precision Agriculture, Sustainability, Conservation.

OP-106

The pivotal role of 'R' software in the detection of spore discharge and dispersal of *Alternaria porri* incitant of purple blotch of onion, in hotspot regions of southern Karnataka

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Abstract: Purple blotch of onion pose significant threats to global cultivation and export, necessitating innovative approaches for early detection and effective management. This study explores the integration of spore traps with 'R' software solutions to enhance disease detection and monitor spore dispersal. Spore traps serve as critical tools for capturing airborne fungal spores, providing early indicators of potential disease outbreaks. The 'R' software enables automated spore identification, allowing for rapid and accurate finding of *Alternaria porri*. This information is crucial for tailoring precise disease management strategies. The study also highlights the role of predictive modeling software in assessing environmental conditions conducive to spore release and disease development. This proactive approach supports timely decision-making for farmers and plant pathologists. Additionally, the integration of machine learning algorithms enhances the predictive capabilities of the software, improving the accuracy of dispersal dynamics and disease forecasts. The integration of spore traps with 'R' software solutions represents a cutting-edge approach to detection and monitoring of purple blotch of onion. This synergistic combination empowers farmers and researchers with timely, accurate, and spatially-informed information, ultimately supporting sustainable and efficient disease management practices.

Keywords: Purple blotch of onion, Spore traps, 'R' software, Disease detection and Spore dispersal

OP-107

**A PRELIMINARY INVESTIGATION OF THE SYNERGISTIC EFFECT OF
METHOTREXATE AND GLUCOSAMINE ON HUMAN COLON
ADENOCARCINOMA CELL LINE, HT29.**

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Background: Methotrexate (MTX) is a potent inhibitor of the dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR) enzyme, crucial for intracellular folate metabolism, DNA synthesis, and cell growth. Widely used in cancer therapy, MTX serves as an anti-metabolite and anti-folate chemotherapy agent for various cancers such as breast, bladder, head and neck cancers, osteogenic sarcoma, leukemia, and colorectal carcinoma. Here we examined the synergistic effect of MTX and glucosamine on human colon adenocarcinoma cell line, HT29.

Methods: Human colorectal carcinoma cell line, HT29, was purchased from NCCS, Pune and it was cultured in Mc Coy's 5A medium with 10% FBS under 5% CO₂.

The anti-proliferative effects of MTX and MTX-glucosamine conjugate on HT29 using MTT assay.

Results: MTX exhibits potential as an anti-cancer agent, and its efficacy is notably augmented when co-administered with glucosamine. Treatment involving a concentration of 0.22 μ M MTX in combination with glucosamine resulted in a significant induction of cell death, with 85.95 $\pm$ 1.6% observed in HT29 cells. The substantial cytotoxic effect warrants further investigation, particularly through meticulous gene expression studies, to elucidate the precise mechanistic underpinnings of this synergistic interaction. This approach is crucial for a comprehensive understanding of the combined therapeutic impact and potential implications for cancer treatment.

Conclusion: This study represents a pioneering exploration, being the first to unveil the synergistic impact of combining MTX and glucosamine on the HT29 cell line. The findings indicate that the combined treatment surpasses the efficacy of MTX in isolation. This discovery holds promise in the realm of drug development for colorectal carcinoma, suggesting that the synergistic effects of the MTX and glucosamine combination could offer valuable insights for advancing therapeutic strategies in this specific cancer context.

Key words: methotrexate, synergism, HT29

OP-108

Artificial Intelligence in Crop Improvement

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Abstract: Attaining food security and sustainability in order to feed the ever-growing population has become major challenge now-a-days mainly due to increased biotic and abiotic stresses, climate change, lack of labour availability, over-fertilization of the land and subsequent decrease in arable land. The classical plant breeding strategy is a very laborious and time taking process when applied to most of the desirable complex traits. Breeding of better varieties in a very fast pace can be attained either through speed breeding or researchers can use predictive modeling algorithms, supported by Artificial Intelligence (AI). These trained AI and machine learning (ML) models deployed in mobile platforms contributes for rapid, large-scale scouting or for real-time detection of various biotic stresses. Moreover, trained ML models using AI helps in offspring and crop yield prediction in line breeding, speed up your hybrid breeding by 50%, improvising genomic selection, to link genomics and phenomics, multi-omics data integration. Over all, AI technologies can accelerate the development of climate resilient crop varieties with improved yield potential and stability and enhanced tolerance/resistance/ resilience to anticipated abiotic and biotic environmental stresses, and can deliver higher genetics gains in farmer's fields in less time.

OP-109

Artificial intelligence: A new tool for plant disease diagnosis and detection

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Abstract: Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a branch of computer science dealing with stimulation of intelligent behaviour in computers. Artificial means "man-made," and intelligence means "thinking power" hence "a man-made thinking power" and "it is not a man versus machine saga; it's in fact, man with machine synergy" AI is not a new word and not a new technology for researchers. This technology is much older than you would imagine. Even there are the myths of mechanical men in ancient Greek and Egyptian periods. The agricultural sector plays a pivotal role in global food security, and the timely detection and diagnosis of plant diseases are essential for maintaining crop yield and quality. In recent years, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative tool in the field of plant pathology, offering novel solutions for disease detection and diagnosis. This review paper provides a comprehensive overview of the recent advancements in utilizing AI techniques for plant disease diagnosis. World has many advanced technologies in the identification of plant diseases but artificial intelligence and machine learning is need of the hour with growing technological interventions in day to day life including agriculture. Cost-effective and reliable applications shall be developed which help the end users for easy detection of diseases and decision making in their management. There are many diseases which shall be considered for AI based diagnosis, their success depends upon strong, precise and accurate referral data authenticated by concerned experts. This review underscores the comprehensive overview of the recent advancements in utilizing AI techniques for plant disease diagnosis which emphasizing adoption of suitable management strategies against plant diseases and achieving the sustainable future.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, food security, Diagnosis, Detection and Sustainable.

OP-110

Effect of 12 weeks high intensity interval training on heart rate variability in patients with obesity-related hypertension: A Randomized control Trial

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Abstract: The objective of the present study is to evaluate the effect of high intensity interval training (HIIT) on measures of heart rate variability (HRV) in patients with obesity-related hypertension. Thirty subjects with obesity-related hypertension were randomly allocated to either HIIT or control group. The outcome measures evaluated before and after 12 weeks were measures of heart rate variability (HRV) including [Mean R-R intervals (MeanNN), Standard deviation of the R-R intervals (SDNN), Square root of the mean squared differences between successive R-R intervals (RMSSD), proportion of differences in consecutive R-R intervals that are longer than 50 ms (pNN50 percentage), total power (TP), low frequency normalized unit (LFnu), low frequency millisecond square (LFms²), high frequency normalized unit (HFnu), high frequency millisecond square (HFms²), LF/HF ratio]. The present study showed significant improvement in linear measures of HRV post-exercise training of 12 weeks [(SDNN $p<0.001$), (RMSSD $p<0.001$), (LFnu $p<0.001$), (HFnu $p=0.028$), (HFms² $p<0.001$), and (LF/HF, $p<0.001$). No significant group differences were observed for MeanNN, pNN50%, TP and LFms². However, significant group*time interactions were observed for (MeanNN, $p<0.001$), (pNN50%, $p=0.791$) and (TP, $p<0.001$) and (LFms², $p<0.001$) post-exercise training of 12 weeks. The present trial is suggestive of improvement in HRV measures post-12 weeks HIIT in obesity-related hypertensive patients.

Keywords: obesity-related hypertension, cardiac autonomic function, heart rate variability,

OP-111

The Application of Artificial Intelligence: An analytical study

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Abstract: The artificial intelligence is a technology which is now coming in fashion. It is making our life easy and full of comfort. There are so many applications of this technology in our day to day life like Alexa, Google Assistant etc. This paper will cover application part of artificial intelligence technology and its practical role etc.

Keywords: technology, artificial intelligence, comfort etc.

OP-112

Publicly Financed Health Insurance Policies and Sustainable Development: An Integrated Analysis of India's Path towards Universal Health Coverage

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Abstract: Sustainable development is a multifaceted concept that encompasses economic, environmental, and social dimensions. It has a profound impact on public health, both directly and indirectly. This research paper aims to conduct a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis of the intersection between publicly financed health insurance policies and sustainable development goal of universal Health coverage. By critically examining the key factors influencing this relationship, we seek to provide insights into how publicly financed health insurance policies can be harnessed to improve global health outcomes which is a goal of sustainable development. The study aims to provide a holistic view of the current state and future prospects. The research evaluates the strengths and weaknesses of insurance policies, explores the opportunities for further coverage, and identifies the potential threats and challenges faced by the healthcare industry in achieving the sustainable health goals. By employing the SWOT framework, this paper offers valuable insights to stakeholders for strategic decision-making and effective utilization of insurance in healthcare.

Keywords: Public health insurance policies, Sustainable development, healthcare sector, Health equity, Universal health coverage

OP-113

**SWIFT SIGHT: PIONEERING TOMATO BLIGHT DETECTION THROUGH
TENSORFLOW IMAGE CLASSIFICATION**

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Abstract: Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) is the second most important vegetable crop, the production and quality of tomato are known to be largely affected by the many pest and diseases. Among them, the fungal blight diseases caused by *Alternaria solani* and *Phytophthora infestans* are the major biotic factors which are limiting its production. Early detection of these diseases is crucial for effective disease management and sustainable agriculture. In the current study, innovative ai based approach utilizing tensorflow-based image classification techniques was employed to detect blight. The total of 1360 of early blight, 1930 of late blight and 2000 images of the healthy plant image samples were collected to build a comprehensive dataset comprising high-resolution images. Leveraging Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) implemented through TensorFlow at teachable machine web tool and the trained model was and validated for accurately classifying these images into healthy or diseased categories. The same trained model was loaded into the android application (kisan doc) which was built by android studio, which was built with simple and farmer friendly user interface. so, our approach in enabling rapid and precise identification of blight diseases in tomatoes, offering a valuable tool for farmers and agricultural stakeholders to mitigate crop losses and improve overall yield.

OP-114

Prevalence and Determinants of Excessive Daytime Sleepiness in Sedentary Young Adults: The Role of Sleep Quality, Anxiety, and Depression

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Abstract

Background: Excessive daytime sleepiness (EDS) in young adults may reflect multiple causes, ranging from lifestyle factors to various health-related difficulties, however, studies about its determinants are still scarce. The purpose of this study was to determine the prevalence of EDS and identify its relationships with sleep quality and mental health characteristics such as anxiety and depression among the young adult population.

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted on a sample of 100 sedentary young adults (age: 23.79 ± 2.76 ; 68 males and 32 females) from New Delhi/NCR India, who scored 'low' on the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ). The individuals were examined for EDS, sleep quality, anxiety, and depression using the Epworth Sleepiness Scale, Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index, and Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale, respectively. Ethical standards as per the Declaration of Helsinki were followed during this study.

Results: The prevalence of EDS among young adults was determined to be 28%. A correlation analysis was undertaken to identify the relationship between the variables under consideration. Spearman's correlation coefficient value was revealed to be a 'positive' value of 0.478 for EDS and anxiety, and 0.228 for EDS and depression ($p < 0.023$) consequently meaning that EDS moved in the same direction as anxiety and depression. No connection was observed between EDS and sleep quality. Following this, linear regression analysis was performed. The overall regression was statistically significant ($R = 0.509$, $R^2 = 0.259$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.235$, $F(3, 96) = 11.161$, $p = 0.00$). The results showed that EDS was significantly positively linked with anxiety ($\beta = 0.468$, 95% CI 0.454-1.145). No association of EDS was found with sleep quality and depression.

Conclusion: EDS has a positive association with anxiety in young adults. Therefore, while screening or treating EDS in young adults, their anxiety levels should be evaluated. Further

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research should be done employing objective measures to assess sleep accompanied by the underlying psychopathology in the young adult population. Keywords: young adults; sedentary; sleepiness; sleep; anxiety; depression.

OP-115

Prevalence and predictors of gynecological issues in working women: A cross sectional study

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Background and Aim: In this modern global world, women are playing dual roles of managing both the family and work responsibilities. There are many work burdens and home responsibilities that cause stress and increase complexity in their life. These stressors and over work have massive concern for the well-being, psychological stress and proper sleep. All of these issues cause many health issues in them including gynecological issues. Therefore this study aims to explore the relationship of stress, sleep quality, menstrual irregularity and gynecological issues among working women.

Methods: A cross sectional study has been conducted including 116 working women of mean age 32.12 ± 6.41 . It included validated standardized measure of sleep quality (Pittsburgh sleep quality index), stress (Perceived stress scale) and questions regarding menstrual history and presence of any gynecological disorder. Shapiro Wilk test was used to test the normality of distribution and Spearman's correlation coefficient and binary logistic regression was used to analyze the data

Results: The results indicated that 62.9 % of working women are suffering from any gynecological disorder, 53.4 % are having irregular menstruation, 85.3% are having poor sleep quality and 75.9 % are having mild to moderate stress. It was also observed that there existed significant positive association between sleep ($r = 0.39, p = 0.00$), stress ($r = 0.40, p = 0.00$), menstrual history ($r = 0.50, p = 0.00$), and presence of any gynecological disorder. Stress (OR = 4.26, 95% CI = 1.36-13.36), sleep (OR = 5.74, 95% CI = 1.10-29.79) and menstrual history (OR = 4.00, 95% CI = 1.85 -8.66) came out to be strong predictors of presence of gynecological issues in working women.

Conclusion: In order to reduce gynecological issues in working women, we should address sleep, stress and menstrual history.

OP-116

**EFFECT OF A PHYSICAL INTERVENTION ON PRONATED FEET SUBJECTS
HAVING CHRONIC LOW BACK PAIN: A PILOT STUDY**

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Abstract

Background: Low back pain (LBP) is a prevalent ailment that impacts approximately 80% of individuals at some stage in their lives. Previous studies have established a connection between pronated feet (PF) and chronic low back pain (CLBP). Physical interventions (PI) have mainly concentrated on addressing the lower back area exclusively, overlooking the biomechanical changes associated with PF in these individuals. The objective of this study was to assess the effect of a recently designed physiotherapy program on pronated feet (PF) subjects experiencing chronic low back pain (CLBP), specifically focusing on changes in pain and navicular drop (ND).

Methodology: Twelve PF subjects with CLBP voluntarily participated in this study. Following the screening process, they were randomly assigned to either experimental (EG, n=6) or control group (CG, n=6). EG completed tibialis posterior strengthening exercises and towel curl exercise, 3 times per week for 6 weeks. However, subjects in CG received only towel curl exercise. Pain and ND were assessed at baseline and at post intervention.

Results: The pain levels in the EG exhibited a significant improvement post-intervention when compared to the CG. ND decreased significantly in both the groups but EG exhibited a more pronounced decrease compared to CG.

Conclusion: This study demonstrated that the inclusion of tibialis posterior strengthening exercises to the towel curl exercises could improve important clinical outcomes, such as pain and ND in PF subjects having CLBP.

Keywords: Flat feet; posture; Medial longitudinal arch; Back pain.

OP-117

Preliminary qualitative chemical evaluation and antioxidant activity of *Trichosanthes cucumerina*

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Abstract: Finding natural and potent antioxidants to prevent pathological issues brought on by free radicals is now a rising area of research. This involves screening and measuring antioxidants from biological samples. The present study was to investigate phytochemical & antioxidant activity of ethanolic whole plant extract of Snakegourd (*Trichosanthes cucumerina*) plant belongs to cucurbitaceae family. Extraction was done by soxhlet method using ethanol as solvent. The phytochemical screening showed the presence of Phenols, Steroids, Alkaloids. The 1-1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging method was used to measure the antioxidant activity using ascorbic acid as standard. The results of this study indicated that the *Trichosanthes cucumerina* whole plant is a good source of functional ingredients, exert significant antioxidant activity on comparing with standard ascorbic acid. However, further research is required to isolate the natural compounds with fascinating biological and pharmacological effects.

Keywords: Traditional Plants, Soxhlet method, *Trichosanthes cucumerina*, Phytochemical Screening, Antioxidants, DPPH assay.

OP-118

Immediate effect of yoga module on state anxiety and selective attention among healthcare workers in a tertiary care hospital of Uttarakhand

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Abstract: The demanding nature of healthcare professions often contributes to elevated levels of state anxiety and challenges in maintaining selective attention among healthcare workers. This randomized controlled trial aimed to investigate the immediate impact of a brief yoga module on state anxiety and selective attention among healthcare workers in a tertiary care hospital in Uttarakhand.

A total of 17 healthcare workers were randomly assigned to either the intervention group (n = 9) or the control group (n = 8). The intervention group participated in a structured 20-minute yoga session, specifically designed to address anxiety and enhance selective attention, while the control group engaged in 20-min medium pace walking. State anxiety was measured using the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI), and selective attention was assessed through a six letter cancellation test (SLCT) immediately before and after the yoga module. Analysis of results revealed a significant reduction ($p = 0.02$) in state anxiety levels among participants in the intervention group compared to the control group ($p = 0.47$) following the yoga module. Additionally, healthcare workers in the intervention group demonstrated a significant improvement ($p = 0.002$) in selective attention as compared to control group ($p = 0.04$).

The findings of this study suggest that a brief yoga module has an immediate positive impact on reducing state anxiety and enhancing selective attention among healthcare workers. Incorporating such short and focused interventions into the daily routine of healthcare professionals could serve as a valuable strategy to mitigate anxiety and promote cognitive well-being. Further research is encouraged to explore the long-term effects and feasibility of integrating yoga practices as part of stress management programs for healthcare workers in similar settings.

Keywords: yoga, state anxiety, selective attention, healthcare workers

OP-119

Research on the physical and chemical compatibility of herbal pharmaceutical excipients with synthetic drugs

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Abstract: The goal of the current study is to determine whether a medicine is compatible with its excipient. The medicine propranolol was chosen as the model drug, and the excipients were fenugreek seed gum (FSG) and tamarind seed gum (TSG). The studies were done by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray diffraction study (XRD) and Thin layer chromatography (TLC). The spectrophotometric graphs showed that there was no significant alteration occurred in position of functional groups in pure drugs and their herbal excipients with respect to their physical mixtures. X-ray diffraction study represented that the characteristic peaks of drug appeared which showing that drug and their excipients was present as a crystalline form as well. The R_f values of the physical mixtures obtained from TLC study on the 0th and 30th day were approximately similar to the R_f values of the pure drug and herbal excipients. All of the experimental results and retention factor clearly validated that the synthetic-herbal drug combinations with pharmaceutical excipients are compatible with each other and can be utilized for successful development of different dosage formulations.

Keywords: FTIR, Compatibility study, TLC, propranolol, Tamarind seed gum, Fenugreek seed gum XRD.

OP-120

Comparison of the effect of two different buffer systems used for the estimation of serum Alkaline Phosphatase on interpretation of the test results.

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Abstract

Objectives: The commonly used IFCC method for Alkaline Phosphatase estimation is based p-Nitrophenyl Phosphate (pNPP) substrate and either of two buffers 2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol (AMP) or Diethanolamine (DEA), this study was carried out with the objective of comparing both buffers and to find out any significant impact on interpretation of the results.

Methodology: This method comparison study was carried out on 75 adult patients' serum samples including normal & abnormal liver function, samples were tested simultaneously with both kits in same analyser. Statistical analysis was done using comparison plot & calculating coefficient of comparison (r) & determination (r^2), comparison was done by paired t test & Bland Altman plot.

Results: The data is distributed normally as shown by Shapiro Wilk p-value 0.52 ($\alpha = 0.05$). Mean & SD with AMP & DEA buffers were 125.95 +/-81.35 U/L & 260.12 +/- 206.39U/L respectively. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) 0.9936 & coefficient of determination (r^2) 0.9872 shows very strong direct relationship in the results. In paired t test, t is 9.22 & p is <0.0001 shows significant difference in the results with both the buffers. Bland–Altman plot shows proportional bias ie the difference in the results increases with higher values. We derived a conversion factor of 2.06 to convert the values obtained from one buffer to another.

Conclusion: This study concludes that both the buffers cannot be used interchangeably and switching over will require either a different reference range or use of a conversion factor which every lab should derive for themselves to avoid false interpretation of patients results.

OP-121

Impact of Chronic Constipation on Aerobic Capacity in Young Adults: A Review

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Introduction

Constipation is not only common in these times but considered a normal phenomenon these days. Constipation lasting for more than 3 months is called as Chronic Constipation. Chronic constipation is characterized by unsatisfactory defecation/feeling of incomplete evacuation, infrequent stools and difficult passage of stools/bowel emptying or all of them. Various factors are involved in the pathogenesis of the disease, including type of diet, genetic predisposition, colonic motility, absorption, social economic status, daily behaviors, and biological and pharmaceutical factors Chronic Constipation leads to numerous side effects which are not limited to social factors but also to psychological factors. It has been seen that aerobic capacity which is the product of capacity of cardiopulmonary system to supply oxygen and the capacity of utilizing oxygen by skeletal muscles is also majorly affected by chronic constipation. In today's time when constipation is not just limited to adults but younger ones are also experiencing the terror of this disease, it is not only required to investigate but necessary to find a way to remedy the situation. With this review we want to find out if aerobic capacity is affected by chronic constipation in young adults.

Methodology: To construct a narrative review on this topic, we examined a number of databases, Google Scholar, Medline, PubMed, Researchgate and Books. Discussion Constipation leads to lack of physical activity which ultimately affects the aerobic capacity of the patient.

Conclusion: Aerobic exercises and Physical activity may be a feasible and effectual option for young adults suffering from Chronic constipation due to which their aerobic capacity is affected.

Keywords: Impact, Young Adults, Aerobic Capacity, Chronic Constipation, Respiratory Status

OP-122

Role of serology in COVID diagnosis

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Abstract: Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV2) has imposed catastrophic impressions on the world. The role and performance of various serological tests for the diagnosis of COVID-19 are unclear. This study aimed to evaluate the performance of seven commercially available serological assays for SARS-CoV-2 antibodies by testing COVID-19 cases and controls.

The serology assays are important adjuncts for the diagnosis of COVID-19 in patients with persistent symptoms, especially in the second week of illness.

Serological diagnosis is usually based on either the demonstration of the presence of specific IgM antibodies or a significant increase in the levels of specific IgG antibodies between two consecutive samples taken 1-4 weeks apart.

Serology testing measures the host antibody response in the form of immunoglobulins (Ig) Such as IgM, IgA, or IgG following infection and/or vaccination. IgM production begins as early as seven days post-infection. By day 14, the majority of individuals should have a detectable antibody response. False negative serology results may occur if testing is performed too soon after exposure where antibody production is non-detectable.

Primary serological tests are used to detect the presence of antibodies in a patient's serum. Secondary serological tests are used to confirm the presence of antibodies and determine their type.

Primary serological tests can be used for both diagnostic and screening purposes. Primary serological testing can provide a rapid diagnosis, while secondary serological tests require more time and resources to perform

Reference

1. Lu H., Stratton C.W., and Tang Y. W. 'Outbreak of pneumonia of unknown etiology in Wuhan , China ; The mystery and the miracle, 'Journal of medical virology , vol.92, no. 4, pp. PubMed
2. WHO Coronavirus COVID-19 Dashboard, update 24 September 2021.

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3. DR. RAMYA KANNAN
4. Predicting COVID-19 severity with a specific nucleocapsid antibody plus disease risk factor score.
5. Sen S, Sanders EC, Gabriel KN, et al.

OP-123
Study of Jaundice in Neonates
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Jaundice in new born is very common. As newborns are having continuous transition in anatomy which result in excessive breakdown of RBC which results in bilirubin buildup in infant's body.

Bilirubin is toxic for infant's body and excessive buildup can cause damage to body particularly in brain can cause neurological compromise in infant which me cause long term problems.

DIAGNOSIS

- **Serum Analysis** (Normal Range: 0.1-1.2mg/dL).

Diagnosis of hyperbilirubinemia confirmed by measurement of serum bilirubin. Noninvasive techniques for measuring bilirubin in infants, including trans-cutaneous and digital photography-based techniques, are being used increasingly and correlate well with serum bilirubin measurements. Risk of hyperbilirubinemia is based on age-specific total serum bilirubin levels.

A bilirubin concentration >10 mg/dL in preterm infants or >18 mg/dL in term infants warrants additional testing, including hematocrit, blood smear, reticulocyte count, direct Coombs test, total serum bilirubin and direct serum bilirubin concentrations, and blood type and Rh group of the infant and mother.

Other tests, such as blood, urine, and cerebrospinal fluid cultures to detect sepsis and measurement of red blood cell enzyme levels to detect unusual causes of hemolysis, may be indicated by the history and physical examination. Such tests also may be indicated for any neonates with an initial bilirubin level >25 mg/dL

- **Visual examination**

VISIBLE SYMPTOMS OF JUANDICE VARYING WITH BILURUBIN LEVEL:

The serum bilirubin level required to cause jaundice varies with skin colour and body region, but jaundice usually becomes visible on the sclera at a level of 2 to 3 mg/dL and on the face at about 4 to 5 mg/dL. With increasing bilirubin levels, jaundice seems to advance in a head-

to-foot direction, appearing at the umbilicus at about 15 mg/dL and at the feet at about 20 mg/dL. Slightly more than half of all neonates become visibly jaundiced in the first week of life.

Almost all hyperbilirubinemia in the immediate neonatal period is unconjugated, which is termed indirect bilirubin, based on older laboratory measurement methods; conjugated bilirubin is termed direct bilirubin.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF NEONATE JUANDICE

The majority of bilirubin is produced from the breakdown of hemoglobin into unconjugated bilirubin (and other substances). Unconjugated bilirubin binds to albumin in the blood for transport to the liver, where it is taken up by hepatocytes and conjugated with glucuronic acid by the enzyme uridine diphosphogluconurate glucuronosyltransferase (UGT) to make it water-soluble. The conjugated bilirubin is excreted in bile into the duodenum. In adults, conjugated bilirubin is reduced by gut bacteria to urobilin and excreted. Neonates, however, have less bacteria in their digestive tracts, so less bilirubin is reduced to urobilin and excreted. They also have the enzyme beta-glucuronidase, which deconjugates bilirubin. The now unconjugated bilirubin can be reabsorbed and recycled into the circulation. This process is called enterohepatic circulation of bilirubin.

PHYSIOLOGICAL CAUSES

- Increased red cell volume and increased red cell destruction.
- Decreased conjugation of bilirubin d/t decreased UDPG-T activity.
- Increased enterohepatic circulation d/t decreased gut motility.
- Decreased hepatic secretion of bilirubin.
- Decreased liver cell uptake of bilirubin d/t decreased ligandin.

PATHOLOGICAL CAUSES

- Excessive red cell hemolysis.
- Defective conjugation of bilirubin.
- Breast milk jaundice.
- Metabolic and endocrine disorder.
- Substance and disorder that affects binding.
- Miscellaneous.

Neonatal Jaundice can be treated by Phototherapy or Exchange transfusion.

References

1. **[POCT management of neonatal bilirubinemia – guidelines for an optimization of kernicterus monitoring].**

Vaubourdolle M, Mailloux A.

2. **Care practices and neonatal survival in 52 neonatal intensive care units in Telangana and Andhra Pradesh, India: A cross-sectional study.**

Hanson C, Singh S, Zamboni K, Tyagi M, Chamarty S, Shukla R, Schellenberg J.

3. **[Efficacy and safety of intravenous immunoglobulins in the management of neonatal hyperbilirubinemia due to ABO incompatibility: a meta-analysis].**

Cortey A, Elzaabi M, Waegemans T, Roch B, Aujard Y.

OP-124

Effect of Anemia on Movement during Gestational Period

Neha

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Abstract: You may have anemia during pregnancy if a complete blood count (CBC) so that your red blood cell which carry oxygen through your body, are low. This can make you feel out of breath, in most causes of anemia during pregnancy, tweaks to your diet can put you on the right path.

TYPE OF ANAEMIA AFFECTING PREGNANCY WOMEN.

There are more than 400 type of anaemia. Some are more common during pregnancy including, *Iron deficiency anemia. From a lack of iron*

Folate deficiency anaemia. From a lack of folic acid. deficiency anaemia. From a lack of vitamin B12 .Is it normal to be anemia during pregnancy.

Yes. Because blood volume increase during pregnancy, mild anaemia is normal iron deficiency is common in pregnancy, with up to 52% of pregnant women developing countries not getting enough iron

ANEMIA EFFECT THE BABY DURING PREGNANCY

Anemia can affect the growth of the foetus especially during the first trimester. If anaemia goes untreated your baby is at higher risk of having anaemia after birth which can lead to development problems also anemia increase the risk of delivery your baby early and having a low weight baby.

CURTAIN DISEASE INCLUDING, SICKLE CELL ANAEMIA AND THALASSEMIA

Donating blood. Heavy menstrual flow. (Before pregnancy) ulcer and polyps.

Symptoms of anaemia during pregnancy.

Fatigue, cold, shortness of breath, weakness, fast heartbeat, headache, skin pale, dry or easily bruised skin.

Diagnosis and test. (How is anaemia during pregnancy diagnosed) A blood test called a complete blood count CBC can diagnose anemia. This blood test is after your first prenatal appointment.

Your health care provider uses the CBC to analyse:

How many red blood cell you have, their size and shape.

How much iron your body has stored.If you are low in vitamins B12 and B9.WHAT IS CONSIDERED SEVERE ANAEMIA

Savere anemia is when result of the CBC so hemoglobin that 6.5 to 7.9 gram per decilita your result so you have savere anemia.How is anemia treated in pregnancy. Treatment for anemia during pregnancy depend on the severity. if you have.

Mild to moderat anaemia. You provider will usually treat it with a daily prenatal vitamin aur iron supplement.Sever anemia. You may need a blood transfusion.

References

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4375689/>.

<https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/23112-anemia-during-pregnancy>.

<https://www.hindawi.com/journals/bmri/2019/7613868/>.

<https://www.vinmec.com/en/news/health-news/what-are-the-effects-of-anemia-during-pregnancy-on-mother-and-baby/>.

OP-125

Alteration of Red Cell Indices during Iron Deficiency Anemia

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Abstract: Iron deficiency anemia is a common disease characterized by a decreased number of red blood cells (RBCs) and, as a result, hemoglobin levels. This deficiency negatively affects various RBC indices and provides important diagnostic insights for medical professionals. Mean corpuscular volume (MCV), a key parameter for measuring the average size of red blood cells, is particularly affected in iron deficiency anemia.

Microcytic red blood cells, which result from a lack of iron that supports normal growth, contribute to the reduction of MCV. This reduction serves as a basic indicator for medical professionals and helps assess the hematology status of the patient. Mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), which represents the average amount of hemoglobin per red blood cell, is another important red cell index affected by iron deficiency anemia.

Iron is essential for hemoglobin synthesis, so iron deficiency reduces MCH, resulting in a lighter red blood cell colour. These cells have reduced hemoglobin content, so they appear paler when examined under a microscope. The mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC), which measures the concentration of hemoglobin in red blood cells, is decreased in iron-deficiency anemia, indicating that the hemoglobin inside the cells is diluted. This decrease is consistent with the hypochromic nature of red blood cells observed in iron-deficient conditions.

In addition to MCV, MCH, and MCHC, red blood cell distribution width (RDW) is also affected by iron deficiency anemia. RDW, which measures fluctuations in red blood cell size, is often increased in iron-deficient conditions. This increase reflects greater variation in cell size and emphasizes the coexistence of microcytic and normocytic cells in the circulatory system. Altered RDW further emphasizes the effect of iron deficiency on red blood cell morphology.

Together, these changes in red blood cell indices provide a comprehensive understanding of iron deficiency anemia and play an important role in diagnosis. Distinct changes in MCV, MCH, MCHC, and RDW collectively represent valuable diagnostic markers for healthcare

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professionals, and these indicators contribute to a differentiated assessment of a patient's hematology profile and It helps distinguish deficiency anemia from other types of anemia, allowing for targeted and effective treatment strategies.

In summary, this summary highlights the importance of red blood cell indices in the diagnosis of iron deficiency anemia. The observed changes in MCV, MCH, MCHC, and RDW together contribute to a comprehensive understanding of hematology changes associated with iron deficiency

This overview highlights the importance of these indicators as diagnostic markers that allow healthcare professionals to make accurate assessments and timely interventions to improve patient outcomes.

Reference: <https://en.wikipedia.org> , <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK260/>

OP-126

Linking local producers to a global customer base leading to rural success in cyber market

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Abstract: This abstract aims into the creation and impact of a cyber-marketplace at empowering rural success by connecting local producers with a global customer. Early findings show that there's a big boost in how much people see and buy products from rural producers in the online marketplace. Previous study have found that local artisans and farmers encounter difficulties in marketing their products beyond their immediate locales due to economic marginalization faced by rural producers, resulting from their limited access to broader markets. The cyber market addresses this challenge by providing a user friendly virtual platform for rural entrepreneurs to exhibit and sell their offerings to a diverse customer base through effective online market strategies, empowering rural producers economically. It focuses on using a complete marketing strategy, which involves promoting on social media and making sure products can be easily found on search engines. The sales data can be collected and analyzed on how users interact with the platform, and the economic impact to see if the proposed methodology is successful. Various initiatives such as those by the government of India that promote rural entrepreneurship and digital inclusion can be noteworthy like digital India, e-NAM (National Agriculture Market), Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana, Make in India.

In summary, the online marketplace has shown it can help rural communities by linking local producers to customers worldwide. This effort seems to have the potential to boost economic growth and sustainability in rural areas. As technology keeps playing a crucial role in how markets work, this model stands as proof of how digital platforms can make a real difference in promoting prosperity in rural regions.

Keywords: Cyber Market, economic marginalization, virtual platform, digital platforms

OP-127

A study on sentiment analysis in teaching learning scenario

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Abstract: Sentiment analysis, also known as opinion mining, stands as a prominent Natural Language Processing (NLP) application utilized extensively to discern human intentions conveyed through reviews. Within the realm of education, opinion mining serves to attentively grasp student perspectives, contributing to the refinement of pedagogical practices. Recent advancements in sentiment annotation techniques and Artificial Intelligence (AI) methodologies allow for the automated labeling of student comments based on their sentiment, minimizing the need for substantial human intervention. This review article addresses various facets: (1) exploring emotional analysis in education at document, sentence, entity, and aspect levels; (2) delving into sentiment annotation techniques, including lexicon-based and corpus-based approaches for unsupervised annotations; (3) examining the role of AI in sentiment analysis, encompassing machine learning, deep learning, and transformers; and (4) elucidating the impact of sentiment analysis on educational procedures, enhancing pedagogy, decision-making, and evaluation. Educational institutions have invested significantly in developing sentiment analysis tools to process student feedback, extracting valuable opinions and insights. The study reviews applications founded on sentiment analysis of student feedback and delves into challenges such as multi-polarity, polysemous expressions, negation words, and opinion spam detection. It also explores current trends in sentiment analysis research. The review concludes by discussing future directions for sentiment analysis in education.

Keywords: Psychology, human emotion detection, supervised learning, unsupervised learning, natural language processing, sentiment analysis, text analysis, opinion mining, behavioral prediction

OP-128

Decoding the Roots of Agony: Exploring the Depths of Cancer-Related Neuropathic Pain

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Abstract: The phrase "neuropathic pain" refers to discomfort brought on by a malfunctioning nervous system. Neuropathic pain can have a variety of different etiologies, such as poisoning, surgery, radiation, trauma, and congenital anomalies. Neuropathic pain is pain brought on by a lesion, damage, or dysfunction of the somatosensory nerve system. Neuropathic pain syndromes associated with cancer are common and debilitating side effects of a patient's main malignancy or medical therapies, such as surgery, radiation, or chemotherapy. Cancer pain often has a mixed etiology or, if it is solely neuropathic, may be one of many pains that a patient experience. Cancer treatments like surgery, radiotherapy, and chemotherapy can have unintended consequences (side effects or complications) or complications, including pain. Chemotherapy or tumors that directly damage the nervous system, such as malignant ones, are the main causes of it, which frequently happen in cancer patients. The most easily categorized clinical presentation involving pain, sensory alterations, and possibly neuromotor involvement is chemotherapy-induced neuropathy. Neuropathic pain often lasts for a long time and either is constant or is divided into numerous painful intervals. It is important to distinguish neuropathic pain from other cancer-related aches because it has worse pain outcomes and requires different treatment techniques. This paper exploring prevalence, underlying mechanisms, impact of nervous and sensory pathways, identification of risk factors and current approaches for cancer related pain management.

Keywords: Neuropathic Pain, Chemotherapy, Radiation, Cancer.

OP-129

“A STUDY ON SEXUAL HARASSMENT FOR WOMEN AT WORKPLACE AND PREVENTING MEASURES”

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Abstract: Sexual harassment is one of the significant issues in majority of organizations. Sexual harassment at workplace is an unwelcoming behavior indulged to employees by their senior authorities or even colleagues. Such inappropriate behavior makes an employee feel uncomfortable and disturbed. It leads the employee to experience an awful, inadequate air at the working environment. It is most commonly seen in case of women’s and the number of cases filed is higher compared to males. It is not specified to any sector of employment or to subjective level, women of every job post gets harassed and which shows the level of security available for women in their working organizations. Any kind of harassment is wrong, but sexually harassing in particular is against women’s right to work. As it makes the working environment more hostile and uncertain, which makes women less likely to take the lead and curbs their ability to be financially independent and strive for all-around development. This results in various negative impacts in both organizational and personal development such as decreased job satisfaction, depression, loss of motivation, diminished sense of self worth, etc. Therefore this paper studies about various methods of sexual harassment experienced by the victims and the consequences face by them under different traits. It is important to create a sense of security in working organizations for efficient performance. It is important to insure that the emphasis is on prevention rather than corrective action. Thus it also speaks about the effective recommendations to prevent sexual harassment at workplace.

Keywords: Sexual harassment, Workplace, Women, Sexual behavior, Organization

OP-130

Behind the Degrees: Decoding Imposter Syndrome among Medical Students from Eastern India- a Cross Sectional Study

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Abstract

Background: The term Impostor Syndrome (IS) or Impostor Phenomenon (IP) was coined by psychological researchers Pauline Clance and Suzanne Imes in 1978. Those who have IP will be less likely to actively engage in educational activities and may not provide their opinions during group discussions, which could lead to them being overlooked. Studies in the past have found that there is a high prevalence of Impostor syndrome among doctors. However there is scarcity of data about the phenomenon of Impostor syndrome among medical students in India.

Aim: To estimate the prevalence of Impostor Syndrome among Undergraduate and Postgraduate Medical Students of Patna.

Methodology: This study employed a cross-sectional study design, focusing on undergraduate and postgraduate medical students in the various medical colleges in Patna over a 12-month period. Sample size for the study was calculated based on the prevalence of impostor syndrome among medical interns, as determined by Mascarenhas VR et al, established as 86%, with a precision of 5% and a 95% confidence interval. Considering a 10% non-response rate, the determined sample size was 280, selected through simple random sampling. Data collection utilized a standardized and validated questionnaire, the Clance Impostor Phenomenon questionnaire. Ethical clearance from the Institutional Ethical Committee was secured prior to study commencement.

Results: 61.07 % were male (n = 171) and 38.93% were female (n = 109). 51.07% (n = 143) were PG students whereas 48.93% (n = 137) were UG students. Mean Clance score of the

participants was 42.70 +/- 15.866. 52.1% (n = 154) has Few Impostor Characteristics, 37.9% (n=74) have Moderate IP experiences, 6.8% (38) have frequently experiences Impostor feelings and 3.2% (n = 14) often has intense IP experiences.

Conclusion: This study reveals a notable prevalence of Impostor Syndrome among medical students in Patna, with a significant proportion experiencing moderate to frequent impostor feelings. Addressing and mitigating these psychological challenges is crucial for fostering a supportive learning environment in medical education.

OP-131

Jack Stone Calculi in the Urinary Bladder: A Rare Case Report

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Abstract:

Background: Urolithiasis constitutes a major health problem with an estimated prevalence between 1 and 20% globally. They are classified into three distinct groups: Migratory, primary and secondary. They can be either single or multiple and usually vary in size, shape, and colour. The pathogenesis is considered multifactorial, with bladder outlet obstruction secondary to benign prostate hyperplasia being a plausible mechanism for stone formation in the vast majority of cases

Objective: This case report details a rare occurrence of "Jack" stone calculi in the urinary bladder, presenting with obstructive lower urinary tract symptoms.

Methods: A 55-year-old male presented with lower urinary tract symptoms, including burning micturition, abdominal pain, and hematuria. Diagnostic imaging revealed irregular thickening of the bladder wall with a large, irregularly shaped stone in the pelvic region. Hematological and biochemistry investigations showed no abnormalities. The patient opted for open cystolithotomy for stone removal.

Results: The surgery successfully removed a single 32x30x28mm Jackstone calculus. The patient experienced no immediate complications and was discharged on the 8th postoperative day. Complete stone removal was confirmed on the 12th postoperative day with a catheter in place for 14 days postoperatively.

Conclusion: This case emphasizes the importance of considering uncommon stone types in the differential diagnosis of bladder stones. Surgical intervention, such as cystolithotomy, can effectively manage these cases, leading to a successful outcome with minimal complications. Understanding the clinical significance of Jack stones is essential due to potential complications, including chronic irritation, inflammation, and the risk for malignancy associated with their distinct morphological features.

OP-132

EFFECT OF IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA ON HbA1c (GLYCOSYLATED HEMOGLOBIN) IN FEMALES WITH CONTROLLED DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract: One of the most prevalent illnesses in the world, diabetes mellitus (DM) has a high morbidity and death rate and one of the most crucial tools for illness detection and tracking is HbA1c. Factors influencing hemoglobin and the half-life of red blood cells can alter HbA1c results since HbA1c is a reflection of the glucose linked to red blood cells. After applying inclusion and exclusion criteria, 50 anemic Females with controlled DM (group A), 50 Non anemic females with controlled DM (group B), 100 non diabetic females, 50 non anemic (group C) and 50 anemic are selected (group D). Their Hb% and HbA1c are noted and analyzed. Mean Hb% in Non anemic females was 13.3 ± 1.1 and in subjects with iron deficiency anemia was 10.84 ± 0.82 and Mean HbA1c values in non-anemic females was 5.67 ± 0.24 while ones with Iron deficiency anemia was 5.82 ± 0.18 . The HbA1c difference is statistically significant with p value of <0.01 Mean Hb% in Non DM Non anemic females was 13.86 ± 0.94 and in subjects with iron deficiency anemia was 10.54 ± 1 and Mean HbA1c values in non anemic females was 5.4 ± 0.12 while ones WITH Iron deficiency anemia was 5.82 ± 0.18 . The HbA1c difference is statistically significant with p value of <0.01 . Anemia can have an impact on the blood's HbA1c levels. Due to red blood cells' longer half-lives. Illnesses like Iron Deficiency Anemia that are linked to reduced erythropoiesis can generally induce an incorrect increase in HbA1c.

Keywords: anemia, females, HbA1c, diabetes mellitus.

OP-133

Social Television and the Dynamics of Gender Representation through it: A case study on the Netflix Original Series, YOU

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Abstract: The present study delves into intricate interplay of gender representation in the popular Netflix series ‘You’ and its reception on Social Television. The research analyses the way male and female leads are being portrayed in the series and subsequent discourses that take place on social media further leading to gender construction. The series presents protagonist Joe as a next-door male character who murders women in lieu of love and female characters as femme fatale. With such representation of gender roles in the series, it became imperative to find out underlying meanings and the reasons behind such indoctrination of gender. The study used ‘You’ as a case study and used qualitative discourse analysis for analysing its audio-visual text and social media interactions. The findings reveal that the story has been problematically represented as a cautionary feminist tale perpetuating harmful stereotypes, normalizing abusive tendencies, providing approval to toxic masculinity and violence. The analysis show that subsequent social media discourses further provide a powerful approval to male dominance and glorifies their violent behaviours. Based on the evidence and analysis of data, the study concluded that the insidious representation of gender in the series is nothing but another reflection of the deep-rooted patriarchal mindset in society and the attempts like ‘You’ play a regressive role in creating balance and just society. The study suggests media content creators and platforms to take on a more responsible approach to storytelling and representing gender norms. As media plays a crucial role in shaping public opinion, its power should be used in rejecting harmful stereotypes and patriarchal mindset and not vice-versa.

Keywords: Social Television, Gender Construction, Cautionary Feminist Tale, Patriarchy

OP-134

Effect of Physiotherapy Intervention on Pain and Quality of Life in Cervical Radiculopathy- A Pilot Study

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Abstract

Background: Cervical radiculopathy (CR) is a clinical condition frequently encountered now a days. Cervical radiculopathy is a result of space occupying lesions in the cervical spine: either cervical disc herniations, spondylosis, or osteophytosis. These affect the pain generators of bony and ligamentous tissues, producing radicular symptoms (i.e., pain, numbness, weakness, paraesthesia) observed in the upper extremity of patients with cervical nerve root pathology. Recruitment of patients will be done according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Baseline records will be obtained before beginning of protocol. Treatment will be done according to the set protocol. Post treatment records will be measured and comparison of both the recording will be done to obtain the result. The aim of the study is to determine the effect of Physiotherapy intervention on pain and quality of life in patients with cervical radiculopathy. For data analysis Parametric Test will be used.

Keywords: Cervical Radiculopathy, Cervical spine, Paraesthesia, Physiotherapy intervention, Upper extremity

OP-135

**A STUDY TO FIND THE USAGE OF SALIVARY CREATININE AS AN
ALTERNATIVE TO SERUM CREATININE IN ESTIMATING RENAL FUNCTION
IN HEALTHY INDIVIDUALS**

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Abstract: Blood sampling is an invasive procedure and requires skill. In patients or individuals who require multiple time creatinine monitoring, venous sampling procedure causes discomfort. To save time, blood and the patients from difficulty, salivary creatinine estimation will help a lot in this aspect. This study aimed to find the correlation between serum and salivary creatinine was conducted on 50 individuals. After selecting them from, study based on criteria. The serum and saliva collected from individuals in the morning between 7 and 9 AM and sent for creatinine estimation. The study shows that there is no correlation between Serum and salivary creatinine with Pearson coefficient “r” = 0.074 and p value of 0.63 (>0.05). Serum creatinine is the standard measurement of renal function and salivary creatinine cannot be used as an alternative.

Keywords: Serum, saliva, creatinine, Alternative, Healthy individuals, Renal function.

OP-136

A Study of Instagram Promotions of the Film 'Gangubai Kathiawadi' and Their Significance in Influencing Audience Perceptions

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Abstract: In the dynamic landscape of the evolving film industry, the role of social media platforms has become indispensable in shaping audience perceptions and driving box office success. Among these platforms, Instagram has emerged as a potent force in the domain of film marketing, offering filmmakers an unparalleled avenue for direct engagement with their audience. This study delves into the realm of film marketing, with a specific focus on the strategic utilisation of Instagram promotions for the film "Gangubai Kathiawadi" and their quantifiable impact on the audience. A meticulous analysis of the promotional content disseminated through Instagram is undertaken, emphasising its influence on audience engagement. Employing a quantitative research methodology, the study utilises audience surveys as instruments to gauge the effectiveness of Instagram promotions in fostering awareness, engagement, and overall audience response.

The study's findings indicate that Instagram promotions play a pivotal role in cultivating awareness about the movie, while influencer-generated promotional content exerts a limited influence that does not significantly correlate with subsequent movie attendance. This comprehensive quantitative survey, paired with a meticulous data analysis, significantly advances our comprehension of the dynamic interplay between film marketing strategies and audience reception within the contemporary digital landscape. Notably, the discerning insights obtained from the study posit that influencer-generated promotional content, while undoubtedly valuable in generating anticipatory excitement surrounding cinematic releases, exhibits a rather limited efficacy in translating such enthusiasm into tangible audience attendance. The findings underscore the paradoxical nature of influencer impact, wherein their ability to engender pre-release fervour contrasts with a comparatively diminished influence when it comes to motivating audiences to actively partake in the cinematic experience.

Keywords: Instagram Promotions, Influencer Collaborations, Movie Promotions, Consumer Behavior, Social Media Engagement, Gangubai Kathiawadi, Bollywood

OP-137

Extraction and Formulation of Perfumes from Essential Oils

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Abstract: Perfumes is the concoction of fragrant essential oils or aroma compounds, fixatives and solvents that is used to give the human body, food objectives, animals & living spaces an affable scent. Fragrance is a prominent measure of cosmeceuticals products being look regarded as an overriding factor in the selection of cosmetics among consumers, fragrances are given significant importance. They also play a crucial role in masking undesirable smells that arise from the fatty acids, oils, and surfactants that are commonly utilized in the formulation of cosmetics. Essential oils are the key assets in the cosmetic industry, as along with development of pleasant aromas in different products, they also contributes as a source of preservatives and active agent simultaneously that offer various benefits to the skin. Moreover, the rising demand for natural ingredients has significantly sparked a renewed interest in the use of plant derivatives in cosmetic and wellness industries, particularly essential oils. This change towards natural products has provoked popular cosmetic companies to promote natural fragrances and choose less processed natural ingredients over artificial ones. This choice is largely due to the potential health risk factors associated with artificial fragrance chemicals, which are commonly used in many cosmetics. Essential oils like citrus, lavender, eucalyptus, tea tree, and other floral oils are highly appreciated for their fragrant properties. Furthermore, fragrance components such as linalool, geraniol, limonene, citronellol, citral are well-loved and widely used in a variety of cosmetics. Extraction is the separation of Aromatically active portions of plant tissues using selective solvents. The general techniques of Aromatic plant extraction include, supercritical Co₂ fluid extraction, steam distillation, enfleurage and many other, may be employed.

OP-138

ANTIARTHRITIC ACTIVITY OF HERBAL PLANTS

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Abstract: Arthritis a serious and chronic inflammatory condition that can affect joints, and other body parts. Genetic, hormonal, environmental and smoking, infactions are some risk factor of arthritis. The treatment which are available including steroidal and non-steroidal allopathic therapies cannot cure or prevent the disease and having several side effect. These treatments can only provide temporary relief by suppressing and reducing the pain in the join. Traditional medicines are prevalent in the treatment of arthritis due to severe side effect of allopathic medicine in many countries. So nowadays researcher shows a great interest in those medicinal agents that are derived from plants because the currently available drugs are either have sertant side effect or are highly expensive. Nature has bleassed a with widly wealth of herbal plants. There are many plants which have good antiarthritic properties. like *Curcuma longa* (Turmeric), *Withania somnifera* (Ashwagandha), *Allium sativum* (Garlic) *Grewia asiatica* (phalsha), *Cyperus rotandus* (Nagarmotha) etc. available throughout the world which are having good antiarthritic prospective. Several native medical system in india make large scale use of medicinal herbs to treat and prevent arthritis. The work has carried out by through searching of defferent online journals. We also have collected the validated plants which are having antiarthritic property. Such as *Curcuma longa*- It is belong to the family Zingiberaceae. It is a potential antiarthritic agent. The main active constituent of the plant is curcumin. It has several pharmacological activities such as anti-diabetic, hypolipidemic, anti-inflammatory, etc. several research studies are reported on the antiarthritic effect of curcumin. And next plant is *Withania somnifera* –It is belong to family solanaceae. Withanolides are its main active chemical constituents. It si also alkaloids, Saponins, phenolic compounds and flavonoids etc. its used to nerve tonic, antidiabetic, memory enhancer, etc. Different studies are done to determine the anti-arthritis activity of this plant. In India there are several herbs in different forms are used in the traditional systems of medicine. Presently investigation of the antiarthritic activity of the herbs leads to the development of many effective herbal therapies for such purpose. For the discovery of potential antiarthritic compounds the suitable informations about the medicinal plants are needed.

OP-139

Ethical Challenges in the application of Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare

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Background: The demand for healthcare services is ever increasing and many countries are experiencing a shortage of healthcare practitioners, especially physicians. The advances in wireless technology and smartphones have provided opportunities for on-demand healthcare services using health tracking apps and search platforms. There is great optimism that the application of artificial intelligence (AI) can provide substantial improvements in all areas of healthcare from diagnostics to treatment. As these technologies become increasingly intertwined with patient care and well-being. The interventions in any form must ensure the safety and ethical issues besides their scientific application values. Ethical issues need to be addressed in depth to avoid any catastrophic results in near future. It is crucial to navigate these challenges effectively.

Aim and objective: To discuss the ethical challenges in the application of AI in holistic healthcare such as privacy, bias, transparency, and accountability.

Methodology: To get some conclusion and suggestion extensive literature search was conducted using different indexing systems. Then the required data were segregated and compiled.

Results: As per the information present currently, patients need to be adequately informed about AI's role in their care, and measures to ensure patient autonomy are paramount.

Conclusion: Even though AI technologies are receiving a lot of attention in medical science, real-world implementations are still facing challenges. The greatest challenge to AI in these healthcare domains is not whether the technologies will be capable enough to be useful, but rather ensuring their adoption in daily clinical practice. As the field of AI in healthcare continues to evolve, ethical considerations should remain at the forefront of decision-making processes.

The future of AI in healthcare: For widespread adoption to take place, AI systems must be approved by regulators, integrated with EHR systems, standardised to a sufficient degree that similar products work in a similar fashion, taught to clinicians, paid for by public or private

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payer organisations and updated over time in the field. It also seems increasingly clear that AI systems will not replace human clinicians on a large scale, but rather will augment their efforts to care for patients. Perhaps the only healthcare providers who will lose their jobs over time may be those who refuse to work alongside artificial intelligence.

OP-140

The Jedi Master

Exploring alternative forms of producing and presenting non-fiction content

Abstract: This research delves into the escalating apprehensions regarding content creation ethics on the social media platform Instagram. The study aims to comprehend the imperative for non-fiction narratives serving as a public sphere of influence. It endeavours to scrutinize innovative methods of crafting visual content capable of mitigating issues such as content overload, biased information dissemination, and media fatigue. To achieve this, the research advocates for a hybrid system that amalgamates traditional and digital mediums. Digital platforms are endorsed for their extensive reach, while traditional mediums, particularly live events, are recommended for fostering a more personalized and authentic experience. The objective is to strike a balance that leverages the vast outreach of digital platforms while concurrently harnessing the authenticity and personalization inherent in traditional mediums. By exploring this hybrid model, the study aspires to contribute novel insights into the realm of content creation, paving the way for a more ethical and effective approach to address contemporary challenges in the digital landscape.

OP-141

Examining Consumer Behavior and brand Perception in Quick-Commerce Applications

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Abstract: Propelled by significant growth in the E-Commerce space, increasing digital penetration and the pandemic restrictions, Quick Commerce applications such as Instamart, BlinkIt and Zepto emerged into the marketplace at a time when Quick-Commerce emerged as a industry showing significant growth in India. This rise in usage has been accompanied by a variety of marketing strategies dedicated to reaching a wider audience. Tapping into the online domain with witty advertisements and trending topics, these applications utilise 360-degree marketing strategies which have several implications on consumer's behaviour, their interactions with the brands and in-turn their perceptions of the same. These advertisements target the consumer on various stages of the AIDA model. Employing a survey questionnaire and a Focus-Group Discussion, the study focussed on understanding the consumer's perception of these brands based on their advertising as well as their behaviour towards these advertisements. The study found out that consumers in Bangalore in the age bracket of 18-25 react positively to digital advertisements of quick commerce applications and believe that they have led to significant awareness and purchasing from the ends of the consumers. The respondents also believed that they stand in favour of these Quick Commerce portals and hold the opinion that they can replace traditional brick-and-mortar shops.

Keywords: Quick Commerce, Grocery Stores, Brand, Consumer Awareness, Consumer Behaviour.

OP-142
DENTISTRY IN METAVERSE

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Abstract: Modern advancements in dentistry have provided great ease in the dental practice. Dentophobia is a major concern especially during the time of invasive dental procedures. Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) have proven beneficial in changing the patient's experience as well as in providing a thorough exposure of the clinical application of dentistry to the dental professionals hence improving their skills and quality of education. VR and AR have set their foot in almost every single branch of dentistry, ranging from maxillofacial surgery, implantology, endodontics to pediatric dentistry. AR and VR are the perfect example of amalgamation of the virtual world and the real world. There are three types of VR systems- immersive, semi-immersive and non-immersive. With the AR system a surgeon is able to map the entire surgery along with the necessary modifications to be incorporated during the procedure to increase its efficacy. VR and AR systems are the modern non pharmacological methods used in the behaviour management in pediatric dentistry with significant positive results. These systems are also used in detecting the pulp canals which increases the quality of an RCT. The use of AR and VR has improved the diagnosis leading to the formulation of an effective and upgraded treatment plan. However certain disadvantages like visual fatigue, expenditure and equipment failure cannot be overlooked while utilising these revolutionised systems.

Keywords: Virtual reality, Augmented reality, immersive, semi-immersive, non-immersive, visual fatigue, expenditure, equipment failure

OP-143

Essential oils used as probiotics and postbiotic

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Abstract: Essential oils and probiotics both are high likely in properties of their antimicrobial activity against antibiotic opposing enteric pathogens. Postbiotic are widely known for their beneficial effect on various animals and humans. Probiotics, as enteric microorganisms, do not exert any parasitic effect on human beings. People have included them as an integral part of daily food for centuries. Studies show that they possess health beneficiary properties. Probiotics retard the growth of microorganisms, while essential oil kills them. A new approach may involve combining the effects of essential oils extract and probiotics due to their complementary antimicrobial effects and almost no side effects. The essential oil and probiotics' symbiotic effect will necessarily be higher than using them alone as a health product. The text discusses the actual definitions of probiotics microorganisms, probiotics, and postbiotic compounds and functional food. The giving considers the relations between selected food components and their effect on probiotics, as well as their effect on some health problems in humans and new possibilities for using probiotics bacteria in the food industry. Probiotics basically refer to consumable cultured food and drinks they also contain good bacteria. These bacteria feed on probiotics, which are food materials. Postbiotic are those products which are healthy byproduct naturally produced by probiotics. These groups of bacteria are necessary to human body. The human gut also a complex ecosystem, contain billions of microorganisms, primarily colonize the large intestine. So that we can show some impotence and a brief introduction about the essential oils used as probiotics and postbiotic and the difference between the probiotics and postbiotic. In the discussion of the topic basically highlighted the effect of importunes of probiotics and postbiotic

OP-144

**EVALUATION OF GLASGOW (IMRIE) SCORE, CRP AND BALTHAZAR SCORE
IN PREDICTING SEVERITY OF ACUTE PANCREATITIS**

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Abstract: Acute pancreatitis (AP) is an acute inflammatory disease and is one of the most frequent gastrointestinal causes of hospital admission. The early assessment of disease severity to estimate the complications and even organ failure is fundamental: approximately 23% of the deaths attributable to AP occur in the first 3 days, and 53% within the first week [1]. Early identification of patients at increased risk of severe and fatal AP is crucial to improve prognosis.[1] Several prognostic scoring systems have been used to predict severity and mortality in AP, including Ranson score, Glasgow score, Balthazar score and the acute physiology and chronic health evaluation (APACHE II).[2]. In addition to clinical scoring systems, numerous individual biomarkers have been proposed as having a predictive value in acute pancreatitis: C-reactive protein (CRP), blood urea nitrogen, haematocrit and interleukins 6 and 8.[3] This study was carried out to compare the efficacy of Glasgow (Imrie)score, C-Reactive Protein and Balthazar score in predicting severity of Acute Pancreatitis based on Revised Atlanta classification (RAC).

OP-145

TRENDS IN VIEWER PERCEPTION OF REMAKE CONTENT IN BOLLYWOOD MOVIES

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Abstract: The dissertation "Trends in Viewer Perception of Remake Content in Bollywood Movies" is a comprehensive study that explores the evolving trends in viewer perception of remakes in the Bollywood film industry. Today, Bollywood is the biggest worldwide film industry, with a film production size of approximately 27000 films. Lately, it has not been a very pleasing time for Bollywood as it is on a spree of producing movies and content that have either been acquired through rights or inspired by, remakes of popular hits from other parts of the Indian Cinema. The present study comprehensively analyzes the complex interplay between filmmakers and audiences in the context of remake content in Bollywood movies since the study analyzes audience responses and experts' views regarding a movie's performance and critical reception of remake content. The research objectives aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors that influence viewer perception of remakes in Bollywood movies. These objectives include identifying the factors behind the success or failure of movies, exploring the role of OTT release, understanding the impact of stardom, and examining the role of cultural perspective in the reception of remakes. The methodology used for this study was a Mixed Method and the data analysis was conducted through thematic analysis. The results of the study indicate that Bollywood remakes are not the most prominent viewed or chosen. Instead, the audience aligns and resonates more with the original or new content present in the market. The study acquired important implications and raised questions for the Bollywood film industry. Suggestions included considerations that the remake content makers should give to the choice of source material for remakes and their execution.

Keywords: Hindi Cinema, Bollywood, Bollywood Movies, Bollywood Remakes, OTT, Stardom.

OP-146

Understanding the relationship between severity of Type-II Diabetes Mellitus and High Blood Pressure in IPD patients.

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Abstract: Type - II Diabetes Mellitus and High Blood Pressure overlap in the population. In many subjects development of type - II Diabetes Mellitus is characterized by the relatively rapid increase in blood glucose levels whether a similar phenomenon occurs during the development of hypertension is not known. Diabetes Mellitus and Hypertension are among the most common diseases and Cardiovascular risk factors and their frequency increases with increasing age. Elevated blood pressure values are a common finding in patients with type -II Diabetes Mellitus. The development of hypertension in diabetic individuals not only complicates treatment strategy and increase the risk for micro vascular and macro vascular complications. Overall result we found are:

1. Development of hypertension and Diabetes Mellitus tract each other over the period of time.
2. Transition of Normotension to Hypertension is characterized by sharp increase in BP values.

OP-147

**EFFECTS OF SELECTED CARBONATED BEVERAGE ON CULTIVATED
MICROORGANISMS FROM PUBLIC TOILET**

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Abstract: This study was conducted by cultivating microbes from a public toilet in a nutrient agar plate as the primary culture. The antimicrobial effect was determined by disk plate method, a common laboratory procedure. In our research work, Minimum Inhibitory Concentration was determined by using different media ratios and the selected beverage-Coke on uniform amounts of microbial inoculum. At the end of the study, it was found that even though coke is used to clean the toilet according to the latest social media information like Instagram, it does not act as an antimicrobial agent as no zone of inhibition was seen around the colonies but on the contrary, a much heavier growth was observed in areas around coke-infused disks due to high sugar content acting as a source of nutrient for the growth of microorganisms.

Keywords: Carbonated beverage-coke, Instagram, antimicrobial effect, Minimum Inhibitory Concentration, disk plate method.

OP-148

Exploratory and social inquiry into the phenomenon of beauty pageants in India

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Abstract: A thorough examination of beauty pageants from 2013 to 2020 with a particular emphasis on Femina Miss India and Miss Diva. The researcher examines the complex nature of these contests, focusing on winners, their performances in international pageants, and functionality. The research utilises a comparative methodology, exploring the historical backgrounds, organisational frameworks, and overarching ideologies of Femina Miss India and Miss Diva with the goal of identifying unique patterns and trends. The study assesses the standards by which participants were judged by a thorough analysis of secondary data, providing insights into the standards of success and attractiveness that are prevalent in society. The trajectories of the winners are followed, shedding light on how these competitions affect individuals' personal and professional paths, both within and outside of the pageant domains.

Keywords: Beauty Pageants, Miss, Miss Universe, Miss World, Femina, Pageant.

OP-149

Ethical Challenges of Artificial Intelligence technology in Palliative care

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Background: Artificial Intelligence (AI) is an area of computer science which involves the development of intelligent machines that work and react like humans. AI has potential to improve healthcare delivery through purposeful analysis of clinical record data. Examples of AI use in palliative care includes the analysis of electronic patient record data to predict survival, classify pain severity and to identify important clinical discussions. Despite the opportunities of AI, there are a number of ethical challenges of using this technology in palliative care. Consequently, this study aimed to identify the ethical challenges of AI in palliative care.

Methods: A narrative scoping review of literature was undertaken to identify the evidence of AI use in palliative care. Three real-world case studies using AI in palliative care were critiqued in depth, using the four ethical principle framework (*Autonomy, Justice, Beneficence, Non-maleficence*). Ethical challenges were identified and summarised into themes.

Results: Very few studies have examined the use of AI in palliative care; no studies discuss the ethical challenges as the primary focus. Ethical challenges for AI in palliative care were summarised into four themes: (1) Data privacy and security; (2) Artificial stupidity; (3) Prognostication; (4) Unexpected results and bias.

Conclusion: AI has potential to support delivery in palliative care; however, a number of important ethical challenges need to be considered. AI healthcare data analysis should be built around an ethical framework. This is important in palliative care as individuals may be more vulnerable compared to other specialities. Research to determine the views and opinions of a patients, caregivers and healthcare professionals is urgently needed. Our work has led to the development of recommendations for ethical AI research in palliative care, which will hopefully guide meaningful use of this technology.

OP-150

Studying the Unconventional Marketing Strategies of Fintech Giant (CRED) –

Ayush Bhattacharya and Dr. Suparna Naresh

Abstract: The fintech industry has witnessed a revolution in marketing strategies, with brands adopting innovative approaches to capture the attention of their audiences. One standout player in this landscape is CRED, a credit card payment platform known for its unconventional marketing techniques. This paper aims to delve deep into the unconventional marketing strategies of CRED, observing its departure from traditional financial services advertising. The primary objective of this study was to explore and understand CRED's unorthodox marketing strategies. By analysing the brand's approach to marketing, the researcher sought to identify what sets CRED apart within the fintech landscape. Adopting a qualitative research methodology, this study utilizes two core methods: case studies and expert interviews. The case studies provide a comprehensive analysis of specific CRED campaigns, examining their effectiveness and impact. Conversely, the expert interviews delve into the theoretical frameworks and practical implications underpinning these marketing strategies. The culmination of these methods yields comprehensive insights into CRED's innovative marketing tactics.

The results of this research illustrate that CRED's marketing approach is genuinely innovative. The case studies reveal the distinctiveness of the brand's campaigns, emphasizing the use of humour, creativity, and an extraordinary communication style. The findings from expert interviews highlight the strategic importance of storytelling, emotional engagement, and the brand's ability to appeal to diverse audiences. These results underscore CRED's innovative marketing approach and its successful deviation from conventional financial services advertising norms. In conclusion, this research demonstrates that CRED's unconventional marketing strategies are pioneering in the fintech landscape.

OP-151

Representation of Therapy and Therapists in Indian Movies and TV Series: An Examination of Accuracy, Influence, and Perception

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Abstract: Film and Psychology have maintained a long-standing relationship, with depictions of therapy and therapists evolving over time. Despite extensive research on mental health portrayals in Hollywood, a void remains in understanding how therapists are depicted in Indian Movies and TV Series. This study aims to bridge this gap by exploring the portrayal of therapists in Indian Movies and TV Series and its influence on audiences, accuracy, and real-life therapists' experiences. Employing a Qualitative methodology, in-depth interviews were conducted with experts following a preliminary Delphi method pilot study. Findings revealed oversimplified representations of mental health in Bollywood Films and TV Series, while Regional films and TV Series showcased more authentic depictions. Experts emphasized the necessity for responsible and accurate contextualization, particularly in extreme treatment scenes. Media portrayals present challenges for therapists in dispelling preconceived notions during sessions, highlighting the need for precise and empathetic representations in Indian Movies and TV Series.

Keywords: Therapy, Therapists, Films, TV Series, Psychology, Bollywood, Regional

OP-152

Indian Cinema and Political Propaganda: The interplay of Ideologies, Politics, and People's Perception.

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Abstract: The aim of this study is to explore and analyze the correlation between Indian Cinema, Propaganda, and Politics, taking 3 major factors into account which are, Bollywood, Philosophical Propaganda, and People's Perceptions towards it. It argues the depiction of nationalism, patriotism, the idea of nation and how all these ideologies are propagate through a crucial tool, films. It also analyses how the increased misrepresentation of religious communities has led to the strengthening of the feeling of "otherization" among communities and how the growing tension among cultures and communities is being used to gain political power. Lastly, the study makes an attempt to analyse what makes the audience resonate with such movies. A triangulation approach was undertaken using content analysis and the survey method to understand the nuances of propaganda through films. Using content analysis, the study observed 2 movies URI: The Surgical Strike, and The Kashmir Files, to delve deep into the concepts of nationalism, the idea of nation, cultural representation. A quantitative approach was taken wherein a survey was conducted to understand the audience's perception of such movies, if it affects their voting decisions, and lastly, if it influences them and in any way shapes their ideologies.

Keywords: Bollywood, Nationalism, Propaganda, Right-Wing, Ideologies, Politics, Jingoism, Hindi Cinema, Agenda, Kashmir.

OP-153

Creator Economy goes Decentralised: An Examination of the opportunities & challenges of Web 3.0 for Content Producers

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Abstract: This study undertakes an in-depth examination of the implications surrounding the transition of the Creator Economy into the decentralized framework of Web 3.0. The primary focus is exploring both the opportunities and challenges content producers encounter amid this transformation. The current study is qualitative and exploratory as the aim was to investigate the issue in detail and develop a comprehensive understanding of the Creative Economy in the Web 3.0 era. Therefore, in-depth interviews with content creators were conducted to collect data. These interviews involved comprehensive engagements with content creators and platform stakeholders, seeking to elucidate nuanced perspectives that influence the trajectory of the Creator Economy within the Web 3.0 paradigm. The data analysis for exploring the emerging patterns was done using Thematic Analysis. Based on the data collected and analysis, preliminary findings bring forth central themes, including transparency issues and a discernible comprehension gap among creators, thereby underscoring the essential requirement for lucid communication from platform stakeholders. The findings depict content creators' nuanced optimism and caution about Web 3.0, emphasizing transparency, while platform stakeholders express commitment to decentralization. I conclude that there is a need for improved communication and strategic initiatives to address challenges and capitalize on opportunities in the evolving digital landscape. This study sets the groundwork for future research, encouraging deeper exploration of Creator Economy dynamics in Web 3.0, including investigations into transparency issues, comprehension gaps, comparative analyses across sectors, and longitudinal studies for evolving insights over time.

Keywords: Web 3.0, Creator Economy, Decentralisation, Platform Stakeholder, Content Creation, Technological Shift

OP-154

Understanding the relationship between severity of Type-II Diabetes Mellitus and High Blood Pressure in IPD patients.

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Abstract: Type - II Diabetes Mellitus and High Blood Pressure overlap in the population. In many subjects development of type - II Diabetes Mellitus is characterized by the relatively rapid increase in blood glucose levels whether a similar phenomenon occurs during the development of hypertension is not known. Diabetes Mellitus and Hypertension are among the most common diseases and Cardiovascular risk factors and their frequency increases with increasing age. Elevated blood pressure values are a common finding in patients with type -II Diabetes Mellitus. The development of hypertension in diabetic individuals not only complicates treatment strategy and increase the risk for micro vascular and macro vascular complications. Overall result we found are:

1. Development of hypertension and Diabetes Mellitus tract each other over the period of time.
2. Transition of Normotension to Hypertension is characterized by sharp increase in BP values.

OP-155

**RULER DROP REACTION: A STUDY OF REACTION TIME AND ITS
RELATIONSHIP TO DISTANCE IN YOUNG ADULTS**

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Background: Reaction time (RT) refers to the duration between a stimulus and the subsequent response. One way to measure RT is through the ruler drop method (RDM). Reaction time is one of the important methods to study a person's central information processing speed and coordinated peripheral movement response.

Objective: To assess the reaction time and its relationship to distance in young adults.

Methodology: We included 40 samples in our study. Participants with the age criteria of 18 to 25 years included.

Results: The Pearson correlation coefficient between distance and reaction time was -0.224, which indicates a weak negative correlation. However, this correlation was not statistically significant (pvalue = 0.88), meaning that there is not enough evidence to conclude that there is a true relationship between distance and reaction time in the population.

Conclusion: The analysis revealed a weak negative correlation between distance and reaction time. However, the obtained correlation was not statistically significant (p-value = 0.88), indicating insufficient evidence to support the existence of a true relationship between these variables in the broader population. This suggests that, based on the current data and analysis, distance does not appear to have a substantial impact on reaction time. Further investigation or a larger sample size might be necessary to draw more conclusive insights regarding any potential connection between distance and reaction time.

Keywords: Reaction time, Young adults, Health.

OP-156

On Estimation of Multicomponent Stress-Strength Reliability for Exponentiated Gumbel Distribution When All the Parameters Are Different

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Abstract: In this paper, we consider multicomponent system reliability where the system has k components with independent and identical strengths and each component is experiencing a random stress. The reliability of such a system is derived when both stress and strength variables follow exponentiated Gumbel Distribution and also with the assumption that all parameters are different. The maximum likelihood and Bayes estimators are obtained and the later are derived using MCMC method. Simulation studies are also done to find the performance of the estimators developed in this paper.

OP-157

“Comparative assessment of Lipoarabinomannan antigen and anti-lipoarabinomannan antibody profile for the serological diagnosis of active tuberculosis: Insight into a case-control study”

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Abstract: Tuberculosis (TB) is a major global health problem caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and it is one of the top 10 causes of death worldwide. Globally 10.6 million individuals have been infected with TB in 2022 according to WHO 2023 report. Diagnosis of TB is very challenging, available tests like acid-fast bacilli (AFB) microscopy, cultures, and X-ray presents severe limitations including lack of sensitivity so there is a need to develop new biomarker-based tests to detect TB. This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of lipoarabinomannan (LAM) antigen and anti-LAM antibodies as diagnostic markers for the diagnosis of active TB. This serological study was conducted on the two groups including TB patients and healthy controls to detect LAM antigen and anti-LAM antibodies. After obtaining consent blood samples were collected from all the study participants. Serum samples were screened for the presence of LAM antigen by developed sandwich ELISA using monoclonal ML34 antibodies and these serum samples were also tested simultaneously for the presence of anti-LAM antibodies by competition-inhibition ELISA method. The evaluation of diagnostic specificity was calculated based on the mean +2 standard deviations of the healthy control optical density. Statistical analysis was performed. The result of our study revealed that LAM antigen and anti-LAM antibodies were found significantly higher in the active TB patients ($p < 0.0001$) compared to healthy controls. The sensitivity and specificity of LAM antigen and anti-LAM antibodies were 88.50%, 100% and 90.5%, 98.5% respectively. Serological study based on LAM antigen and anti-LAM antibodies detection using ELISA has demonstrated outstanding clinical diagnostic value for active TB.

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Keywords: lipoarabinomannan, tuberculosis, antigen, anti-lipoarabinomannan, diagnosis, marker, ELISA, serum.

OP-158
**PUBLIC PERCEPTIONS AND POLITICAL PERSPECTIVES ON SOCIAL
SECURITY REFORM**

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Abstract: In contemporary societies, the concept of social security stands as a fundamental pillar of the social contract, promising citizens a safety net in times of economic hardship and retirement. As demographic shifts, fiscal challenges, and evolving economic landscapes continuously reshape the terrain of social security, it becomes increasingly imperative to scrutinize the public's perceptions and the political perspectives that underpin decisions regarding reform. This research paper embarks on a journey to unravel the intricate tapestry of attitudes, beliefs, and policy orientations that surround the subject of social security reform.

There has been a major expansion of social security programmes in India during the last fifteen years or so, along with wider recognition of economic and social rights. This paper discusses five programmes that can be seen as partial foundations of a possible social security system for India: school meals, childcare services, employment guarantee, food subsidies and social security pensions. The record of these programmes varies a great deal between Indian states, but there is growing evidence that they make an important contribution to human well-being, and also that the achievements of the leading states are gradually spreading to other states as well. Much scope remains for extending these efforts: despite the recent expansion, India's social security system is still very limited in international perspective. The paper also discusses some general issues of social policy in India, such as the arguments for universalization versus targeting and the value of a rights approach to social security.

Keywords: Social Security, Public, Political, Economy, Policy

OP-159

Effect of 20-min yoga module on mental health outcomes of healthcare workers: a pilot randomized controlled trial

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Abstract

Introduction: The demanding nature of healthcare professions often leads to high levels of stress and burnout among healthcare workers. This pilot randomized controlled trial aimed to investigate the potential benefits of a brief 20-minute yoga module on the mental health outcomes of healthcare workers.

Methods: A total of 20 healthcare workers from a tertiary care hospital were randomly assigned to either the intervention group or the control group. The intervention group participated in a structured 20-minute yoga session five times a week for a duration of four weeks, while the control group performed 20-min medium pace walking. Mental health outcomes such as mindfulness, trait anxiety, professional quality of life and happiness were assessed using mindful attention awareness scale (MAAS), state trait anxiety inventory (STAI), professional quality of life scale (PROQOL) and self-rated happiness scale respectively. Outcome assessments were performed at the baseline and subsequent to the four-week intervention period.

Results: Out of a total of 20 participants, 17 successfully completed the intervention, with 9 in the yoga group and 8 in the control group. Paired t test demonstrated a statistically significant improvement in mindfulness ($p = 0.02$), trait anxiety ($p = 0.001$) and happiness scale ($p = 0.04$) in yoga group. Conversely, the control group showed no significant differences in the domains of mindfulness ($p = 0.08$), trait anxiety ($p = 0.07$) and happiness ($p = 0.24$).

Conclusion: This pilot randomized controlled trial suggests that a brief 20-minute yoga module may be an effective and feasible intervention for improving the mental health outcomes of healthcare workers. Further research with a larger sample size and long-term follow-up is warranted to confirm and extend these findings. Implementing such cost-effective and

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accessible interventions could contribute to the overall well-being and resilience of healthcare professionals facing the challenges of their demanding work environments.

Keywords: Yoga, mental health, healthcare workers

OP-160

Intelligent Traffic System - Review

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Abstract: With broad ramifications for environmental issues, economic productivity, and safety, urban congestion continues to be a serious problem. This paper proposes an innovative solution, the Intelligent Traffic Signal System (ITSS), to this ubiquitous problem. Our ITSS dynamically adjusts traffic signal timings in real-time based on the analysis of real-time traffic data by utilizing cutting-edge technologies such as deep learning, image processing, and wireless sensor networks.

The review of the literature indicates a thorough investigation of novel traffic control strategies, including fuzzy logic, RFID technology, and computational intelligence. Our ITSS seeks to improve traffic flow, boost the effectiveness of the transportation infrastructure, and shorten travel times by combining components of these strategies. The integration of various technologies makes it possible to take into account variables like emergencies in a comprehensive way, which promotes flexible and effective traffic management.

In order to gather traffic data in real time, the suggested methodology entails placing sensors and cameras in strategic locations. When this data is processed using sophisticated algorithms and machine learning techniques, the best possible signal timings are produced that are specific to the flow of traffic. In order to provide a reliable and responsive system, the workflow includes image capture, processing, and object detection.

The study concludes by highlighting the importance of real-time analytics and data-driven decision-making in developing adaptive traffic signal control strategies. ITSS becomes a key component in streamlining traffic, cutting emissions, and raising the standard of urban living as smart cities develop. Transportation systems that are intelligent and optimized are made possible by the combination of artificial intelligence, sensor technology, and connectivity.

By offering a complex solution that combines multiple technologies to address urban congestion methodically, this research advances the field. Future research will evaluate the

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ITSS's applicability in the real world through testing and validation. With cities expanding and mobility needs rising, the suggested system is a model for clever, sustainable, and effective urban transportation planning.

Keywords: Deep Learning, Reinforcement Learning, Image Processing, Wireless Sensor Networks, RFID Technology, Computational Intelligence, Temporal Difference, Traffic Pattern Analysis, Computer Vision.

OP-161

“Artificial Intelligence (AI) & Its Role in Health Care, Medical Education And Research”

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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI): Also K/A Machine Intelligence, Refers To Set Of Technologies Enabling Computers To Perform A Variety Of Advanced Functions, Including Intensively Complex Tasks.

HISTORICAL ASPECTS- Initiated In 1950s, Name ‘AI’ Was Coined By – “Father Of AI”: John McCarthy *Ada Lovelace:"Mother Of AI“ & *‘AI’ First CEO: Mika(Not Human).

‘AI’ VARIETIES: Cloud, Azure, CHATGPT (Chat-Generative Pre-Trained Transformer), Google AI Research, Techopedia, AI Real Life, Strong AI- Philosophy, Reactive Machines, Limited Memory Machines, Theory Of Mind, Self-Awareness, Generative AI– Experimental, Machine Learning (ML) Etc.

Responsible AI Design:(3) Key Pillars; A.R.T- Accountability, Responsibility, Transparency

‘AI’ ROLE IN HEALTH CARE: ‘AI’ Delivers- More Accurate: * Diagnostics; Treatment Plans, * Predictive; Proactive Big Data Analysis For QOL Improvement, Preventive Care Recommendations, Predicting Disease Spread, * Administrative Applications With Reduced Human Error & 24/7 Patient Services, * Automating Processes.

‘AI’ Has Significant Important Role In- Robotics : Mental Health : Cardiology : Radio-Dx Etc. Medical Records Management Deptt. , Medical Transcription, Telemedicine, Epidemic; Pandemic Scenarios & Others. “Deep Learning AI” Helps To- Detect Diseases Faster, Provide Personalized Treatment Plans, Automate Certain Processes, Such As Drug Discovery & Diagnostics. Healthcare ‘AI’ Future- In India & Aound The World, Is Fast Growing And Has Huge Economic Potentials. Health Care ‘AI’ Impact – Strengthening, Facilitating Improved Health Care Delivery Systems Yet, AI Won't Replace Doctors, But Doctors Who Don't Use AI Will Be Replaced. Generative AI: Available Best Medical SoftWares: Hippocratic AI; Enhancing Medical Diagnosis, Merative AI; Health Data Management, Enlitic AI; Reading Medical Images, Regard AI; Predictive Healthcare Analytics, Twill Health AI; Personalized Patient Care, Viz. AI: Stroke Detection & Various Up Coming Others.

‘AI’ ROLE IN MEDICAL EDUCATION - ‘AI’ - Has Significantly Important Role In Medical Education With Potential To Facilitate Complicated Tasks & Improve Efficiency.

ChatGPT Use Can Provide Interactive Environments To Practice Communication Skills With Simulated Patients & DALL-E Is Used For Practicing Diagnostic Imaging Skills. Designing To Mimic Real-World Scenarios Maximally, Providing A Safe Environment For Learning And Practice Skills Is Achievable. With Advantage Of Quick Responses For FAQs, Rendering Accessible Medical Education For All Anytime And Anywhere, Yet Cannot Replace Human Teachers. The Only Disadvantage; Reduced Human Interaction.

‘AI’ ROLE IN HEALTHCARE RESEARCH-‘AI’ Applications Continuous Rapid Accelerated Growth With Involved Potential Uses Across The Healthcare Sector (Both Physical And Mental Health) Includes- Drug Discovery; Virtual Clinical Consultation; Disease Diagnosis; Prognosis; Medication Management And Health Monitoring With Advantages Of- Speed, Precision, Cost-Effectiveness, & Improved Outcomes Than Traditional Methods, Facilitate “Bio-Medical Research” Processings. For Biomedical Research AI’s Established Beneficial Role With Availability Of Several Different Tools Involving All Components & Stages Of Research Publication Including Plagiarism Is Authentically Well Recognized. Several Tools, Search Engines For Research, Thesis Writing Are Available, Latest- Google BARD AI Tools.

DEEP FAKE: - Also K/A Synthetic AI (Form Of Generative AI) - Technology Based Upon Deep Learning & Fake: Synthesisizing Media (Audios, Videos, Images, Real Time Or Live Etc.) - Can Be Weaponized To Do Harm & Hence Needed Legal Involvements.

KEY WORDS- 1. AI- Machine Intelligence 2. Health Care 3. Medical Education
4. Medical Research 5. Emerging: Available Tools- Technologies

OP-162

Role of Public Relations Strategies in the success of Tamil Movies

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Abstract: This research delves into the globalization of Tamil cinema, popularly known as "Kollywood," exploring the multifaceted factors that contribute to its international success. Against the backdrop of a rich storytelling tradition and cultural diversity, Tamil films have transcended geographical boundaries, captivating audiences worldwide. The study investigates the pivotal role of promotional strategies and public relations (PR) in propelling Tamil movies onto the global stage. Utilizing a mixed-methods approach, the research addresses questions regarding the influence of promotional strategies on viewer choices, the impact of PR on cinematic narratives, and the interplay between cultural identities and promotional tactics. Historical contexts, theoretical frameworks, and empirical studies form the basis for a comprehensive literature review. The research aims to shed light on how the digital era, diaspora communities, streaming platforms, and collaborations with international talent contribute to the globalization of Tamil cinema. By analyzing key films and industry trends, the study provides insights into the evolving dynamics of film promotion in the globalized landscape.

Keywords: Tamil cinema, Kollywood, globalization, promotional strategies, public relations, diaspora communities, digital platforms, film industry, cultural identities, mixed methods.

OP-163

Unlocking Opportunities: The Expansive Scope of Artificial Intelligence in Digital Marketing

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Abstract: The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in digital marketing has become a pivotal force, reshaping the landscape of how businesses connect with their target audiences. This research paper explores the vast scope of AI in digital marketing, examining its impact on various facets of the industry, from customer engagement and data analytics to personalized content delivery and predictive marketing strategies. By delving into case studies, current trends, and future possibilities, this paper aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the transformative power that AI holds within the realm of digital marketing. This research paper aims to investigate the evolving landscape of digital marketing with the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies. It delves into the various applications of AI in digital marketing, assessing its impact on efficiency, personalization, and overall campaign effectiveness. The paper employs a comprehensive literature review, case studies, and industry examples to illustrate the significant role that AI plays in reshaping the digital marketing landscape. Through an exploration of current trends and future possibilities, this research seeks to provide insights into the expansive scope of AI in the field of digital marketing.

OP-164

Effect of heavy metal pollution on vegetable crops and its mitigation

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Abstract: Heavy metals are naturally occurring elements, but human activities such as industrial processes, mining, and the use of certain agricultural inputs can lead to their accumulation in the soil and subsequent uptake by plants. Heavy metal pollution can have significant adverse effects on vegetable crops, posing risks to both human health and the environment. Heavy metals, such as lead, cadmium, and mercury, can negatively impact plant growth and development. They can interfere with various physiological processes, including nutrient uptake and photosynthesis, leading to stunted growth and reduced crop yields. Excessive concentrations of heavy metals in the soil can lead to toxicity in plants. Different metals have different toxic thresholds for different crops. For example, cadmium is known to be highly toxic to many plants, and its accumulation in edible plant parts, such as fruits and vegetables, can pose health risks to consumers. Some heavy metals have a high affinity for accumulating in specific plant tissues, particularly in the edible parts of vegetables. This bioaccumulation can result in the concentration of heavy metals in the food chain, leading to potential health risks for humans who consume contaminated crops. Heavy metals can compete with essential nutrients for uptake by plant roots. This competition can result in nutrient imbalances within the plants, affecting their nutritional quality and making them less suitable for consumption.

To mitigate the effects of heavy metal pollution on vegetable crops, it is essential to monitor and regulate industrial activities, practice sustainable agricultural methods, and implement proper waste disposal and remediation techniques for contaminated soils. Additionally, regular testing of soil and crops for heavy metal content can help identify and address potential risks to both the environment and human health.

Keywords: Heavy metal pollution, mitigation, lead, cadmium, mercury, bioaccumulation, productivity, human health, etc.

OP-165

Prevalence of pre frailty and frailty among Indian adults: An application of discriminant analysis using LASI data

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Abstract: To truly create a thorough understanding of pre-frail and frailty, it is imperative to determine which aspects of the frailty phenotype yield the most meaningful information. This paper has examined the onset of pre-frailty and frailty in three age groups: 45–59, 60–74, and 75+. Each component of frailty may have unique screening properties, offering several ways to diagnose and assess frailty more accurately. Additionally, this study looks into the characteristic that distinguishes between a robust and a frailty condition in India by different age group. Secondary data (LASI wave1–2017–18) were used in this study. This study concentrated on the individuals in the LASI dataset who were 45 years of age or older. This study made considerable use of LASI biomarker data. A total of 59917 adults (27795 males and 32122 females) were enrolled for study after the missing cases were eliminated. In this study frailty criterion is based on Fried concept of a physical frailty phenotype, comprising unintentional weight loss, exhaustion, low physical activity, slow walking, and weak muscles. Prevalence of pre frailty and frailty among 45+ age group were 65.9% and 22.8%. Low physical activity is the most prevalent component among individual who are pre frail in 45-59 and 60-74 age group while in a 75+ age group weakness is the prevalent component. The diagnostic accuracy of fried frailty phenotype components in India by different age group was calculated in this study. Low physical activity and weakness shows sensitivity more than 90% which appeared to be a good indicator of frailty across all age group. A discriminant analysis aimed to identify the variables that discriminate between robust and frailty conditions in two age groups (45-59 and 60+). Only depression and IADL is strong predictor in 45-59 age groups whereas in 60+ age group IADL, cognition, depression, and morbidity are the strong predictors. This study is the first of its kind in India that investigates the most crucial components of the frailty phenotype that significantly contribute to an individual's vulnerability to adverse health outcomes in adults (45-59) and older adults (60+). This study proposes that proactive measures can be taken to hinder the early onset of pre frailty and mitigate its progression into full frailty.

Keywords: Robust, Pre frail, Frail, Adults.

OP-166

Digital Disruption: Transforming the Banking Landscape

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Abstract:

This research investigates the profound transformation in the banking sector as a result of digital disruption. Focused on understanding the multifaceted dimensions of this transformation, the study explores the strategies, challenges, and opportunities that emerge as traditional banking undergoes significant change. Through the analysis of case studies, industry trends, and technological advancements, the research aims to unravel the intricate dynamics of digital disruption and its impact on financial institutions. The findings contribute to a broader understanding of how technology is reshaping banking services, providing insights into the strategies employed by banks to adapt and excel in the digital era. This research is intended to offer valuable perspectives for industry stakeholders, policymakers, and scholars navigating the ongoing journey of digital disruption in the banking sector.

Keywords: Banks, Digitalization, Digital disruption, Digital Transformation

OP-167

The Role of AI and Education Research in Shaping a Sustainable Future

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence is the science of making machines that can think like humans. It can do things that are considered "smart." AI technology can process large amounts of data in ways, unlike humans. The goal for AI is to be able to do things such as recognize patterns, make decisions, and judge like humans. AI Contributions to Sustainable Development

It aids in analysing climate data, predicting extreme weather events, and improving disaster preparedness. AI algorithms help optimize renewable energy deployment, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and promote sustainable practices.

The Grade scope AI tool enables students to assess each other while providing feedback, which are often time-consuming tasks without AI technology. Grade scope relies on a combination of machine learning (ML) and AI to make it easier to grade, which saves time and energy Tech companies use AI to optimize data centre energy consumption and emissions. Vendors throughout the food supply chain use AI and analytics for predicting demand, thereby reducing waste and losses. The fashion industry suffers from high return rates, and returned clothing ultimately ends up in landfills.

Development of 21st Century Skills

Through simulations and interactive scenarios, students can apply their knowledge in real-world situations. Every student is different, and some may have special needs. AI can identify students who need additional support and provide specific resources for their needs.

Benefits of AI in Education1. Personalized Learning: AI adapts content to individual learning styles and paces, addressing diverse needs within a classroom. 2. Enhanced Engagement: AI-driven tools, such as gamified learning apps and virtual tutors, make learning more interactive and enjoyable. AI Contributions to Sustainable Development

It aids in analysing climate data, predicting extreme weather events, and improving disaster preparedness. AI algorithms help optimize renewable energy deployment, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and promote sustainable practices. AI provides valuable feedback to teachers and students. Some higher education institutions are using AI systems to keep an eye on

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learners' improvements and to prepare the teachers if there is any matter with student presentation. Various AI systems permit learners to obtain the guidance they require.

Spectroscopic Study of Interaction of the Chlorophyll and Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles

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Abstract

Engineered metal oxide nanoparticles have recently gained attention owing to their wide spread use in consumer based products. It is expected that metallic oxide nanoparticles will find their way into atmospheric, terrestrial and aquatic environment, where their fate and behavior are largely unknown. Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles are being used in nano-electronic/nano-optical devices, energy storage, cosmetic products, nanosensors etc. With the increase in the level of nanoparticles in the atmosphere due to anthropogenic activities it is essential to study the reaction dynamics involving bio macromolecules with nanoparticles due to large surface area and high reactivity. The reactivity of the nanomaterial with biomolecules is dependent on the concentration, size, and shape of the nanoparticles. The present investigation describes spectroscopic study of the interaction of chlorophyll molecule with different concentrations of zinc oxide nanoparticles (20mM, 100mM, 200mM, 300mM, 400mM, 500mM, 600mM and 800 mM) of size 30 nm using laser induced fluorescence, and ATR-FTIR spectroscopy techniques. The chlorophyll molecule from the leaves of Onion plant has been extracted in methanol. The steady state and time resolved laser induced fluorescence spectra of the chlorophyll molecule with different concentration of ZnO nanoparticles have been recorded. The obtained spectrum shows decrease in the fluorescence signal of the bands at wavelengths 680 nm and 730 nm followed by increase in the fluorescence signal ratio (F_{680}/F_{730}) indicating instability of chlorophyll molecule. In addition, the time resolved fluorescence measurements indicate a drastic decrease in the life time of chlorophyll molecule up to 100 mM ZnO nanoparticles and at higher concentration life time increases but it is always smaller than the life time of chlorophyll molecule. The ATR-FTIR spectra of the chlorophyll and with different concentration of ZnO nanoparticles have been recorded in the spectral region 480-4000 cm^{-1} . The study reveals changes in the conformation of the chlorophyll molecule.

THE INSIGHT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) IN DRUG DISCOVERY AND DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

From the last few years, there has been a huge increase in data digitalization in the pharmaceutical field. But it brought up the challenge like acquiring, scrutinizing, and applying that knowledge to solve complex clinical problems [1]. The motivation of using the AI is due to its ability to handle large volumes of data with enhanced automation [2]. AI is a technology-based mechanism involving many advanced tools and networks that can mimic intelligence like humans. At the same time, it does not threaten to replace human physical presence [3,4] completely. AI can interpret and learn from the input data to make independent decisions for accomplishing important objectives by using certain systems and software. Some of the applications of ai are continuously being extended in the pharmaceutical field. The role of artificial intelligence (AI) in medicinal chemistry has been enhanced in previous years as a potent means of revolutionizing the pharmaceutical industry [5]. Drug discovery, it is the process of identifying and developing new medications, it is complex and time-consuming job that traditionally relies on techniques, such as trial-and-error experimentation and high-screening at every step. However, Machine learning (ML) and natural language processing are some of the techniques of AI which offer the potential to increase and improvise the process by enabling more efficient and accurate analysis of large amounts of data [6]. Recently use of deep learning (DL) to predict the efficacy of drug compounds with high accuracy has been described by the authors of [7]. Researches going on have highlighted the capacity of AI to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of drug discovery processes. By considering Ethical norms into account, and further research is much needed to fully understand the pros and cons of AI in this area [8]. Although there are challenges, but in future AI is expected to contribute in the development of new medications and therapies .

UNLOCKING NATURE'S SECRET: HOW IS AI REVOLUTIONISING NATURAL PRODUCT DISCOVERY IN MEDICINAL PLANT (DATURA STRAMONIUM)

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to revolutionize the drug discovery process, offering improved efficiency, accuracy, and speed. However, the successful application of AI is dependent on the availability of high-quality data, the addressing of ethical concerns, and the recognition of the limitations of AI-based approaches. In this article, the benefits, challenges, and drawbacks of AI in this field are involved and possible strategies and approaches for overcoming the present obstacles are proposed. The use of data augmentation, explainable AI, and the integration of AI with traditional experimental methods, as well as the potential advantages of AI in pharmaceutical research is applied for medicinal plant (Datura stramonium). Overall, it highlights the potential of AI in drug discovery in medicinal plant and provides insights into the challenges and opportunities for realizing its potential in this field. AI can facilitate virtual screening of large compound databases against specific biological targets. This can help identify potential therapeutic compounds in medicinal plants, saving time and resources compared to traditional screening methods. AI applications in chemoinformatics can analyze the chemical structure of plant compounds and predict their biological activities. Machine learning algorithms can be trained on known medicinal compounds to develop predictive models. These models can then be used to analyze the chemical composition of plants and predict potential bioactive compounds, streamlining the discovery process. AI-driven robotic systems can automate laboratory experiments, enabling high-throughput screening of plant extracts for bioactivity. This accelerates the pace of discovery and allows researchers to explore a broader range of possibilities. AI can process vast amounts of data, including information from scientific literature, traditional medicine practices, and experimental results. This ability allows researchers to analyze and integrate diverse data sources to identify potential medicinal compounds in plants more efficiently. AI can help analyze vast datasets related to Datura stramonium, including information on its chemical

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composition, traditional uses, and potential medicinal properties. This data analysis can reveal patterns and correlations that help in identifying bioactive compounds. Keywords: artificial intelligence, drug discovery, AI-assisted content generation, AI-limitations, Medicinal plant, Datura stramonium

Unleashing the Power of Artificial Intelligence in E-commerce for Enhanced Customer Experiences and Business Optimization

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Abstract:

When the term "artificial intelligence" is mentioned, popular culture often conjures images from movies such as Steven Spielberg's A.I. Artificial Intelligence (2001), the sci-fi thriller Ex Machina, or the cult classic Blade Runner from 1982. However, within the e-commerce sector, the focus shifts away from humanoid robots and leans more towards learning technologies and algorithms as the foundational elements.

In the realm of today's online retail landscape, AI plays a pivotal role in enabling businesses to deliver an enhanced customer experience both on and off their e-commerce platforms. By leveraging collected business and customer data, AI facilitates informed decision-making and more accurate predictions about the future. As a transformative force, Artificial Intelligence (AI) presents unprecedented opportunities for refining customer experiences and optimizing various aspects of e-commerce operations. This article investigates the manifold applications of artificial intelligence (AI) in the e-commerce realm, underscoring its capacity to reshape customer relationships, streamline business operations, and elevate overall operational efficiency.

Keyword: Artificial Intelligence, E-commerce, Power, Business Optimization

OP-172

Lipid Profile in People Living with HIV/AIDS

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Abstract:

Studies have shown that PLHIV have higher levels of total cholesterol, triglycerides, and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol, and lower levels of high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol compared to HIV-negative individuals. Total study population was 89 patients. We have found the increase in the dyslipidemia in the persons living with HIV on treatment with increasing years of treatment. There was increase in LDL, Total cholesterol, Triglycerides, and decrease in HDL. There was decrease in renal function and increased prevalence in Diabetes as the years of treatment increases. CD4 count is decreasing as the years of treatment increases. Our study has some limitations being that the groups are not equally distributed, the changes in medications and other acute diseases were not taken into considerations.

Key words: Dyslipidemia, **People Living with HIV/AIDS**, CD4 count

Novel Methods for the Preparation of Peppermint Oil Microspheres

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Abstract

Microencapsulation is one of the novel methods for the delivery of active constituents with enhanced therapeutic effects. Peppermint oil possesses many pharmacological activities like anti-inflammatory, insect repellent, antispasmodic, anti-tumor, nerve stimulator, and many more. The main challenge in the case of essential oil is its volatility. The drawback can be overcome by the encapsulation method. Gas-liquid chromatography of extracted oil indicates the presence of Menthone, Menthyl acetate, Iso-neomenthone, etc., Microencapsulate form of peppermint oil prepared by three different methods. The maximum particle size distribution is in the range of 3.05-micron meters. The broad peak obtained in the range of 3440.584 cm^{-1} signifies the vibration of –OH groups in FTIR.

Keywords: Peppermint oil, Microspheres, Encapsulation, Menthone, Ethylcellulose

TEMPORAL AND STRUCTURAL CHANGES IN COST AND RETURNS IN FINGER MILLET (*Eleusine coracana*) CULTIVATION IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

This study assesses the growth trends in Cost A1, C2, C3, gross returns, and yield in the context of Finger millet (*Ragi*) cultivation across various states in India. Over an eighteen-year period (2004-05 to 2021-22), an analysis was conducted to examine the percentage change in Cost A1, C2, C3, as well as expenditures on seed, fertilizer, manures, human labor, and animal labor. The findings revealed an upward trajectory in Cost A1 for Finger millet (*Ragi*) cultivation across all Indian states, surpassing Cost C3. This suggests a swifter increase in input and paid-out costs in comparison to indirect expenses like land rent and fixed capital interest. Notably, Tamil Nadu exhibited the highest growth in Cost C at 46.02%. Negative yield changes were observed in Tamil Nadu and Maharashtra, whereas Karnataka demonstrated improved performance. In terms of expenditure, the percentage increase in spending on chemical fertilizer was lower compared to manures, despite both inputs experiencing a substantial overall increase. This analysis sheds light on the intricate dynamics of cost components and agricultural performance in Finger millet (*Ragi*) cultivation across diverse states in India.

KEYWORDS: Cost, Finger millet (*Ragi*), Temporal and Structural Changes

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